

Ph.D. Dissertation

Method for Air-tightness Prediction using Airflow Characteristics in High-Rise Residential Buildings

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The Graduate School
Sungkyunkwan University
Department of Civil, Architectural and
Environment System Engineering

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Abstract

Method for Air-tightness Prediction using Airflow Characteristics in High-Rise Residential Buildings

As modern buildings become taller and more air-tight, it has become extremely important to accurately determine their air-tightness. This is because the amount of ventilation varies depending on the air-tightness level of the building, and the amount of ventilation is closely related to the indoor air quality and energy use intensity.

Representative methods for measuring air-tightness include the tracer gas method and the fan pressurization method. In the tracer gas method, although the air-tightness of the entire building can be measured using this method, the air-tightness of the components of the building cannot be measured.

In contrast, the air-tightness of a building's components can be measured using a blower door test, which is a typical fan pressurization method. However, the blower door test has certain limitations including a complex measurement preparation process, high cost, and problems at measurement process. Therefore, in this study, a simple method for predicting the air-tightness was developed that could address the problems and limitations of conventional air-tightness measurement methods.

This paper proposed a novel method for predicting the air-tightness of building components using the differential pressure generated by the stack effect in high-rise residential buildings. As with the principle of a blower door test, the concept of the proposed method was established using the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume. The air volume was measured by a fan used in a blower door test. The novelty of this study lies in the fact that the air

volume could be determined by measuring only two sets of differential pressures rather than measuring the air volume using a fan. The equations and processes proposed here could also be applied to actual buildings. As prerequisites of the proposed processes, the direction of airflow must be clear owing to the stack effect, the differential pressure must be formed over a certain level, and an air leakage report must be secured for a single component in the main airflow path. An air leakage report for a single component is relatively easy to obtain. The proposed method was evaluated on an actual building to verify its validity.

To generalize the method proposed in this paper, all measurements and analyses were conducted under different conditions by varying the building heights, indoor and outdoor temperatures, and the number of floors of each building. The relationship between pressure difference, temperature difference, height difference, and percentage errors for the predicted results was analyzed by the Pearson's correlation analysis. Also, a 95% confidence interval in the measured pressurization and depressurization results by blower door test was derived. Based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval for each building, the minimum differential pressure was at least 24 Pa. Based on the applicable 24 Pa, acceptable conditions in which the predicted and measured values were consistent for all buildings were $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,000$ m·°C. When the predicted results at the derived 95% confidence interval were statistically evaluated using the indicators (NMSE, FB, and FS) suggested in the ASTM Guide D5157-97, the values calculated for the proposed method met the criteria for adequate model performance. If the applicable pressure difference and acceptable conditions can be satisfied, the air-tightness is predicted under actual living conditions using the method proposed in this paper instead of the blower door test.

Keywords: Air-tightness prediction, Pressure difference, Residential building,
Actual living conditions, Building envelope

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

Owing to the growing population density, the demand for high-rise buildings has increased [1] (Figure 1-1). The high-rise residential buildings with 40 floors or more have been constructed as multi-household apartments. In particular, a skyscraper is defined as a building with a height of 200 m or more or 50 stories or more, and a total of 124 skyscrapers have been built in South Korea by 2020. Table 1-1 shows the number of skyscrapers by region in Korea by 2020, Seoul have the most with 39, followed by Busan with 25 and Incheon with 24 [2]. As the height of a building increases, the stack effect in the building becomes extreme. Accordingly, various problems are created, such as difficulties in opening and closing doors, increased noise, strong winds from elevators, increased movement of viruses and odors, deterioration in indoor air quality, and increased building energy consumption through infiltration.

Figure 1-1 Construction of high-rise buildings by year

Table 1-1 Number of skyscraper by region in South Korea by 2020

Region	Number of skyscraper	Region	Number of skyscraper
Seoul	39	Daegu	8
Busan	25	Ulsan	4
Incheon	24	Gyeongbuk and Gyeongnam	3
Gyeonggi	20	Chungnam	1

Air-tight construction techniques and products have been used to address these problems [3-4] (Table 1-2 and Figure 1-2), establish a pleasant indoor environment, and reduce building energy consumption [5]. It is extremely important to accurately evaluate the air-tightness level of buildings as the height of buildings increases and they become more air-tight. This is because the amount of ventilation varies depending on the air-tightness level of the building, and the amount of ventilation is closely related to the indoor air quality. In addition, various strategies are being applied to reduce building energy consumption; these include enhancing building insulation and air-tightness, improving HVAC systems and equipment efficiency, and developing energy-saving controls [6]. Building energy is closely related to air-tightness (infiltration). Improving the level of air-tightness in a building is particularly important when minimizing building energy demand [7-8]. Moreover, with improvements in insulation performance, up to 30% of the heating demand in winter is owing to infiltration [9]. This is because infiltration must be maintained in an appropriate state to avoid indoor thermal discomfort. During this time, load fluctuations owing to the operation of cooling and heating systems in rooms can occur, resulting in higher energy costs. It is therefore extremely important to understand the level of air-tightness of the building because the air-tightness of a building envelope significantly affects the heating and cooling load [6].

Table 1-2 Air-tight construction techniques and products

Construction	Window frame	Pipe and duct	Masonry wall	Electrical wiring
Material	Sealant, air-tight tape	Sealant, air-tight tape	Insulation urethane foam, air-tight tape	Air-tight socket and tape
Process	Window construction (before insulation construction)	Before masonry work	Before plastering work	After interior construction
Location	Window frame-structure connection	AD/PD upright piping	Masonry wall pipe penetration area	Distribution board of households

Figure 1-2 Air-tight construction methods

The Korean government also mandates the measurement of air-tightness through various systems. A zero-energy building certification system has been introduced for both public and private buildings to realize mandatory zero-energy design by 2025. A zero-energy building certification must meet three criteria: a building energy efficiency of grade 1⁺⁺ or higher, an energy independence rate of 20% or higher, and the installation of a BEMS or remote electronic meter [10]. According to the building energy efficiency level certification and zero-energy building certification standard, air-tightness measurements must be conducted to calculate Energy Use Intensity (EUI) in the actual building. In principle, the air-tightness (h^{-1}) must be measured

at 50 Pa per household in apartment using a blower door test by randomly selecting three households for each plane type apartment [11-12]. The government also mandates the measurement of air-tightness through other systems including standard construction specifications and energy-saving design standards for buildings [13-14].

Because the building envelope is the main infiltration and leakage path, other countries have also made it mandatory to require a certain air-tightness level in the building envelope. The air-tightness of the building envelope can be classified into that of three items, i.e., the curtain wall, component, and envelope. Each item also requires to have a certain level of air-tightness according to various standards including DIN EN 12152 [15], Singapore Standard SS 381 [16], ASHRAE Standard 90.1 [17], and DIN EN 12207 [18].

The air-tightness of a building is also used as an input condition in simulations when predicting the energy consumption, which may fluctuate owing to factors other than the performance level of the building [19]. In addition, the air-tightness is used as an input condition for simulations analyzing airflows through multi-zone modeling [20]. The input conditions in simulations must be accurate for a reliable prediction; the predicted results can be extremely different from the actual results depending on the air-tightness input used in an airflow simulation. Therefore, air-tightness must be accurately measured [21].

Representative methods used to measure the air-tightness of a building include the tracer gas method and the fan pressurization method. The details of each method, including their principle and method of measurement, related criteria, related research, and limitations will be covered in Chapter 2. ASTM E741-00 [22] describes three tracer gas test methods. A widely used method is the CO₂ concentration decay test method, which is based on natural decay as a result of dilution through the infiltration of outdoor air. The concentration decay data are fitted to an exponential curve and the air changes per hour (ACH) are obtained. Another representative method for measuring the building air-tightness is the fan pressurization method, which has been used for

almost 50 years [23]. In this method, a building is pressurized or depressurized using an air conditioning system or fan, and the air-tightness is then obtained by measuring the volume of airflow at a given difference in the internal/external static pressure [24]. The CO₂ decay method is used to determine the amount of infiltration for the entire building; however, it is impossible to measure the air-tightness of a specific component of a building, such as the building envelope, which is a limitation of this method. On the other hand, the blower door test causes various problems because a high differential pressure condition must be formed in the building, which differs from actual building conditions.

Therefore, this paper proposes a simple method that can address the limitations of conventional air-tightness measurement methods. The proposed method can determine air-tightness by measuring the differential pressure naturally generated in the actual building based on the stack effect. First, through a literature review, the relationship between the differential pressure and the air-tightness in a building is established, and the principle or theoretical validity of the proposed method is verified. In addition, formulas and processes that can be applied in real buildings are presented, and the validity of the proposed processes is verified through a case study conducted on an actual building. Finally, through various case studies, the proposed method is generalized such that it can be applied to all buildings.

1.2 Research process and contribution

In this paper, a new method for measuring the air-tightness in high-rise residential buildings is proposed. First, the relationship between differential pressure and air-tightness is examined through basic theory, principles, and the method by which the differential pressure and air-tightness are formed in a high-rise building. The limitations of existing air-tightness measurement methods are then analyzed through a literature review. Based on the analysis, the principle and

theoretical validity of a new method for measuring air-tightness that can address existing limitations are established. In addition, the validity of the formula used in the proposed method is verified. The air-tightness is predicted by measuring the differential pressure on an actual building in order to apply the proposed method and compare its results with those determined using a blower door test. Finally, the proposed method is generalized to all buildings by predicting the air-tightness under various conditions including different buildings, temperatures, and heights. The following presents the scope and methods used in this study and describes the focus of each chapter.

Chapter 2: Pressure difference and air-tightness in buildings

In this chapter, through a review of the literature, factors influencing the driving force for airflows in a building were investigated. The factors influencing the differential pressure formed by the stack effect in the building were also analyzed. In addition, the relationship between the differential pressure generated and the air-tightness in the building was analyzed, and the theoretical validity of the proposed method was verified.

The theoretical validity of the proposed method's formula was verified by analyzing the definitions and principles behind conventional air-tightness measurement methods. Moreover, the rationale behind this study was discussed by analyzing the problems and limitations of conventional air-tightness measurement methods. The novelty of this study was presented through a review of existing research on the measurement and prediction of air-tightness using conventional measurement methods and various other techniques.

Chapter 3: Development of a new method to measure air-tightness

This chapter discusses the method proposed in this paper. The concept of the proposed method was established based on the principle of existing air-tightness measurement methods covered in the previous chapter. In addition, the originality of the proposed method was highlighted by discussing the differences between this study and existing studies. A new equation

was proposed to measure air-tightness using differential pressure, and the theoretical validity of the equation was verified. In addition, a specific process was proposed so that the equation could be applied to actual buildings.

A case study was conducted on an actual building to verify the validity of the proposed method. The air-tightness was predicted using the proposed method by measuring the differential pressure in the actual building. To verify the validity, the results obtained were compared with the air-tightness measured using the blower door test.

Chapter 4: Evaluation of the proposed method for air-tightness prediction

This final chapter aimed to generalize the method proposed in this paper. In the previous chapter, a high-rise residential building was used as a case study of the proposed method. In addition, a pressure difference was largely formed because the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was large. Therefore, the air-tightness predicted by the proposed method was similar to the air-tightness measured by the blower door test.

This chapter revealed whether the method proposed in this paper could be employed even under conditions of a small pressure difference. As the proposed method aims to predict the air-tightness by using the differential pressure generated by the stack effect in a building, various conditions were investigated by varying factors such as the temperature and height of the building.

Case studies were conducted for low- and mid-rise buildings, which were relatively small in height compared to the buildings considered in the previous chapter. The differential pressure was measured on each floor for each building, and the air-tightness was predicted using the measured differential pressure. A blower door test was also used to measure the air-tightness at the same points where the differential pressure was measured; this measured air-tightness was compared with the predicted air-tightness. The percentage errors of the predicted results were used to examine the dependence on the differences between indoor and outdoor temperatures as well as height differences, which are the main factors affecting the differential pressure. Based on the

dependence on both factors, it was possible to predict the air-tightness through the proposed method even under low differential pressure conditions. The relationship between pressure difference, temperature difference, height difference, and percentage errors for the predicted results was analyzed by the Pearson's correlation analysis. Also, a 95% confidence interval in the measured pressurization and depressurization results by blower door test was derived. Based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval for each building, the minimum differential pressure condition that could be applied to the proposed method in this study was presented. Based on the applicable pressure difference, acceptable conditions in which the predicted and measured values were consistent for all buildings were suggested. The acceptable condition is suggested by existing air-tightness measurement standards such as ASTM Standard E779-03, ISO 9972, and EN 13829 as $\Delta H \times \Delta T$. The predicted results at the derived 95% confidence interval were statistically evaluated using the indicators (NMSE, FB, and FS) suggested in the ASTM Guide D5157-97.

The research process used in this study is shown in Figure 1-3.

Figure 1-3 Research process

Chapter 2 Pressure difference and air-tightness in buildings

In this chapter, to propose a new method for measuring the air-tightness using the differential pressure, the influencing factors and principles behind the generation of an airflow driving force in a building were reviewed. In addition, the concepts and principles behind the formation of a differential pressure in a building, along with its influencing factors, were established, and the relationship between the differential pressure and air-tightness of a building was determined.

The validity of the formula used in the proposed method was confirmed by the principles of conventional air-tightness measurement methods. The proposed method was then enhanced by addressing the limitations of conventional air-tightness measurement methods. The existing conditions for measuring air-tightness were identified by examining the relevant standards of each air-tightness measurement approach.

Finally, the novelty of the method proposed here was highlighted through a review of existing research on air-tightness measurement and prediction methods.

2.1 Theoretical background

2.1.1 Driving force for airflow in a building

As shown in Figure 2-1 [25], the driving force of an airflow in a building is affected due to external winds, the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures, and the pressure generated by mechanical ventilation systems. Factors influencing the airflow can be classified into environmental, architectural, facility, and occupant factors.

Environmental factors include the external wind (direction and speed), outdoor air temperature (indoor/outdoor temperature difference), and regional characteristics around the building. The external wind depends largely on two factors that determine the driving force of the

air inside the building. The external wind differs according to the geographic and regional characteristics of the surrounding area and acts differently depending on the shape of the building. The wind acts as a pressure (wind pressure) on the building envelope, which induces airflow inside the building. The difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures acts as a static pressure on the building owing to the difference in the weight (density) and buoyancy of the indoor and outdoor air, thus generating a vertical airflow.

The mechanical ventilation system pressurizes or depressurizes the target space through a fan, causing a pressure change in the space and artificially creating an airflow. The air volume depends on the size of the mechanical ventilation system and is generally sized to fit the load, which must be taken into account because it can fluctuate based on the resistance in the duct.

The airflow driving force in the building is formed owing to the pressure difference generated by the external wind, the difference between the indoor/outdoor temperatures, and the mechanical ventilation system. The pressure distribution and airflow are determined according to the air-tightness of the entrance doors and partitions that exist on the horizontal and vertical airflow paths of the building. In an actual case, because the opening and closing state of doors is determined according to the living patterns of occupants, occupant behavior is a factor that changes the leaking area of the building. In addition, the driving force of an airflow in the building may vary depending on the operating conditions of an occupant's ventilation system.

The airflow in a building can be described using the Bernoulli equation. Equation (1) is Bernoulli's equation, for which the total head is always a constant and its value is preserved. The total head is the sum of the pressure head, velocity head, and position head. Figure 2-2 [26] shows that Bernoulli's equation is established as indicated in Equation (2) when an incompressible ideal gas flows in a steady stream in a tube. Because $\gamma = \rho \times g$, the equation can be transformed into Equation (3). Equation (4) [27] is used to determine the total pressure difference, which is the sum of the static pressure difference, the dynamic pressure difference in each zone, and the

pressure difference according to the height; it is expressed as the sum of the pressure due to the stack effect and the pressure due to the wind acting on the opening of the building envelope. Equation (4) shows the factors that create an airflow from due to the pressure difference in the building.

Figure 2-1 Influencing factors and effects of airflow in buildings

Figure 2-2 Normal flow of an incompressible ideal gas in a tube

$$\frac{P}{\gamma} + \frac{V^2}{2g} + Z = \text{Constant} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{P_1}{\gamma} + \frac{V_1^2}{2g} + Z_1 = \frac{P_2}{\gamma} + \frac{V_2^2}{2g} + Z_2 = H \text{ (Constant)} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta P = \left(P_1 + \frac{\rho V_1^2}{2} \right) - \left(P_2 + \frac{\rho V_2^2}{2} \right) + \rho g (Z_1 - Z_2) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta P = P_j - P_i + P_s + P_w \quad (4)$$

where P/γ is the pressure head (m), $V^2/2g$ is the speed head (m), Z is the position head (m), ΔP is the total pressure drop at two points (Pa), P_1 , P_2 are the positive pressure at the inlet and outlet (Pa), V_1 , V_2 are the flow rate at two points (m/s), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), g is the gravitational constant (9.81 m/s^2), Z_1 , Z_2 are the height of the inlet and outlet (m), P_j , P_i are the total pressure in the P_j and P_i zone (Pa), P_s is the stack pressure (Pa), and P_w is the wind pressure (Pa).

2.1.2 Factors forming a pressure difference in a building

The stack effect is the difference in pressure caused by the mass of a column of air located inside and outside a building [28]. The air pressure on the ground surface in winter is low inside the building based on the air pressure due to the weight of the air when the inside of the building is warm and the outside of the building is cold. Air that enters the building from the ground surface moves to the upper part of the building as a result of this pressure difference. Considering the

ideal gas law, the difference in temperature according to the cross-section of a building wall causes a difference in the density of air between the outside and inside. The pressure difference between the wall sections is the result of this difference in density, and the airflow caused by this pressure difference is defined as the stack or chimney effect. Although the stack effect is predominant in high-rise buildings owing to their size, in reality, it occurs in all types of buildings. During the summer, because the temperature inside a building is lower than that outdoors, the outdoor air enters the upper floors of the building and moves to the lower floors of the building, and an airflow that is opposite to the stack effect occurs. This is called the reverse stack effect. Theoretically, because the stack effect increases in proportion to the difference in indoor/outdoor temperatures, the reverse stack effect is not a significant problem. This is because the difference in indoor/outdoor temperatures is smaller than that during winter. In addition, a vertical position is created in which the pressure inside the building matches the pressure outside, which is called the neutral pressure level (NPL) of the building under the influence of the stack effect. The outside air pressure in the lower floors of the neutral zone is greater than the indoor pressure, and the external air pressure in the upper part is less than the indoor pressure; thus, the outside air flows into the interior in the lower part of the neutral zone, while air flows out from the interior in the upper part. Moreover, as the distance increases vertically from the neutral zone, the pressure difference increases. The neutral zone is theoretically located at the mid-height of the building; however, if there is a large opening in the upper floors of the building, the neutral zone is located at a point higher than the mid-height; conversely, if there is a large opening in the lower floors of the building, the neutral zone is located at a point lower than the mid-height [28-29]. In most high-rise residential buildings, the front door of a household is more air-tight than the external entrance door; thus a neutral zone is often formed below the mid-height point. The stack effect mainly occurs in the vertical space of the building, such as in an elevator shaft or stairwell, while the airflow mainly occurs in the building, as shown in Figure 2-3.

The pressure difference due to the stack effect is a function of the difference in weight (density) of the air column between the interior and exterior of the building and the vertical distance from the neutral zone. Assuming that the temperature and air pressure are constant at a specific height, the pressure due to the stack effect decreases constantly as the height increases. The pressure difference due only to the difference in air density can be expressed using Equation (5) [30]. According to the sign conventions, the pressure difference in the neutral zone becomes 0 and is a (+) value in the neutral zone, which is a condition in which pressure is applied to the room from the outside. In addition, it is a (-) value in the upper part of the neutral zone, which is a condition in which pressure is applied from the room to the outside.

Figure 2-3 Pressure distribution and airflow characteristics by the stack effect

However, in the case of an indoor temperature change in a high-rise building, Equation (5) should be modified to consider the change in air density according to the building height. The difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures causes a change in the pressure due to the stack effect, which in turn causes air to flow through the exterior wall of the building according

to the ideal gas law. The pressure difference due to the stack effect can be expressed using Equation (6), when the indoor air density decreases as the building height increases and the indoor/outdoor temperatures are considered [31-32]. The indoor and outdoor pressure distributions in the building are shown in Figure 2-4. The density of both the outdoor and indoor air is defined by air temperature, and in this case, Equation (6), which is the pressure difference due to the stack effect, is proportional to the distance from the neutral zone and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures. As indicated, the greater the external temperature difference, the greater is the pressure difference due to the stack effect.

Figure 2-4 Indoor and outdoor pressure profiles in buildings

$$P_s = P_r - \rho g H \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta P_s = (\rho_o - \rho_i) g (N - h) = \rho_o \left(\frac{T_i - T_o}{T_i} \right) g (N - h) \quad (6)$$

where P_s is the stack pressure (Pa), P_r is the stack pressure at reference height (Pa), g is the gravitational constant (9.81 m/s^2), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), and H is the height above reference

plane (m), ΔP_s is the pressure difference caused by stack effect (Pa), ρ_o is the outdoor air density (kg/m^3), ρ_i is the indoor air density (kg/m^3), N is the height of neutral pressure level above reference plane without any other driving forces (m), h is the height of interest (m), T_o is the outdoor temperature (K), and T_i is the indoor temperature (K).

2.1.3 Relationship between pressure difference and air-tightness in a building

A pressure difference and an airflow path are required to generate an airflow, and the amount of airflow is influenced by the magnitude of the differential pressure and the (air-tightness) resistance to blocking the airflow along its path. In a building, the pressure difference is caused by the wind and the stack effect or by the mechanical ventilation system, and this is referred to as the driving force of the airflow. This driving force moves air in and out of the building, and the air volume is determined by the air-tightness levels of various building elements including exterior and interior walls, doors, windows, floors, and elevator doors along the airflow path. As the air-tightness increases, a higher differential pressure is formed, and the amount of air passing through decreases [33]. Figure 2-5 shows the relationship among the differential pressure, airflow, and air-tightness in a building.

Figure 2-5 Relationship between air-tightness, differential pressure, and airflow along the horizontal air flow path in a building

The relationship among the air-tightness, differential pressure, and airflow along a horizontal airflow path in a building can be explained by the relationship between the air-tightness and air volume through an opening (Equation (7)). Figure 2-6 shows the airflow through an opening based on the differential pressure. The following relationship can be explained through Bernoulli's theorem.

$$Q = C_D A \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P}{\rho}} \quad (7)$$

where Q is the airflow through the opening in the building (m^3/s), C_D is the discharge coefficient, A is the opening area (m^2), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), and ΔP is the pressure difference of the opening (Pa).

Figure 2-6 Airflow through an opening based on differential pressure

If Bernoulli's theorem is applied to a pressurized space P_1 and a non-pressurized space P_2 , Equation (8) follows. At this time, because the height is the same, $Z_1 = Z_2$, and under the condition of that the amount of leakage that is blocked without opening the door, V_1 , which is the fluid flow in a pressurized space, reaches a value close to 0 and can thus be regarded as such. This can be summarized through Equations (9) and (10). Because $(P_1 - P_2) = \Delta P$ and the specific weight of air $\gamma = \rho \times g$, the above can be summarized as Equation (11). At this time, because the air mass

flow rate Q_m (kg/s) is constant in any cross-section, Equation (12) can be derived, which becomes equal to Equation (13). Here, Q_m/γ ((kg/s)/(kg/m³)) becomes the volumetric flow rate Q (m³/s), and $A_1/A = C_D$ is defined as the discharge coefficient. Equations (11) and (13) can be expressed as Equation (14), which are the same as Equation (7). The relationship among the differential pressure, air-tightness (air leakage area), and airflow rate can be explained using Bernoulli's theorem as follows.

$$\frac{V_1^2}{2g} \gamma + Z_1 \gamma + P_1 = \frac{V_2^2}{2g} \gamma + Z_2 \gamma + P_2 \quad (8)$$

$$P_1 = \frac{V_2^2}{2g} \gamma + P_2 \quad (9)$$

$$V_2^2 = \frac{(P_1 - P_2)}{\gamma} \times 2g \quad (10)$$

$$V_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2g}{\rho g} \times \Delta P} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\rho} \times \Delta P} \quad (11)$$

$$Q_m = V_1 \times A \times \gamma = V_2 \times A_1 \times \gamma \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{Q_m}{\gamma} = V_1 \times A = V_2 \times A_1 \quad (13)$$

$$Q = V_2 \times A_1 = V_2 \times C_D \times A = \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P}{\rho}} \times C_D \times A \quad (14)$$

The relationship between the pressure difference and air-tightness in a high-rise residential building can be explained based on the pressure distribution and Thermal Draft Coefficient (TDC), γ , through the stack effect.

A pressure difference occurs owing to the stack effect, and this pressure difference is distributed among the building elements according to the shape and composition of the building, as well as the air-tightness (air leakage area) of each building element. TDC is a concept that represents this pressure distribution; it is defined as the coefficient acting on the building envelope in the uppermost and lowermost layers. It can be expressed as Equation (15) using the symbols in the pressure profile in the building shown in Figure 2-7 [29]. TDC has been defined in

ASHRAE [34], as the differential pressure applied to the building envelope at the top and bottom layers divided by the theoretical differential pressure and has been suggested in a study by Tamura and Wilson [35-36]. TDC is the sum of the pressure difference applied to the building envelope in the uppermost and lowermost layers divided by the sum of the pressure difference applied to the inner compartment between the building envelope and shaft in the uppermost and lowermost layers. The value of TDC is between 0 and 1, and the larger the air-tightness of the building envelope, the larger is this value. TDC is important because it can be used as an indicator of the air-tightness and the degree of pressure distribution between the compartments of various components in an interior space and the building envelope due to the stack effect.

$$\gamma = \frac{P_a}{P_t} = \frac{|\Delta P_{wT}| + |\Delta P_{wB}|}{|\Delta P_{wT}| + |\Delta P_{wB}| + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \Delta P_{fi}} = \frac{|\Delta P_{wT}| + |\Delta P_{wB}|}{|\Delta P_{wT}| + |\Delta P_{wB}| + |\Delta P_{sT}| + |\Delta P_{sB}|} \quad (15)$$

where γ is the thermal draft coefficient (-), P_a is the sum of actual pressure difference due to stack effect (Pa), P_t is the sum of theoretical pressure difference due to stack effect (Pa), ΔP_{wT} is the pressure difference applied to the building envelope from the top floor (Pa), ΔP_{wB} is the pressure difference applied to the building envelope from the lowest floor (Pa), ΔP_{fi} is the sum of the pressure difference applied to the floor in the i floor (Pa), ΔP_{sT} is the pressure difference applied to the shaft wall from the top floor (Pa), and ΔP_{sB} is the pressure difference applied to the shaft wall from the lowest floor (Pa).

Hayakawa and Togari [37] noted that the TDC proposed by Tamura and Wilson was defined only using the differential pressure generated at the top and bottom floors, indicating that there is a limit to the other floors. Because the shape of the reference floor plan in an office building is mostly similar, it is assumed that similar pressure distributions will occur on each floor, and the existing TDC was redefined as the coefficient of the building envelope in each floor. Figure 2-8 shows that when the airflow path is formed horizontally from the outside air to the inside of the vertical shaft, it can be expressed through Equation (16).

$$\gamma_i = \frac{\Delta P_{wi}}{\Delta P_{wi} + \Delta P_{si}} = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{A_w}{A_s}\right)^2} \quad (16)$$

where γ_i is the thermal draft coefficient on the i floor, ΔP_{wi} is the pressure difference applied to the building envelope on the i floor (Pa), ΔP_{si} is the pressure difference applied to the shaft wall on the i floor (Pa), A_w is the leakage area of the building envelope in any floor (m^2), and A_s is the leakage area of the shaft wall in any floor (m^2)

Figure 2-7 Pressure profiles of a building with an open plan

Figure 2-8 Floor plan of a building with an open plan

Cho [29] judged that the sum of the differential pressure formed in an inner compartment is also important in high-rise residential buildings, unlike office buildings where only the differential pressure formed on the building envelope is important. First, they confirmed the possibility of applying the TDC in high-rise residential buildings. In addition, the concept of an Internal Thermal Draft Coefficient (ITDC) was proposed by employing the TDC concept of the building envelope.

As shown in Figure 2-9, if the interior space of a high-rise residential building is divided into several spaces, such as the building envelope, an interior partition, and a vertical shaft, the differential pressure owing to the stack effect is distributed according to the leakage area for each component. Therefore, if the differential pressure and leakage area of each component on the airflow path can be measured, the horizontal and vertical pressure distributions in each floor can be determined; thus, the pressure distribution of the entire building can be calculated. The definition of ITDC is shown in Equation (17).

$$ITDC=1-\gamma_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m \Delta P_{pj} + \Delta P_{si}}{\Delta P_{wi} + \sum_{j=1}^m \Delta P_{pj} + \Delta P_{si}} \quad (17)$$

where ΔP_{pj} is the pressure difference applied to the inner compartment on the j^{th} floor (Pa).

If the outermost inner compartment excluding the building envelope, i.e., the first inner compartment, is assumed as a new building envelope, and the TDC concept is applied to the relationship between the remaining inner compartments, the differential pressure of the new building envelope can be calculated. In addition, similar to the calculation of the TDC using the air-tightness ratio, if the leakage area of the first internal compartment and the equivalent leakage area of the remaining internal compartments can be obtained, TDC', which can be used to calculate the leakage area between the internal compartments, can be applied (as shown in Equations (18) and (19)).

$$\gamma'_i = \frac{\Delta P_{p1}}{\Delta P_{p1} + \sum_{j=2}^m \Delta P_{pj} + \Delta P_{si}} = \frac{1}{1 + (A_{p1}/A_{e-1})^2} \quad (18)$$

$$A_{e-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left[\frac{1}{A_s^2} + \sum_{j=2}^m \frac{1}{A_{pj}^2}\right]}} \quad (19)$$

where γ_i is the thermal draft coefficient in the first interior partition, ΔP_{p1} is the pressure difference applied to the first interior partition (Pa), A_{p1} is the leakage area in the first interior partition (m^2), A_{e-1} is the equivalent leakage area in the interior partition of the building, including the leakage area in the vertical shaft, excluding the leakage area in the first interior partition (m^2), and A_{pj} is the leakage area in the j interior partition (m^2).

Figure 2-9 Section of a building with a compartmented floor plan

Yoon et al. [38] proposed a method for predicting the air leakage area in internal compartments using the TDC' proposed by Cho and shown in Equation (7). Figure 2-10 [38] shows the concept of calculating the leakage area of the inner compartment for a horizontal airflow path. First, the TDC is determined by measuring the pressure difference of the inner compartment on a horizontal airflow path. In addition, by measuring the leakage area of the first internal compartment, the equivalent leakage area can be calculated. Thus, the leakage area of the inner compartment can be predicted by applying the TDC concept to each compartment.

To verify the proposed method, the leakage area of each compartment was calculated using the method proposed above by measuring the differential pressure and the air-tightness of the first internal compartment for an actual building. Based on the results, the uncertain input parameters (leakage area, and coefficient, and exponent of the flow) were then optimized using a genetic

algorithm (GA). Based on the optimized parameters and the process proposed in their study, the airflow simulation method for the entire building was optimized. In addition, the validity of the proposed method was verified through a comparison and analysis of the measured and simulated values. Thus, Yoon et al. proposed a calibration method for a whole-building airflow simulation in high-rise residential buildings.

$$\gamma_{i,j} = \frac{\Delta P_{i,j}}{\sum_{j=1}^m \Delta P_{i,j}} \quad (20)$$

$$A_{i,j} \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P_{i,j}}{\rho}} = A_{i,j+1} \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P_{i,j+1}}{\rho}} = \dots = A_{i,m} \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P_{i,m}}{\rho}} \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta P_{i,m} = \Delta P_{i,j} \left(\frac{A_{i,j}}{A_{i,j+1}} \right)^2 \quad (22)$$

$$\gamma_{i,j} = \frac{\Delta P_{i,j}}{\sum_{j=1}^m \Delta P_{i,j}} = \frac{\Delta P_{i,j}}{\Delta P_{i,j} + \Delta P_{i,j} \left(\frac{A_{i,j}}{A_{i,j+1}} \right)^2 + \dots + \Delta P_{i,j} \left(\frac{A_{i,j}}{A_{i,m}} \right)^2} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{A_{i,j}} \right)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{A_{i,j}} \right)^2} \quad (23)$$

$$A_{i,j} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma_{i,j}} \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{A_{i,j}} \right)^2}} \quad (24)$$

$$A_{i,e} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{A_{i,j}} \right)^2}} = A_{i,j} \sqrt{\gamma_{i,j}} \quad (25)$$

where γ'_i is the thermal draft coefficient in the first interior partition, ΔP_{p1} is the pressure difference applied to the first interior partition (Pa), A_{p1} is the leakage area in the first interior partition (m^2), A_{e-1} is the equivalent leakage area in the interior partition of the building, including the leakage area in the vertical shaft, excluding the leakage area in the first interior partition (m^2), and A_{pj} is the leakage area in the j interior partition (m^2).

Figure 2-10 Derivation of unknown leakage area in a horizontal airflow path using TDC

2.2 Conventional air-tightness measurement methods

2.2.1 Principles of tracer gas methods

A. Tracer gas

Tracer gases are used for a wide range of applications including building ventilation [39], diagnostic techniques [40-41], and tracing [42]. To determine the ventilation rates, an ideal tracer gas must have certain properties [43]:

- Uniqueness: It must not exist in the same environment as the target space. In addition, an ideal tracer gas should not exist in the atmosphere; therefore, it should be distinguishable from all other air components in the atmosphere. In general, it should not be mixed with air and can be used as a tracer gas if its constituents are much greater than those in other atmospheres.

- **Measurability:** It should be easily measured even at low concentrations. Moreover, a measurement instrument should be able to quantitatively determine the actual concentration of all tracer gases injected.
- **Safety:** The tracer gas used should be non-allergic, non-toxic, and non-flammable to avoid posing a danger to people, materials, or the environment around the actual measurement site.
- **Inactivity (non-reactivity):** The tracer gas should be inactive and should not burn. In addition, it should be harmless to the human body and not cause any allergies. Because a tracer gas is used based on the conservation laws to determine the airflow, it must not react chemically or physically with any systems or components. Therefore, an ideal tracer gas should not have any physical or chemical effects, such as on the air density or airflow of any system or component.
- **Convenience:** A tracer gas should be readily available and economical to apply.

These characteristics are ideal from a theoretical perspective; in reality, however, tracer gases are selected primarily based on their cost and cost of the equipment required for measurement. Because a tracer gas has difficulty meeting all of the above requirements in a realistic manner, many studies have been conducted to determine the gas that comes the closest to satisfying the above characteristics. According to a study conducted by Sandberg, various tracer gases should be used depending on the purpose of measurement [44]. Gases that are mainly used as tracers include helium (He), hydrogen (H₂), water vapor (H₂O), methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitric oxide (NO_x), sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆), carbon perfluorocarbons (PFCs), and radioactive materials. Recently, SF₆ has been used as a tracer gas as it does not exist in the atmosphere and can be tested in small amounts compared to NO or CO₂. Although it is mainly used with PFCs, there is a limit to our understanding of it in terms of the internal flow phenomenon because this gas is denser than the atmosphere. In addition, it has also been considered a greenhouse gas. In contrast, although CO₂ levels can be affected by human

movement (breathing) and high CO₂ concentrations can be danger, CO₂ is relatively inexpensive. Moreover, when it is measured using a CO₂ concentration decay method, it shows a reduction rate similar to that of SF₆; thus, the resulting accuracy is relatively high. There is also an advantage in that it is easy to analyze the differences according to regions owing to the wide range of general concentration distribution. Table 2-1 shows the properties of major tracer gases used [39] [45].

Table 2-1 Characteristics of various tracer gases

Tracer gas	Molecular weight	Boiling point (°C)	Density(25 °C) (kg/m ³)	Detection Range (PPM)
Dichlorodifluoromethane (Freon 12)	120.91	-29.8	5.13	0.05 to 2000 0.001 to 0.05
1,1,1,2-Tetrafluoroethane (R-134a)	102.03	-26.3	4.25	-
Sulfur Hexafluoride (SF ₆)	146.06	-50.8	6.18	0.05 to 2000 0.00002 to 0.5
CO ₂	44.01	-56.6	1.98	0.05 to 2000
Helium	4	-268.9	0.17	-
NO	30	-147	1.85	0.05 to 2000
Perfluoron-n-hexane (C ₆ F ₁₄)	338.04	-60	1680	-

B. Trace gas method using the injection method

The first tracer gas technique was developed by Pettenkofer in 1858, in which CO₂ was used as a tracer gas to evaluate ventilation in hospitals [46]. Later, a tracer gas method was developed by Marley [47] and Dick [48] to evaluate the amount of natural ventilation in a building; since then, many researchers have used a tracer gas to evaluate building ventilation. A tracer gas system consists of a tracer gas, a tracer gas injection device, a mixing device, a sampling device, and a gas analyzer. A tracer gas injection device injects the tracer gas to a desired location in the building, and the evaluation method varies depending on the injection method applied.

Experimental methods according to the tracer gas injection method include the pulse, decay, and step-up (at a constant injection) methods [49]. The change in concentration over time for each method is shown in Figure 2-11 [45].

(1) Pulse method

The pulse method is used to inject a certain amount of tracer gas into an air supply duct or an arbitrary point in the room for a short period of time. To obtain the first time point with respect to time, the concentration after injection is calculated by measuring the change in concentration over time after reaching the maximum value. This is economical because a lower amount of tracer gas is used; however, a precise concentration meter is required because significant errors can occur compared to the decay and step-up methods [49]. If sufficient tracer gas has been discharged, its concentration can be calculated using Equation (26).

$$Q_T = \frac{\bar{Q}_T}{C} \quad (26)$$

where Q_T is the instantaneous injection of tracer gas (m^3h^{-1}), C is the instantaneous tracer gas concentration ($\text{mol(ecul)es tracer} \cdot \text{mol(ecui)es air}^{-1}$), and \bar{X} is the average value of the variable for the time T .

(2) Decay method

In the decay method, the tracer gas is first injected at a constant concentration; injection of the tracer gas is stopped when the concentration of the tracer gas in the room reaches a certain value. The concentration of the tracer gas gradually decreases over time, and when a tracer gas that does not exist in the atmosphere is used, the concentration approaches zero in the steady state. Although this is a commonly used method, it is important to make the tracer gas concentration constant in the room because otherwise, this method has a disadvantage in that the air in the room

must be completely mixed, and a mixing device must be used to maintain the concentration at a constant level. The decay method can be expressed using Equation (27). This equation may fit the data measured using the regression method. The fitting parameters are C_R and λ_R . The precision of the method can be estimated through regression. A typical method of analysis applies a linear regression to the log of concentration. This technique is extremely sensitive to zero drift and tends to excessively increase the contribution of the lowest concentration value to the fitting. To reasonably estimate the precision of this technique, a detailed error analysis of this type of regression can be conducted based on an uncertainty analysis of other decay techniques [49].

$$C(t) = C_R \times e^{-\lambda_R t} \quad (27)$$

where λ is the air change rate (m^3h^{-1}) and X_R is the variable value obtained by using the regression equation.

(3) Step-up method (constant injection)

The step-up method is used to continuously inject a tracer gas into an arbitrary point in the room or the supply air duct and maintain it at a certain level. After injection, the change in concentration over time is measured. A steady state is reached by converging at a specific concentration without any further change in concentration. There is a disadvantage here in that a large amount of tracer gas is required, and the effect of infiltration cannot be considered. When the amount of tracer gas injected is constant, it can be expressed in the same way as in Equation (28). Some researchers [50-51] used a nonlinear method to directly fit this curve and determine the ventilation and effective volumes; however, most of these methods require the steady state to be reached, and the data are then converted into a steady-state equation (Equation (29)) [49].

$$C(t) = \frac{Q_T}{Q_R} + \left(C_R - \frac{Q_T}{Q_R}\right) e^{-\lambda_R t} \quad (28)$$

$$Q_R = \frac{Q_T}{C(t)} \text{ when } e^{-\lambda t} \ll 1 \quad (29)$$

where Q is the ventilation flow (of air) (h^{-1}).

(a) Pulse Method

(b) Decay Method

(c) Step-Up Method

Figure 2-11 Injection methods of tracer gas

2.2.2 Limitations of tracer gas method

As described above, the pulse method is economically advantageous because the amount of tracer gas required is small; however, large errors can occur because the uncertainty is significant

compared to that of other methods [49]. In addition, the constant injection or the step-up method is expensive because it uses a large amount of tracer gas and does not take into account the effect of infiltration. Compared to the other two methods, the decay method assumes a complete mixing in the room, and thus a mixing device is required, making it important to maintain the initial concentration in the entire room. This study attempted to examine the limitations of a CO₂ concentration decay test, which is one of the most commonly used decay methods, under the assumption of complete mixing.

The most widely used approach is the CO₂ concentration decay test method, which tracks the change in concentration over time by spraying a high concentration of CO₂ indoors. The concentration decay data are fitted to an exponential curve to obtain the ACH. This method is usually applied as a long-term method to measure the air-tightness of a room or calculate the average amount of infiltration. However, when calculating the infiltration rate using this method, there is a time lag between wind fluctuations and the resulting diffusion in the concentration of the tracer gas [53]. When measuring air changes using a decay method, ASTM E 741-00 [22] recommends a minimum period between the first and last samplings. For infiltration rates between 0.1 and 0.2 h⁻¹ or even lower, the required minimum decay time will be between 5 and 10 h or more. Furthermore, this method is difficult to apply under actual living conditions. Moreover, because the tracer gas decay method calculates the infiltration rate of an entire zone or building, it cannot be used to predict the air-tightness of individual airflow components (e.g., envelope or doors).

2.2.3 Principles of fan pressurization methods

A. Measurement method and principles of blower door test

A representative method for measuring building air-tightness is the fan pressurization method, which has been used for almost 50 years [23]. In this method, a building is pressurized

or depressurized using an air conditioning system or a fan, and the air-tightness is then determined by measuring the volume of airflow at a given difference in internal/external static pressure. A typical implementation of this method is the blower door test, which pressurizes/depressurizes at a higher pressure than the actual condition of the building, making it possible to minimize the influence of external environmental factors that can affect the resulting air-tightness [53]. Using this method, it is possible to calculate the representative air-tightness of buildings and compare it with that of other buildings.

In the blower door test, the air-tightness is calculated by measuring the amount of air flowing out or flowing into the building envelope when the household is pressurized or depressurized. Any airflow generated through the fan or blower installed at the front door of a household will escape through the building envelope. This is because all spaces connected to the outside, such as ventilation ports, bathroom fans, kitchen hoods, and power outlets, of the household to be measured are sealed, and only the building envelope is not sealed. In other words, the air-tightness of a building may be defined as the air-tightness of its envelope. The air to be pressurized must maintain a specific pressure difference in the building, and the less air-tight the building, the more volume of air is required. In general, in a blower door test, the pressure difference is continuously increased or decreased from 10 to 75 Pa at the location to be measured, and the room is continuously pressurized or depressurized.

The relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume obtained through the blower door test of an entire building is shown in Figure 2-12 [28]. The data points are expressed as the air-tightness measured in a single building, which is characterized based on its air-tightness by combining the data to the regression line, enabling a general comparison with other buildings. This relationship is greatly affected by the shape of openings, and in the case of the building envelope, the shape of openings is not uniform and the airflow is not sufficiently developed owing to turbulence. The characteristics of the openings of each of these buildings can be described

using a power law equation such as Equation (30).

$$Q = C(\Delta P)^n \tag{30}$$

where Q is the airflow through opening (m^3h^{-1}), C is the flow coefficient ($\text{m}^3/(\text{h}\cdot\text{Pa}^n)$), and n is the pressure exponent. In the blower door test, the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume is used to calculate the values of the airflow coefficient (C) in $\text{m}^3/(\text{h}\cdot\text{Pa}^n)$ and flow exponent (n), which are characteristics unique to a building.

Here, C is a function of the leakage path and is an intrinsic characteristic. The value of C is characteristic of the building and does not change even when measured under various pressure difference conditions. It can be considered as a characteristic of the air that escapes into the building envelope of the building. The value of C is approximately 0.6 for a wide range of Reynolds numbers but can only be calculated by applying a value of 0.78 for significant flow passages with vertical divisions such as doors [54]. However, C is the most accurate parameter and can take various values for one building. There is no limiting value for C .

Figure 2-12 Airflow rate versus pressure difference data in a building based on a blower door test

In addition, n is the pressure index and is also a unique characteristic of a building. Walker reported that the n value is constant during pressurization-induced infiltration in cracks in the building envelope [55]. The n value is generally assumed to be 0.65 in simulations [20]. The n value decreases with a larger leakage path and takes a value of approximately 0.5. In addition, the smaller the gaps and cracks, the larger the n value; smaller openings typically have an n value of approximately 0.65 [56]. If n is not measured as a value between 0.5 and 1.0 in the blower door test, it is necessary to recheck if external doors at the place to be measured were opened and if external places outside the building envelope were sealed. The n value is limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1 [57-58].

To determine the C and n values, it is necessary to obtain air volume data under various differential pressure conditions by using a fan and a pressure gauge capable of measuring the air volume and differential pressure. The values of C and n are determined using the data obtained by defining the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume using the power law equation (Equation (30)), which is the basic equation used in the blower door test. To determine the values of Q (air volume) and ΔP (differential pressure) in Equation (30), the values of C and n must be converted using natural logarithms. Equations (31) and (32) indicate that the log values of the differential pressure and air volume are assumed to be x and y , where $i = 1, 2, 3 \dots N$ (N is the number of data obtained from pressurization or depressurization), respectively. Equations (31) and (32) can be expressed through Equation (33). In Equation (33), the value of n indicates the relationship between the differential pressure and air volume. In other words, it indicates the slope of the linear function of the differential pressure and the air volume. It can also be said that the value of n applies the same concept as that of slope Beta-1 of the regression line in the regression analysis of air volume data under various differential pressure conditions. Equations (34) and (35) can then be used to determine the average differential pressure and air volume, and Equations (36) and (37) can be used to determine the dispersion of the differential

pressure and air volume, respectively. Equation (38) indicates the covariance of differential pressure and air volume. In this way, after performing calculations through Equations (34)–(38), the n value can be obtained using Equation (39) by dividing the covariance of the differential pressure and air volume by the variance of the differential pressure. Finally, the C value can be calculated by substituting it into n in Equation (40) obtained from Equation (39) [59]. The air-tightness, i.e., ACH or the air change rate (h^{-1}), is determined by calculating the air volume under a 50 Pa differential pressure condition using the obtained C and n values and dividing it by the volume (m^3) of the measured location.

$$x_i = \ln(\Delta P_i) \quad (31)$$

$$y_i = \ln(Q_i) \quad (32)$$

$$y = \ln(C) + nx \quad (33)$$

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \quad (34)$$

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \quad (35)$$

$$s_x^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (36)$$

$$s_y^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2 \quad (37)$$

$$s_{xy} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y}) \quad (38)$$

$$n = \frac{s_{xy}}{s_x^2} \quad (39)$$

$$C = \exp(\bar{y} - n\bar{x}) \quad (40)$$

As a result, the key to determining the air-tightness using the blower door test lies in the C and n values. The air-tightness can easily be obtained only if the values of C and n, which are characteristics unique to the location to be measured, are known. To summarize the relationship between the C and n values of the blower door test, the differential pressure and air volume are measured at the measurement site using a pressure gauge or fan, and the measured values are used

as the C and n values, which are characteristics intrinsic to the measurement site. The air-tightness can be calculated from the obtained C and n values. Finding the C and n values for the location to be measured is the key to determining the air-tightness when using the blower door test.

B. Relationship between differential pressure and airflow based on the principle of the power law equation

As indicated above, the C and n values are extremely important. In particular, grasping the meaning of and obtaining the C and n values in the power law equation is key to determining the air-tightness when using a blower door test. In the blower door test, the C and n values are defined based on the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume using the power law equation. Considering Equation (33), the relationship between differential pressure and air volume is a linear functional equation with two unknowns. The two unknowns, $\ln(C)$ and n, can be obtained even with only two datasets measuring the differential pressure and air volume. However, in general, for a blower door test, measurement standards such as ASTM Standard E779-03 [57], ISO 9972 [61], EN 13829 [24], and CIBSE-TM 23 [62] recommend performing 5–7 measurements, using a maximum of 10 differential pressure levels, and employing air volume datasets [24] to overcome various problems that may occur during the measurements. The explanatory power of a dataset also increases by using multiple measured datasets.

Figure 2-13 shows the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume by applying the power law equation, indicating that the value of n can be expressed as the slope of the linear functional equation. In addition, the figure shows a graph indicating the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume, as the results of a blower door test. That is, n uses the same concept as that of slope Beta-1 of the regression line during the regression analysis. Beta-1 is the mean change in the dependent variable y for one unit increase in the independent variable x. Beta-1 is the covariance of the independent variable and the dependent variable divided

by the variance of the independent variable [60]. This is the same concept as that applied when calculating the n value in the power law equation of the blower door test because n is the covariance of the differential pressure and the air volume divided by the variance of the differential pressure.

Figure 2-13 Relationship between differential pressure and airflow using power law equation in the blower door test

2.2.4 Differences in standards related to the fan pressurization method

There are certain measurement standards that are referred to when performing a blower door test. In the United States, the ASTM Standard E779-03 [57], ISO 9972 [61], and EN 13829 [24] developed by the International Organization for Standardization are used, and in United Kingdom, CIBSE-TM 23 [62] is applied.

The method for expressing the measurement results, the method for correcting the average difference in measured pressure, the method for calculating the leakage amount using the air volume, the method for expressing the power law equation, the method for correcting the leakage machine number, and the method for expressing the leakage area results are different for different standards. Thus, a review of such methods was conducted. First, various methods for expressing

air-tightness were reviewed.

A. Equivalent or Effective Air Leakage Area (EqLA or ELA)

All openings in the building envelope are combined into an overall opening area and a discharge coefficient (C_D) for a building when the equivalent or effective air leakage area is calculated through Equation (41) [28]. Some common air-tightness ratings include the effective air leakage area (ELA) at 4 Pa assuming $C_D = 1.0$ [63], the equivalent air leakage area (EqLA) at 10 Pa assuming $C_D = 0.611$ [64], and the airflow rate at 50 Pa that is divided by the building volume to determine the ACH [65]. A representative method for measuring building air-tightness is fan pressurization.

ELA is a concept that was first established by Lawrence Berkeley Laboratory [66]. When a differential pressure of 4 Pa occurs inside and outside a building, the size of the opening through which air leaks is converted into a nozzle area similar to the inlet side of a blower door fan.

EqLA is a leak scale that is mainly used by the Canada National Research Council [67]. The amount of leakage generated when a differential pressure of 10 Pa is applied to the target space is converted into the area of the orifice on a thin plate.

An air-tightness rating, whether based on the air leakage area or predicted airflow rate, is generally normalized by a certain factor to account for the building size. Normalization factors include the floor area, exterior envelope area, and building volume. Owing to a wide variety of possible approaches to normalization and several definitions of the reference pressure difference, as well as the use of the air leakage area concept, many different air-tightness ratings can be used. Reference pressure differences include 4, 10, 25, 50, and 75 Pa. Reference pressure differences of 4 and 10 Pa are promoted because they are closer to the pressure differences that induce an air exchange, and therefore better model the flow characteristics of an opening. Although this may be true, they are outside the range of measured values in the test; therefore, predicted airflow rates

at 4 and 10 Pa are subject to a significant uncertainty [68-71].

$$A_L = 10000Q_r \frac{\sqrt{\rho/2\Delta p_r}}{C_D} \quad (41)$$

where A_L is the equivalent or effective air leakage area (cm^2), Q_r is the predicted airflow rate at Δp_r (from curve fit to pressurization test data) (m^3/s), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), Δp_r is the reference pressure difference (Pa), and C_D is the discharge coefficient.

B. Cubic Feet per Minute at 50 Pa (CFM50), ft^3/min and CMH50, m^3/h

CFM50 refers to the amount of airflow that must be introduced into a room to maintain an indoor/outdoor pressure difference of 50 Pa per minute per cubic foot of the target building. When using metric units (CRC Handbook of Energy Efficiency), cubic meters per hour at 50 Pa (CMH50), m^3/h , is occasionally used. A pressure of 50 Pa is created when a wind blows at approximately 9 m/s.

C. Air Change rate per Hour at 50 Pa (ACH50), h^{-1}

ACH50 represents the amount of air movement in the target building, i.e., the number of times indoor air is ventilated in an hour when a pressure of 50 Pa is applied. It can be calculated by dividing CFM50 by the cubic feet of the target building. This is useful for comparing the air-tightness measured in buildings of different sizes.

D. Minneapolis Leakage Ratio at 50 Pa (MLR)

The MLR is calculated by dividing CFM50 by the amount of leakage per unit envelope area by the envelope area of the building. It is often used to determine the air-tightness of wooden buildings. A wooden building with an MLR ranging from 0.5 to 1.0 is classified as air-tight.

E. Air permeability, cfm/ft², L/s.m²

This is a scale representing the amount of leakage per unit area divided by the amount of leakage by the total area of the building envelope. This concept is mainly used in the EU and the UK.

F. Normalized Leakage (NL)

The ASHRAE Standard 62.2 establishes air leakage performance levels for residential buildings. It is an index that converts the leaking area of a building when considering the size and height of a residential building. These levels are in terms of the effective annual average infiltration rate, which is based on the normalized leakage (NL) area, taking into account the size and height of the building. Equation (42) shows how NL is calculated. In ASHRAE Standard 62.2 [72], after the air-tightness level of a building is calculated using the above equation, it is evaluated as shown in Table 2-2 [72] according to the resulting value. Table 2-3 summarizes the method of expressing the air-tightness described above and the criteria related to its calculation formula.

$$NL = 0.1 \left(\frac{ELA}{A_F} \right) \left(\frac{H}{H_r} \right)^{0.4} \quad (42)$$

where NL is the normalized leakage, ELA is the effective leakage area using 4 Pa reference pressure ($C_D = 1.0$) (m^2), A_F is the floor area (Normalized leakage area) (m^2), H is the vertical distance from the lowest above-grade floor to highest ceiling (m), and H_r is the reference height (2.5 m)

There are various criteria for measuring the air-tightness of a building. Table 2-4 shows the measurement procedures and methods for each standard, such as the ASTM Standard E779-03 [57] in the United States, ISO 9972 [61], EN 13829 [24] developed by the International Standardization Organization, and CIBSE-TM 23 [62] in the United Kingdom.

Table 2-2 Air-tightness rating evaluation by NL of ASHRAE Standard 62.2

Air-tightness rating	NL standard	ACH50
A	$NL < 0.10$	1
B	$0.10 \leq NL < 0.14$	2
C	$0.14 \leq NL < 0.20$	3
D	$0.20 \leq NL < 0.28$	5
E	$0.28 \leq NL < 0.40$	7
F	$0.40 \leq NL < 0.57$	10
G	$0.57 \leq NL < 0.80$	14
H	$0.80 \leq NL < 1.13$	20
I	$1.13 \leq NL < 1.60$	27
J	$1.60 \leq NL$	-

Table 2-3 Calculation formula and related standards according to the air-tightness index

Air-tightness index	Calculation formula	Standard
CFM50	$MLR = \frac{CFM50}{\text{Building envelope}}$	-
ACH50	$ACH50 = \frac{CFM50 \times 60}{\text{Building volume}(\text{ft}^3)}$	EN 13829, ISO 9972,
ELA (4 Pa)	$A_L = 10000Q_r \frac{\sqrt{P/2\Delta p_r}}{C_D}$ $C_D=1 (4 \text{ Pa}), C_D=0.611 (10 \text{ Pa})$	ASTM Standard E 779-03, EN 13829, ISO 9972
EqLA (10 Pa)		CGSB 149.15-M96, JIS A 2201, EN 13829, ISO 9972
NL	$NL = 0.1 \left(\frac{ELA}{A_F} \right) \left(\frac{H}{H_r} \right)^{0.4}$	ASHRAE Standard 62.2

Table 2-4 Measurement conditions and methods used in each air-tightness standard

Standard	ASTM Standard E779-03	ISO 9972 / EN 13829	CIBSE TM-23
Measurement result	ELA at 4 Pa CFM50	ACH, CFM50/ft ² EqLA at 10 Pa, ELA at 4 Pa	ELA at 50 Pa
Pressure difference correction	Use the average value	$\Delta p = \Delta p_m - \frac{\Delta p_{0,1} + \Delta p_{0,2}}{2}$	-
Calculation of leakage using airflow	Depressurization	$\dot{V}_L = C_L(\Delta p)^n$	Pressurization
	$Q_o = Q \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_o}$	Depressurization $C_L = C_{env}(\frac{\rho_e}{\rho_o})^{1-n}$	$Q_m = Q_c \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_m}$
	Pressurization	Pressurization	Temperature correction
	$Q_o = Q \frac{\rho_o}{\rho_i}$	$C_L = C_{env}(\frac{\rho_i}{\rho_o})^{1-n}$	$Q_{env(out)} = Q_m(\frac{T_i + 273}{T_o + 273})$
Power Law Equation	$Q = C(\Delta p^n)$	$\dot{V}_{env} = C_{env}(\Delta p)^n$	$Q = C(\Delta p^n)$
Leakage coefficient correction	$C_o = C(\frac{\mu}{\mu_o})^{2n-1}(\frac{\rho}{\rho_o})^{1-n}$	$\dot{V}_{\Delta p_r} = C_L(\Delta p_r)^n$	$C_s = C_{env}(\frac{\rho_{env}}{\rho_s})^{(1-n)}$
Air leakage area	$A = C_o(\frac{\rho_o}{2})^{\frac{1}{2}}(dP_r)^{(n-\frac{1}{2})}$	$A_L = 10000Q_r \frac{\sqrt{\rho/2\Delta p_r}}{C_D}$	$ELA = Q(\frac{\rho}{2\Delta P})^{0.5}$
Acceptable conditions	$\Delta T \times \text{height} < 200 \text{ m} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta T \times \text{height} < 250 \text{ m} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (ISO 9972) $\Delta T \times \text{height} < 500 \text{ m} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (EN 13829) Wind speed < 6 m/s	$\Delta T < 10 ^\circ\text{C}$ Wind speed < 3 m/s
Pressure range	10 to 60 Pa	10 to 50(≤100) Pa	15 to 50 Pa
Number of point	(By 5 to 10 Pa) > 5 at each direction	> 5 at each direction	(By 5 Pa) 8
Related Standard	Energy Star, IECC, LEED, ASHRAE	Passive House, ATTMA 1.2	R-2000, LEED / ASHRAE Canada
Origin	USA	International / Europe	UK

2.2.5 Limitations of the blower door test

The blower door test, which is a typical fan pressurization method, has certain limitations in terms of cost, time, and measurement method. These limitations can be largely divided into two types: limitations related to the preparation process and cost, and limitations that inevitably arise during measurements.

We first discuss the limitations in terms of preparation process and cost. First, it is impossible to conduct an experiment alone. Experiments must be conducted in groups of two or more people. When measuring the air-tightness, it is necessary to pressurize and depressurize the location to be measured at intervals of 5 to 10 Pa. When the location is pressurized and depressurized, the air volume of the fan must be adjusted because the air volume at the suitable building pressure must be adjusted. At this time, an adjustment ring is used that adjusts the air volume of the fan, and when pressurized, the adjustment ring must be located outside the front door of the measurement location. In addition, when conducting the blower door test, a fan is installed at the front door of the measurement location; thus, when pressurizing the location, one person must be present outside.

Second, blower door test equipment is expensive (approximately 10 million won), and the labor costs required to perform air-tightness measurements are also high. According to a report by RDH Building Engineering, Ltd., the average cost of performing an air-tightness measurement is \$2,000–25,000 [73]. Therefore, it is difficult to measure the air-tightness using a blower door test because its equipment is expensive. Table 2-5 indicates the cost incurred when performing air-tightness measurements according to RDH Building Engineering, Ltd.

Third, the measurement preparation process is complex. Significant preparations must be made in order to conduct a blower door test. All areas connected to the outside air, except for the building envelope to be measured, must be sealed in an air-tight manner. Examples of such areas include kitchen hoods, sinks, household ventilation openings, bathroom exhaust fans, bathroom

sinks, and drain holes. The FLIB (German Air-tightness Association) and EN 13829 [24] recommend a thorough preparation process including sealing, closing, and ceasing the operation of a total of 27 elements of the buildings, openings, and installations before performing air-tightness measurements using a blower door test.

Table 2-5 Costs incurred when measuring air-tightness as reported by RDH Building Engineering, Ltd.

Air-tightness test	Approximate cost
Quantitative testing procedures	
Whole Building Air-tightness Test (CGSB 149.10, ASTM E 779, ASTM 1827 or USACE) - Single large blower unit or multiple smaller blower units to pressurize/depressurize whole building with multiple zones	Depends on Building Size and Timing of Test, \$2,000 to \$25,000+
Whole Building Air-tightness Test (CGSB 149.15) - Use of building ventilation system to pressurize/depressurize whole building with multiple zones	Depends on Available Equipment (unlikely within a MURB) \$8,000 to \$12,000
Balanced Fan Depressurization/Pressurization Test of Single Zone - Determination of interior separator and exterior building enclosure air-tightness characteristics of a single zone within a multi-zone building	\$3,000 to \$6,000
Constant Decay Tracer Gas Testing (ASTM E 741)	\$5,000 to 10,000+
Constant Injection Tracer Gas Testing (ASTM E 741)	
Constant Concentration Tracer Gas Testing (ASTM E 741)	
Component Air-tightness Test (ASTM E 783) - Field test of air-tightness of single component such as a door or a window	Depends largely on access to component \$1,000 to \$2,000
Detached House Blower Door Air-tightness Test	\$150 to \$500
Qualitative testing procedures	
Performance Verification Infrared Photography - Infrared photography to identify air leakage locations while building is pressurized/depressurized	\$1,000 to \$2,000 as an add to whole building pressurization test
Performance Verification Smoke Test - Smoke testing to identify air leakage locations while building is pressurized/depressurized	\$1,000 as an add to whole building pressurization test
Diagnostic Infrared Photography - Infrared photography to identify air leakage locations in response to an identified issue at a discrete location	\$2,000 as an add to whole building pressurization test
Diagnostic Smoke Test - Smoke testing to identify air leakage locations in response to an identified issue at a discrete location	\$500 to \$1,000

When installing a fan on the front door of the location to be measured, it is necessary to ensure that the necessary frame and materials required to hang the fan on the door are prepared in advance and made air-tight. In particular, if non-experts are conducting this test and if proper installation is not ensured, the installed frame and material will detach once the fan pressure is applied, making it impossible to perform measurements.

Finally, measurements in a residential building are subject to many limitations because a loud noise is generated. Although measurements can be made when the household is not occupied, it is impossible to conduct realistic measurements under such conditions because residents may complain when the building is occupied again.

We now discuss the problems that can inevitably occur when performing measurements using a blower door test. First, it is difficult to measure the zero-flow pressure. The zero-flow pressure is measured at the start and end of the test to determine the change in this pressure caused by the fan or blower door while accounting for climatic conditions. ISO 9972 requires the absolute value of the zero-flow pressure difference to be less than 5 Pa (0.10 lb/ft²) [61] [74-75]. However, the zero-flow pressure does not remain constant during the fan pressurization test, making it an important source of uncertainty in the measurements [76]. In addition, because the number of measurements (before and after the pressure difference measurements) and the measurement time (at least 30 s) are also considered, the zero-flow pressure difference should be determined taking into account all the three items above. The difference in zero-flow pressure may not be established depending on the characteristics of the building, height, household size, and external weather conditions. If such a pressure is not established, it will be impossible to measure the air-tightness. Figure 2-14 shows a situation in which it is impossible to use the blower door test because the difference in the zero-flow pressure is not established.

Second, because the pressure of a building is inherently unstable owing to factors such as the stack effect and wind pressure under any given air-tightness condition, it is difficult to control

the pressure in a real building. Thus, building pressures can affect the correlations between the pressure differences and airflow rates determined by the blower door test, causing the measurements to be inaccurate. Figure 2-15 shows a situation in which it is impossible to perform measurements because the measuring equipment does not recognize the pressure in the building.

Figure 2-14 Situations in which the difference in zero-flow pressure is not established

Figure 2-15 Situations in which the measurement equipment does not recognize the pressure in the building

Third, for buildings beyond a certain size, it can be difficult to secure a sufficient difference in pressure and airflow required to accurately measure the air-tightness [77]. Because the general fan air volume of the blower door test is limited to 20,000 CMH, an additional fan is required when this value is exceeded. In addition, when two or more fans are needed, the equipment and the measurement method itself are different; thus, a skilled expert is required, and additional costs are incurred. Figure 2-16 indicates that the air-tightness level of a building is poor, and an excessive volume of fan air is required.

Figure 2-16 Situations in which measurements are impossible when the standard air volume of the fan is exceeded

Finally, because the measurement process recommends approximately 5–10 measurements within the range of 10 to 60 Pa, a large number of measurements must be performed. The measurement process thus becomes complicated and even impossible owing to the various variables applied. Without professional skills, this is difficult to cope with. Figures 2-17 and 2-19 show situations in which measurements are impossible owing to inexperience in such installations.

Thus, the blower door test method has several practical limitations and challenges, particularly for multi-unit residential buildings or high-rise buildings with large stack and wind effects.

Figure 2-17 Measurement difficulties owing to improper installation (1)

Figure 2-18 Measurement difficulties owing to improper installation (2)

Figure 2-19 Measurement difficulties owing to improper installation (3)

2.3 Literature review on air-tightness measurement and prediction methods

2.3.1 Air-tightness measurement using the CO₂ concentration decay test

The CO₂ concentration decay test has been investigated in numerous studies from the 1980s till now and has been improved upon based on recent advancements in technology. A CO₂ concentration decay test using tracer gas techniques can reflect the fluctuating infiltration rate and is suitable when evaluating the infiltration rate in real time.

Recently developed wireless sensor technologies can allow easy low-cost monitoring of variables related to the indoor air quality and thermal environment [78]. In addition, reviews and research have been conducted on the reduction of the tracer gas cost, and recently, studies calculating the amount of infiltration using the CO₂ gas generated by occupants as a tracer gas have been actively conducted. Unlike conventional tracer gas methods, the occupant-generated CO₂ method directly uses gas generated by occupants; thus, there is no need to inject a tracing gas [79], making it possible to perform calculations every hour in buildings with occupants. The

occupant-generated CO₂ tracer gas method has received considerable attention as it can determine the infiltration rate in real time and reflect the actual environmental conditions [80-84]. This method tracks the exponential decrease in CO₂ concentration formed indoors with respect to the background concentration level after occupants leave a building [85]. However, the low concentration levels and short-term periods of occupant-generated CO₂ in such a method can lead to a considerable amount of uncertainty in the infiltration calculations [79] [86]. First, there may be errors in selecting the start and end times for calculating the infiltration rate [81]. Errors will increase at low concentrations in cases when indoor CO₂ concentrations decrease and approach outdoor levels [85], similar to ISO 12569 [87], where the need for a meaningful difference in concentration between the start and end points is emphasized. High uncertainties during low-concentration periods may lead to an over- or underestimation of the results. It is necessary to analyze the time range that can minimize the measurement uncertainty when applying this method. Traditional tracer gas methods require a relatively long measurement time and assume that the air exchange rate is constant over a long period [49]. However, this assumption cannot be applied when calculating the infiltration rate based on short-term CO₂ fluctuations and may lead to measurement errors in a space with a fluctuating ventilation rate. It is thus necessary to set an appropriate time interval (ΔT) to express the time-varying infiltration rate. Although ASTM E741-00 [22] stipulates a minimum duration between the initial and final samples over a significant time interval under low air exchange rate conditions, it cannot be used in all situations.

The tracer gas method assumes a constant background concentration, whereas the background CO₂ concentration in a room can change with time and place. Although the fluctuating background CO₂ concentration affects the infiltration calculation, the indoor CO₂ concentration in a traditional tracer gas method is sufficiently high, and the dependence on the outside CO₂ fluctuation is low. The average outside CO₂ concentration can be used when calculating the infiltration rate using a traditional method [49]. However, when calculating the

time-varying infiltration rate at a low concentration, assuming the background concentration to be a constant value can lead to uncertainty.

As a result, studies calculating the amount of infiltration of a building using a CO₂ concentration decay test do not incur a tracer gas cost, and studies on methods for calculating the amount of infiltration in real time using the low-concentration CO₂ generated by occupants have been conducted. In addition, efforts are being made to shorten the measurement time when calculating the amount of infiltration.

2.3.2 Air-tightness measurement using the blower door test

Air-tightness measurements have mainly been conducted in Europe and North America, where air-tightness standards have been established. However, unlike domestic buildings, these buildings are single-family houses or low-rise buildings made of wood or masonry. Therefore, they are different from the reinforced concrete structures that are mainly used domestically; thus, the air-tightness data obtained in these countries also differ. Research on the air-tightness of buildings began in the 1990s and mainly included studies on foreign air-tightness standards, air-tightness measurement and evaluation methods, and air-tightness measurements [88-89]. Koo et al. [90] later measured the air-tightness of households and the building envelope in super-high-rise residential-commercial buildings. As a result of determining the air-tightness characteristics of high-rise residential buildings, it was revealed that the air-tightness of the building envelope differs significantly according to the workability, and the leakage area is approximately 15% less for depressurization than for pressurization. By conducting actual air-tightness measurements on residential-commercial, multi-family, and detached houses, Kwon et al. [91] revealed that the air-tightness of recently constructed buildings has been improved. In addition, it was revealed that it is necessary to evaluate the air-tightness according to the domestic status. In Korea, there are no legal standards for the air-tightness of a building, and thus, there is no data that can be used as

reference.

In a study conducted by Shin [92], the leakage distribution ratio was derived by measuring the air-tightness of each building part, including the shell; they also investigated a method of measuring air-tightness in domestic buildings based on foreign measurement methods. In addition, Shin [93] and Ji [94] conducted many measurements on high-rise apartment houses in Korea. The air-tightness of a total of 1261 households in buildings was measured, and the range of ACH50 values varied from 0.72 h^{-1} to 4.81 h^{-1} (mean of 2.23 h^{-1} , median of 2.16 h^{-1} , ACH50). The air-tightness values were classified according to the type of building envelope: the curtain wall was found to have a value within the range of $1.89\text{--}4.13 \text{ h}^{-1}$, whereas the other punch window was found to have a value within the range of $1.55\text{--}2.71 \text{ h}^{-1}$, indicating that its air-tightness was better than that of the curtain wall.

Undram et al. [95] investigated the air-tightness of 20 buildings measured in previous studies [96-101] to understand the current air-tightness state of mid- and high-rise buildings in the country. A comparison was also conducted with the air-tightness of mid- and high-rise buildings measured abroad [102-107]. Because the unit of expression of the measurement data differs depending on the researcher, it was integrated into EqLA for comparison and analysis. As a result of comparing the air-tightness of 20 domestic buildings based on their year of construction, it was confirmed that the air-tightness was excellent in recently built buildings. The average value of the sheath air-tightness was $1.9 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$ at 75 Pa, and when it was divided by the sheath type, the value for the curtain wall was $2.2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$ at 75 Pa, and that for the punch window was $1.6 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$ at 75 Pa. Although there are no significant differences between the curtain wall and punch window, the air-tightness of the curtain wall system is greatly affected by the construction quality in comparison to the punch window. Compared with the three levels, i.e., loose ($4.2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$ at 75 Pa), average ($2.1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$ at 75 Pa), and tight ($0.7 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$ at 75 Pa), which are the air-tightness values of the building envelope defined by ASHRAE [108], all buildings built after 2010 in Korea were at an

air-tight level higher than the average. This is because all apartment houses and buildings recently built in Korea are high-rises and have been built following increased interest in air-tightness owing to the stack effect and improved construction technologies. Figure 2-20 shows a comparison of the envelope air-tightness between domestic and overseas buildings according to the year of completion. Figure 2-21 shows a comparison of the envelope air-tightness for domestic buildings based on the envelope type and year of completion [95].

Figure 2-20 Comparison of envelope air-tightness between domestic and overseas buildings according to completion year

Figure 2-21 Comparison of envelope air-tightness for domestic buildings according to envelope type and completion year

Only a few studies have been conducted on high-rise buildings that are not residential buildings [98] [109-110]. The reason for this is that residential buildings are classified by households in apartment and their air-tightness can be easily measured; in contrast, large business facilities are difficult to measure owing to equipment, time, manpower, and cost limitations. Shin [93] measured the air-tightness of four non-residential high-rise buildings. Most high-rise buildings used for business facilities and complex purposes are mainly made of a curtain wall, and because they are planned openly, their internal resistance is smaller than that of residential buildings; thus, the air-tightness of the building envelope is extremely important [37]. As a result of the measurement, the air-tight buildings were measured within the range of 2.20–3.30 m³/h·m² at 75 Pa, and the rest of the buildings were measured within the range of 4.80–6.01 m³/h·m² at 75 Pa. In addition, the n value was measured to be within the range of 0.56–0.63, with an average of 0.61, thus demonstrating a trend similar to that of residential facilities. It is thus necessary to discuss the derivation of a representative value suitable when considering domestic buildings by reviewing the current value of 0.67, which is applied based on foreign data. In addition, in the results of the curtain wall mock-up test conducted prior to construction, the standards were sufficiently satisfied, whereas the air-tightness level of the curtain wall measured at the actual site was lower than the planned level. Thus, the air-tightness of the building envelope measured in an actual building rather than the air-tightness level determined in the design should be reflected.

2.3.3 Air-tightness prediction according to various techniques

Research is also being conducted to predict the air-tightness using new methods owing to the disadvantages and limitations of existing methods for evaluating air-tightness. Such a new method was used to create a database of air-tightness test results obtained *in situ* for 58 local residential units. An analysis of these measurement results indicates that there are four input parameters, which had been previously investigated and evaluated, that have a dominant effect

on the test results. The possibility of successfully predicting the air-tightness was examined by applying a neural network model [111-115]. However, because a limitation of this study is the generalization of results, further research must be conducted using a larger sample of the measured data, and additional configurations of neural networks must be investigated.

Ji et al. [94] [116-117] performed a statistical analysis based on empirical models to derive a model equation that could predict the air-tightness of reinforced concrete apartment buildings, which are popular in Asia. Air-tightness data from 486 units measured by the authors in the past 8 years were used. For an effective prediction of air-tightness, a correlation analysis and a multiple regression analysis were applied step-by-step in their study. The statistical approach in their study has a limitation in that the prediction results may vary depending on the attributes and type of data collected by various countries.

Han [118] developed a multi-zone network airflow model calibration process to improve the predictive performance of building air-tightness. In their study, a theoretical examination of existing air-tightness measurement methods was conducted. This study emphasized the necessity of an airflow movement prediction simulation and a simulation correction in the building used to establish the air-tightness prediction model correction process. Then, a correction process was established by analyzing the air-tightness variables of the building. This study also conducted simulations on other buildings for validation. Because a simulation correction model was also created in this study, there is a limitation in that it is impossible to predict the air-tightness of other buildings using a simulation.

Shin [93] proposed a calculation method for determining the air infiltration of high-rise buildings based on the air-tightness and pressure due to the stack effect. Because a review of the infiltration rate for high-rise buildings was conducted based on the same measurements used for low-rise buildings, it did not accurately reflect the stack effect impacting the amount of infiltrating air in high-rise buildings. In their study, the air-tightness requirement of various countries was

first investigated and measurements were performed in different buildings. As a result, an air-tightness database was presented. Next, to simplify the pressure difference across the envelope in high-rise buildings, an averaging method was suggested to consider the changes in the pressure difference across the envelope owing to the stack effect. Finally, an estimation model was proposed by applying the coefficients as complex factors influencing the pressure difference across the building envelope in high-rise buildings. This study also has a limitation in that it is impossible to predict the household air-tightness of other buildings because the method predicts the amount of infiltration of the entire building through a simulation correction.

This study is different from the concept of TDC previously reviewed, but the viewpoint of predicting the air-tightness by using the differential pressure formed by the stack effect is the same. Cho [29] proposed TDC' which can be used to calculate the leakage area between the internal compartments similar to the calculation of the TDC using the air-tightness ratio.

Yoon et al. [38] redefined the TDC to reflect the leakage area, which is an input parameter that is difficult to measure appropriately from the perspective of simulation modeling. Based on the measured pressure distribution of the analyzed building, the unknown input parameters were deduced primarily using the TDC'. The uncertain input parameters (leakage area and flow coefficient and exponent) were then optimized using a GA. However, their study measured the input parameters of the simulation such as the leakage area. In other words, there is a disadvantage in that the leakage area must be measured for an element in the horizontal leakage path of the building. In addition, uncertainty inevitably exists when the equation proposed by ASHRAE is used to convert the predicted leakage area into air-tightness.

Therefore, in the present study, a new method is proposed to measure air-tightness using the pressure difference instead of directly measuring the leakage area, which is a disadvantage of previous studies.

2.4 Discussion

This chapter theoretically examined a new method to measure the air-tightness using the differential pressure naturally generated by the stack effect in a building. In addition, this chapter examined the driving force of air in a building, as well as the factors influencing the formation of differential pressure. The relationship among the differential pressure, air-tightness, and airflow was also analyzed. The principles of existing air-tightness measurement methods were reviewed, and the limitations of these existing methods were analyzed. Finally, the originality of this study was established through a review of studies conducted on the measurement and prediction of air-tightness. A summary of this chapter is as follows.

- 1) Factors affecting the driving force of air in a building include the stack effect, wind, the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, and mechanical ventilation systems. The driving force of air in a building can vary based on the external environment of the target building, architectural characteristics, facility characteristics, and living patterns of occupants. A differential pressure in a building is generated by the stack effect and is based on the relationship between the differential pressure, the air-tightness, and the air volume in the building. Additionally, the higher the air-tightness level, the higher is the differential pressure that is formed; thus, the amount of air passing through decreases. The differential pressure, air-tightness, and airflow in a building can be explained by the Bernoulli equation. Because the differential pressure in a building is formed by the stack effect, the pressure distribution varies according to the air-tightness of the components in the building. The relationship between pressure difference and air-tightness can be explained by the pressure distribution and TDC by the stack effect in a high-rise residential building. As a result, the relationship among the differential pressure, air-tightness, and airflow in the building was identified, and

the theoretical validity of this study was established.

- 2) Tracer gas methods and fan pressurization methods were reviewed as representative approaches to measuring air-tightness. Depending on the injection method, tracer gas methods can include pulse, decay, and step-up (constant injection) approaches. The principles, characteristics, and measurement techniques for each method were described. The limitations of each method were also analyzed. Next, the principles and measurement techniques of the blower door test were described. In addition, the differences between criteria related to the blower door test were analyzed, and a method for expressing the air-tightness of each criterion was considered. Limitations of the blower door test include a complex measurement preparation process, high cost, and measurement-related limitations. By analyzing these various limitations, the need for a simple method to measure air-tightness such as that proposed in this paper was emphasized.
- 3) Domestic and international research trends on the measurement and prediction of air-tightness were investigated. CO₂ concentration decay tests are conducted to measure the air-tightness by considering the CO₂ gas generated by occupants. Because CO₂ is a low-concentration gas, there is some uncertainty regarding this method, and many efforts have been made to improve this approach. The blower door test measures the air-tightness of numerous buildings to secure data, and studies to predict air-tightness by matching these data with statistical techniques are in progress. However, it is difficult to secure a large number of air-tightness data points. In addition, this study is different from the concept of TDC previously reviewed, but the viewpoint of predicting the air-tightness by using the differential pressure formed by the stack effect is the same. Using TDC' proposed by Cho, Yoon et al. redefined the TDC to reflect the leakage area, which is an input parameter that is difficult to measure appropriately from the

perspective of simulation modeling. However, their study measured the input parameters of the simulation such as the leakage area. In other words, there is a disadvantage in that the leakage area must be measured for an element in the horizontal leakage path of the building. Therefore, in the present study, a new method is proposed to measure air-tightness using the pressure difference instead of directly measuring the leakage area, which is a disadvantage of previous studies.

Chapter 3 Development of a new method to measure air-tightness

This chapter was proposed a new method to measure air-tightness using differential pressure. It was mentioned that this study was essential by reviewing the limitations of the existing air-tightness measurement method. Also, it was presented to the background and principle of the proposed method in this study, which was the air-tightness measurement using the differential pressure. It was verified to the theoretical validity of the method and equation proposed in this study through the power law equation used in the existing air-tightness measurement method. This chapter was presented a specific process for applying the proposed method in an actual building. Also, this chapter was shown to the results of a case study that the predicted air-tightness by the proposed method was compared with the measured air-tightness by the blower door test method. Lastly, it was examined to the dependence on the temperature difference between indoor and outdoor and the height difference in the building, which are the main factors that form the pressure differential, and was suggested to differential pressure conditions to apply the proposed method.

3.1 Principles of a method to predict the air-tightness using differential pressure

3.1.1 Theoretical background

Air-tightness is defined through the relationship between differential pressure and the airflow rate of building components. The volume of airflow in a building is defined as the differential pressure, as shown in Equation (30), and the air volume is expressed by the magnitude of the

differential pressure and air-tightness on the airflow path.

$$Q = C\Delta P^n \quad (30)$$

$$\ln Q = \ln(C) + n \ln(\Delta P) \quad (43)$$

where Q is the airflow of the target space (m^3/h), ΔP is the pressure difference at the target space (Pa), C is the airflow coefficient of the target space ($\text{m}^3/(\text{h}\cdot\text{Pa}^n)$), and n is the flow exponent of the target space.

In buildings, natural airflow can occur due to the pressure differences caused by wind and temperature differences. The airflow rates are also related to the air-tightness of various building components, including exterior and interior walls, doors, windows, floors, and elevator doors on the airflow path [33]. Sherman experimented with thousands of buildings and defined the relationship between pressure differences and airflow shown in Equation (30) [28] [119]. In Equation (30), the airflow coefficient, C , represents the size of the leakage area, and the flow exponent, n , is the pressure index. It shows the rate of change in the airflow rate according to the pressure difference when airflow occurs through leakage at the target location [120]. The value of n is between 0.5 and 1.0; the more the airflow is turbulent, which is characteristic of an airflow path with a large leakage area, the closer n will be to 0.5, and the more the airflow is laminar, which is characteristic of an airflow path with a small leakage area (such as small gaps and cracks), the closer n will be to 1 [58]. The relationship between several differential pressures and the corresponding airflow rates in terms of C and n is shown in Figure 3-1(a). Figure 3-1 (b) shows the relationship between different pressures and the airflow rates using natural logarithms as C and n . To define C and n , respectively, the airflow in the target space (defined by Equation (30)) must be transformed into Equation (43) [57]. The value of n is the covariance of the differential pressure and airflow divided by the variance of the differential pressure. The value of C can be obtained by substituting the value of n in Equation (30). Once C and n are defined, the airflow can be calculated under any pressure condition.

(a) Airflow rate versus pressure difference

(b) Airflow rate versus pressure difference using natural logarithms

Figure 3-1 Relationship between pressure difference and airflow

3.1.2 Differentiation from conventional air-tightness measurement methods

In this study, the novelty is presented to a method for predicting the air-tightness using differential pressure instead of the blower door test. In principle and concept, the air-tightness prediction method proposed in this study is based on the pressure difference of the components in the building, which are similar to those of a blower door test. However, unlike an existing blower door test, it is not necessary to produce a high differential pressure condition that differs from the actual building condition. Figure 3-2 and Table 3-1 are simply explained to comparison of the blower door test and the proposed method. The key of the blower door test is the measurement of the data set of the differential pressure and air volume of the location to be measured. It measures the amount of air that flows out of the building envelope by pressurizing or depressurizing the measurement location to a certain pressure. It is impossible to measure the air volume without a fan of the blower door test. However, this study proposes a method to measure the air volume without a fan. Among the winter characteristics of high-rise residential buildings, there is a stack effect, there is a characteristic that the amount of air flowing in and the amount of air flowing out to one space is always the same under steady state conditions [25] [27]. As a result, it is necessary to the differential pressure and air volume flowing out of the building

envelope to measure air-tightness of building envelope. If the air volume entering the front door of household can be measured, the air volume flowing out of the building envelope can be known. The amount of air entering the front door of household can be obtained through the air leakage test report of the front door of household. Also, the differential pressure can be easily measured using a portable differential pressure meter. Therefore, this study was proposed a new method to predict the air-tightness by utilizing these points.

As a result, it can be said that the novelty is that the number of differential pressures to be measured is small compared to the conventional measurement method, and that the air volume is not directly measured unlike the direct measurement of the air leakage area or air volume as in research [29] [38].

3.2 Predicting the air-tightness by measuring the differential pressure of building components based on actual weather conditions

3.2.1 Formula suggestion

The prediction method proposed in this study can be found in its theoretical basis in the relationship between pressure difference and air-tightness. The reason is that the air-tightness affects the differential pressure distribution and air flow in the building [33]. The air-tightness prediction method using differential pressure proposed in this study is proposed by using the Power law equation used in the conventional blower door test. This is because the purpose of this study is to propose a simple method that can replace the blower door test. In addition, it was proved that the proposed method is theoretically possible by using the Power law equation used in the existing blower door test.

Table 3-1 Comparison of the existing method and proposed method

Comparison	Blower Door Test	Proposed method
Measuring element	$Q(\text{Airflow}), \Delta P$ (Building envelope)	ΔP (Building component with airtightness, Building envelope)
Calculation element	n, C	$Q(\text{Airflow}), n, C$
Number of measurements	5 to 10	≥ 2
Power law equation	$Q=C(\Delta P)^n$	$Q=C(\Delta P)^n$
Result of measurements	1/h @ 50Pa, EqLA @ 10Pa, ELA @ 4Pa	1/h @ 50Pa, EqLA @ 10Pa, ELA @ 4Pa
Air leakage area	$A_L=10000Q_r \frac{\sqrt{\rho/2\Delta P_r}}{C_D}$	$A_L=10000Q_r \frac{\sqrt{\rho/2\Delta P_r}}{C_D}$

Figure 3-2 Comparison of the existing method and proposed method

First of all, Equation (44) means that the amount of air flowing into the front door of the household and the amount of air flowing out to the building envelope of the household are always the same under steady state. Theoretically, it is assumed that the air flow in the space under steady state is only moved through the main air flow paths of high-rise residential buildings such as elevator doors, corridors, front door of household, and building envelope. This is because the amount of air flowing in and the amount of air flowing out is always the same in a space by a

stack effect [38]. First of all, Equation (44) means that the amount of air flowing into the front door of the measurement

$$Q_a = Q_b \quad (44)$$

where Q_a is the amount of air that flows into the front door of the measurement location by the stack effect (m^3/h) and Q_b is the amount of air that flows out the building envelope of the measurement location by the stack effect (m^3/h).

The equations proposed in this study to predict the air-tightness by measuring differential pressure are as follows. Equation (30) is the Power law equation used in the blower door test. In Equation (30), C and n values, which represent characteristics of the components to be measured, are unknown, so equations for the two differential pressures are required and are given in Equations (45) and (46). The differential pressure and air volume excluding C and n values should be required, and the air volume can be obtained using the air volume and differential pressure of the front door of household in apartment as premised in Equation (44), but the differential pressure of the building envelope must be measured. However, since the same differential pressure is always generated in the same space, conditions in which different differential pressures can occur must be configured. At a single weather condition, the differential pressure of a single building component is constant. Therefore, measurements from different weather conditions are required to define the two unknown factors n and C . For that purpose, Equations (45) and (46) are substituted into Equation (47). As shown in Equation (47), if the binomial theorem based on C in Equation (45) becomes Equation (48), and substituting C in Equation (48) into Equation (46), it becomes Equation (49). This is because C and n values do not change under any pressure difference condition in the particular characteristics building [119]. Equation (50) is the logarithm of Equation (47) needed to define n , and n is summarized as given in Equation (51). In Equation (51), the data set of the building envelope can be obtained through the actual measurement, and the air volume data set of the building envelope can be secured through the air volume and the

differential pressure at the front door of the household in apartment, so the n value can be obtained. Once n is organized into the value of Equation (51), C can be calculated using Equation (52). Equation (52) is a summary by substituting the n-value of Equation (51) into Equation (45). In Equation (52), C can also be obtained using only the differential pressure and air volume of the building envelope, similar to the n value, so that both C and n values can be obtained only by measuring the differential pressure. The airflow Q_2 can then be expressed as Equation (53). In that way, the air-tightness metric at 50 Pa suggested by the existing blower door test method (ACH50) can be calculated using Equation (54).

$$Q = C\Delta P^n \quad (30)$$

$$Q_1 = C(\Delta P_1)^n \quad (45)$$

$$Q_2 = C(\Delta P_2)^n \quad (46)$$

$$\frac{Q_2}{Q_1} = \frac{(\Delta P_2)^n}{(\Delta P_1)^n} \quad (47)$$

$$C = \frac{Q_1}{(\Delta P_1)^n} \quad (48)$$

$$Q_2 = \frac{Q_1}{(\Delta P_1)^n} \times (\Delta P_2)^n \quad (49)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{Q_2}{Q_1}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{\Delta P_2}{\Delta P_1}\right)^n \quad (50)$$

$$n = \frac{\ln Q_2 - \ln Q_1}{\ln \Delta P_2 - \ln \Delta P_1} \quad (51)$$

$$C = \frac{Q_1}{(\Delta P_1)^{\frac{\ln Q_2 - \ln Q_1}{\ln \Delta P_2 - \ln \Delta P_1}}} \quad (52)$$

$$Q_2 = \frac{Q_1}{(\Delta P_1)^{\frac{\ln Q_2 - \ln Q_1}{\ln \Delta P_2 - \ln \Delta P_1}}} (\Delta P_2)^{\frac{\ln Q_2 - \ln Q_1}{\ln \Delta P_2 - \ln \Delta P_1}} \quad (53)$$

$$\text{ACH50} = \frac{1}{V} \times \frac{Q_1}{(\Delta P_1)^{\frac{\ln Q_2 - \ln Q_1}{\ln \Delta P_2 - \ln \Delta P_1}}} (\Delta P_2)^{\frac{\ln Q_2 - \ln Q_1}{\ln \Delta P_2 - \ln \Delta P_1}} \quad (54)$$

where Q_1 is the airflow of building envelope in conditions of outdoor temperature 1 (m^3/h), ΔP_1 is the pressure difference at the building envelope in conditions of outdoor temperature 1 (Pa), Q_2 is the airflow of building envelope in conditions of outdoor temperature 2 (m^3/h), ΔP_2 is the pressure difference at the building envelope in conditions of outdoor temperature 2 (Pa), V is the

volume of the target space (m^3) and ACH50 is the air change rate through the building envelope at 50 Pa (h^{-1}).

As above, C and n values can be defined as the differential pressure of the building envelope that can be secured through measurement, the air volume of the front door of household in apartment, and the air volume of the building envelope that can be obtained from the differential pressure. Also, with the proposed method, the air-tightness can be predicted in the same way as the blower door test. However, due to the nature of the proposed equation, it is only possible to measure the differential pressure under at least two different ambient temperature conditions. In this study, the theoretical basis for predicting the air-tightness by measuring only the differential pressure through equations (45) to (54) was presented.

Figure 3-3 shows how to predict air-tightness by measuring the differential pressure of building components on the horizontal air path under actual weather conditions. This method can be applied wherever the airflow of a building has a constant direction through a series of paths. The air flows from the first partition to the second under the assumption that the volume of air is theoretically always the same along the serial airflow paths. In other words, a single quantity of air moves from the second partition to the i^{th} partition [38]. Therefore, the air-tightness of each component can be predicted by measuring the differential pressure of each component along the horizontal air path, as shown in Figure 3-3.

3.2.2 Verification of the theoretical validity of the formula

The method proposed in this study can predict air-tightness with two data sets of air volume and differential pressure of the front door of household and the differential pressure of the building envelope, and it is proved that it is theoretically possible with a new equation using the power law equation.

Figure 3-3 Predicting air-tightness using pressure differences across various partitions in the airflow path

In the case of the existing blower door test that measures air-tightness, the measured differential pressure and air volume data sets are at least 5-7. However, since the method proposed in this study is required the two data sets of differential pressure, it was examined whether there is a difference from the actual blower door test result. In the case of the power law equation used in the blower door test, it is necessary to have only two data sets of differential pressure and air volume to obtain C and n values. Of course, in the blower door test measurement standard, it is recommended to measure 5-7 differential pressure and air volume data sets [24] [57] [61-62], but it was reviewed whether it is reliable with only two differential pressure and air volume data sets.

Therefore, it was examined whether the C and n values calculated by the equation proposed in this study are reliable. Based on the actual measurement results of the blower door test, C and n values were calculated using 5 to 7 differential pressure and air volume data sets. In addition, C and n values were calculated by the method proposed in this study by using two data sets among the measured results, and compared and analyzed with calculated C and n values using data sets of 5 to 7 differential pressures and air volumes. Table 3-2 shows the measured results of C, n, and

air-tightness using 7 data sets of differential pressure and air volume by blower door test. This is measured results of households in apartment located on the 27th floor of a high-rise residential building.

Table 3-2 C, n, and air-tightness results in the 27 stories building using blower door test

Reference Pressure	Number of ΔP	Air-tightness (h^{-1})	Air Flow Coefficient (C) ($m^3/(h \cdot Pa^n)$)	Flow Exponent (n)
50 Pa	7 set	2.92	59.61	0.609

Table 3-3 is a comparison of C and n values obtained by the blower door test and C and n values obtained by the proposed method. There was no significant difference between the results measured with 7 differential pressure data sets using the blower door test and the predicted results with two differential pressure data sets using the proposed method. However, there were cases where a slight difference occurred. This is because it is produced to a high differential pressure condition that differs from the actual building condition by the blower door test, so the effect on the temperature difference can be ignored if the differential pressure by the blower door test is greater than the differential pressure naturally generated by the temperature difference [53]. However, the measurement was performed on the 27th floor, and the differential pressure was about 34 Pa. Therefore, if C and n values are calculated using the differential pressure data set with a pressure less than 34 Pa, the effect on the temperature difference cannot be excluded. That is, if C and n values are calculated using 20 Pa and 30 Pa, it is difficult to accurately calculate due to the dependence on the temperature difference. Therefore, the one differential pressure data of two differential pressure data sets to calculate C and n values is larger than the differential pressure that can occur due to the temperature difference. Also, the differential pressure by the temperature difference is slightly different for each building, but C and n values can be predicted similarly to the actual value if C and n values are predicted with two differential pressure data sets with a

difference of about 20 Pa or more. The most similar to the measured value is when the interval between the two differential pressure data sets is the largest. As a result, it was determined that it is reasonable to predict the air-tightness using the equation proposed in this study.

Table 3-3 Comparison of C and n values calculated by existing and proposed methods

Method	Number of ΔP	Using Pressure Difference	Air Flow Coefficient (C) ($m^3/(h \cdot Pa^n)$)		Flow Exponent (n)	
			Value	Error (BDT*–PM*)	Value	Error (BDT*–PM*)
Blower door test (BDT*)	7 set	20Pa to 70Pa	59.61	-	0.609	-
Proposed method (PM*)	2 set	20 Pa, 30 Pa	47.15	12.46	0.682	-0.073
		20 Pa, 40 Pa	53.40	6.21	0.641	-0.032
		20 Pa, 50 Pa	56.08	3.53	0.624	-0.015
		20 Pa, 60 Pa	57.10	2.51	0.618	-0.009
		20 Pa, 70 Pa	57.76	1.85	0.614	-0.005
		30 Pa, 40 Pa	66.29	-6.68	0.582	0.027
		30 Pa, 50 Pa	67.12	-7.51	0.578	0.031
		30 Pa, 60 Pa	66.54	-6.94	0.581	0.028
		30 Pa, 70 Pa	66.30	-6.69	0.582	0.027
		40 Pa, 50 Pa	68.38	-8.77	0.574	0.035
		40 Pa, 60 Pa	66.76	-7.16	0.580	0.029
		40 Pa, 70 Pa	66.30	-6.69	0.582	0.027
		50 Pa, 60 Pa	64.63	-5.02	0.588	0.021
		50 Pa, 70 Pa	64.75	-5.15	0.588	0.021
		60 Pa, 70 Pa	64.91	-5.31	0.587	0.022

3.2.3 Proposal of processes applicable to actual buildings

Figure 3-4 shows the prediction process in detail. The differential pressure generated under natural conditions is measured [121], and the airflow rate of each analyzed component is calculated for the measured differential pressure condition.

Step 1 describes the prerequisites or provisions required to apply the method suggested in this study. The differential pressure should be greater than the error range of the pressure gauge. Therefore, the weather must create conditions that satisfy that requirement. Additionally, the

direction of the indoor airflow must be clear. An important premise in analyzing airflow in a building is that the air volume passing through each building partition is constant across the horizontal airflow paths, as explained above, and the pressure difference varies with the weather conditions. Unlike the conventional blower door test method, the air-tightness prediction method proposed in this study does not measure the airflow volume but predicts air-tightness based on the pressure difference. For that prediction, air leakage test data should be prepared for building components along the horizontal airflow line. Then, the airflow rates are calculated using the differential pressure conditions measured according to the previous air-tightness test report showing the relationship between the differential pressure and the airflow rate. For example, in a residential building, the air leakage report for the entrance door is easily and reliably obtained. If no air-tightness reports are available for the analyzed building components, the air-tightness of a representative building component can be measured by the blower door test method in the field.

In Step 2, the pressure difference of the front door of household and building envelope are measured at least twice under different weather conditions. The airflow rates for the front door and building envelope are calculated for the measured pressure difference. Using two or more sets of differential pressure data and airflow rate data, the C and n values can be deduced using Equations (7) and (8).

Finally, in Step 3, the air-tightness metric (ACH50) of the building envelope is calculated using those C and n values.

Figure 3-4 Process for predicting air-tightness using pressure differences

3.3 Application of air-tightness prediction method using pressure difference

A process that can apply the newly proposed method in this study to an actual building was presented. In this chapter, a case study was conducted to evaluate the applicability of the proposed method to predict the air-tightness using differential pressure measurement under actual climate conditions.

3.3.1 Description of a target building

The differential pressure should be greater than the error range of the pressure gauge because the air-tightness prediction method proposed in this study uses the differential pressure generated in natural conditions. Therefore, the weather condition must create adequate differential pressure, and the direction of the indoor airflow must be clear. A target building for this case study was a

high-rise multi-residential building in Jeonju, Jeollabuk province, with 3 stories below the ground and 42 stories above the ground. In high-rise buildings, the direction of the airflow is clear, and the pressure difference of the building components is larger than in low-rise buildings because of the long vertical airflow in the building (i.e., the stack effect).

It is a high-rise residential building with a height of 137.9 m. This target building is used as an underground parking lot from the 3rd basement level to the 1st basement level, and the 1st and 2nd floors above the ground are composed of shopping centers and convenience facilities, and the 3rd floor above the ground is used as a neighborhood living facility. The residential part starts with the 4th floor above the ground and reaches the 42nd floor, and in the case of the 26th floor above the ground, an evacuation floor is created so that you can evacuate from fire. A total of 302 apartment houses are composed of 75 units of 43.89 m², 152 units of 84.02 m², and 75 units of 84.04 m². Table 3-4 is a description of the building to be measured.

Table 3-4 Details regarding the building to be evaluated

Building information	Location: Jeonju, Jeollabuk province, South Korea
	Type: Multi-residential building
	Number of floors: 42F above ground and B3F underground
	Height: 137.9 m
	Floor area of each household: 43.89 m ² – 84.04 m ²

The high-rise residential building was measured to consider the airflow throughout the building. This is because the method was proposed to predict the air-tightness by using the differential pressure that may be occurred due to the stack effect.

The vertical air flow path in the building is connected from the 3rd basement to the rooftop, and there are two elevator shafts and stairwells that are connected from the 3rd basement to the 42nd floor.

In the horizontal air flow path, there are four households in apartment, and there is a corridor

in the middle, and a fixed window in contact with the outside air exists in the corridor. Air is moved through the front door of each household through the corridor from the stairwell, elevator shaft, and fixed windows in contact with the outside air, and flows out or inflows through the building envelope of each household.

On the first floor of the building to be measured, there are shopping malls and various convenience facilities. Since the area where the outside air can be contacted is large and the door is not air-tight, there is a high possibility that air will move through it. However, shopping malls and various convenience facilities are blocked with walls to prevent outdoor air. Therefore, outdoor air can only flow into the underground parking lot and the lobby on the first floor. Figure 3-5 shows the characteristics and bird's-eye view of the building to be measured.

Figure 3-5 Bird's-eye view of the target building and building characteristics

3.3.2 Description of field measurements

A. Measurement period and location

As explained above, the method to predict the air-tightness proposed in this study is important to understand the airflow throughout the building. It can be said that the air flow is mainly determined by the differential pressure generated by the outside temperature, wind direction and wind speed, the shape of the building, the ventilation system, and the patterns of the occupants. Therefore, it is important to limit the above factors to understand the pressure distribution of the entire building. The actual measurement was conducted at dawn to minimize the effect of wind. The elevator and ventilation systems were stopped in operation.

Temperature and humidity are measured at the external weather environment and the temperature of components in the building. The differential pressures were measured at the elevator door, stair door, front door of household, and building envelope, which are components on the horizontal and vertical air flow paths in the building.

To predict air-tightness using the method proposed in this study, two sets of differential pressure data are required for the analyzed building components. Therefore, field measurements were made twice in the same location at times with different outdoor air conditions. As the interval between the two differential pressure data sets increases, the predicted result was similar to the measured result using the blower door test. Therefore, the second measurement was performed by selecting a day that was formed high pressure difference. The first measurement was performed from October 31 to November 1, 2017, and the second measurement was conducted from January 26 to 27, 2018. Table 3-5 shows the measurement items and the range and accuracy of the measurement equipment.

The measurement items and locations are shown in Figure 3-6. The measurement locations were selected by directions of the horizontal and vertical airflow in the analyzed building. There are two main air flow paths at the horizontal measurement location. The first is a case where

outside air flows into the corridor through the fixed window of the corridor, and this air flows into the household through the front door of the household, and this air flows out the building envelope. The second is the elevator shaft and stair room, where the air of elevator shaft and stair room flow into the household through the corridor and the front door of the household, and this air flow out the building envelope. On the 26th floor, the evacuation floor is directly connected to the outside air, so air flows into the evacuation room from the elevator shaft and the stair room through the windbreak room, and the air flows out the evacuation room. As a result, the horizontal measurement positions for the differential pressure were the elevator shaft, stair door, front door, and building envelope of the residential building unit.

Table 3-5 Measurement instruments and specifications

Measurement item	Measurement instruments	Specifications	Confer.
Air-tightness	Blower door test (Minneapolis DG-700)	Range	510 to 10,700 CMH
		Accuracy	5%
Pressure difference	GE Druck DPI 740	Range	75,000 to 115,000 Pa
		Accuracy	±0.02% of reading
		Resolution	1 Pa
Temperature and humidity	Testo 175 hi	Range	-20 to 55 °C
		Accuracy	±0.4 °C
		Resolution	0.1 °C
Outdoor temperature, wind velocity and direction	Davis Vantage Pro2 6152	Range	-40 to 64 °C
		Accuracy	±0.5 °C
		Resolution	0.1 °C

At the vertical measurement location, the outside air flow into the lobby on the first floor, and the air moves to the upper part through the elevator shaft and the stair room, and flows into the household through the corridor and the front door of household. The air flows out the building envelope. The first floor is a lobby, and the second floor is connected to the first floor without a ceiling, so there is no the building envelope and all air are moved to the upper part. The 3rd floor

is used as a neighborhood living facility, the 4th floor to the 42nd floor is the residential unit.

As a result, the vertical measurement locations were the 3rd basement floor, first floor lobby (where there is a lot of air inflow), 4th floor (as a lower floor), 16th floor (neutral zone), 36th floor (upper floor), and 42nd floor (top floor). The number of measurement locations for differential pressure is minimized by the proposed method, which can predict air-tightness using differential pressure measurements from only a few locations. However, in high-rise buildings where the stack effect occurs, differential pressure should be measured at various heights because it varies according to the height of the building. In other words, measurements were made at different vertical points to examine the characteristics of differential pressure by height.

B. Measurement of external weather, temperature, and humidity

First, the external weather environment was measured. This is because it is essential when measuring the air-tightness using the blower door test. It was measured to the outside temperature, wind direction, and speed. Especially, outside temperature is very important because the differential pressure generated in the main air flow path of the building, elevator shaft, stair room, front of household in apartment, and building envelope, is different depending on the outside temperature. In addition, as the wind direction and wind speed increase in intensity, the wind pressure acting on the building can have a significant influence, so it is a must be measured. In order to minimize the influence of the wind, it was measured at dawn when there is not much wind, but the conditions at the time of measurement are difficult to judge other than the measured results. The measuring equipment used a weather station such as the Davis Vantage Pro 2 6152 model. This model is commonly used in many research institutes and can measure cloudiness, humidity, solar irradiation, etc. other than the items to be measured in this study.

Second, in the case of temperature and humidity measurement, the temperature distribution in the building must be measured because it is very closely related to the air flow in the building.

This is because the differential pressure generated by the stack effect may vary depending on the difference between the outside temperature and the indoor temperature. Temperature and humidity were continuously measured during the measurement period in the main air flow paths such as stairwells, elevator shafts, corridors and lobbies, and households using Testo 175 hi model. Also, the temperature and humidity distribution were measured each floor because these were varied depending on the height of each floor.

Figure 3-6 Analyzed building and the measurement items and their locations

C. Pressure difference measurement

Differential pressure is the most important factor that causes airflow in the building. Also, it is absolutely necessary to apply the method proposed in this study. The differential pressure was measured horizontally for the main air flow paths such as elevator shaft, stair room, front door of household in apartment, and building envelope. It cannot be vertically measured for all spaces due to the limitation of the number of equipment. For this reason, measurements were made mainly on the basement floor and the first floor where the main airflow occurs. Also, residential units were measured on the 4th floor, where the residential unit begins, on the 16th floor, which is the middle floor estimated to be neutral zone, and on the 36th and the 42nd floors, which is the top layer. The differential pressure was measured using Testo 510i, a Smart probe pressure difference model. In particular, differential pressure measurement of the building envelope has to measure the inside and outside of the household in apartment. Therefore, the hose was exposed to the outside and the remaining parts were sealed with vinyl to minimize the airflow outside and inside, and the external pressure was measured for each layer. Although it is continuously measured, the error was corrected by measuring the absolute pressure at the place where the differential pressure is measured using the GE Druck DPI 740 model. In addition, the external pressure for each floor was corrected by measuring the absolute pressure for the outside of the first floor and the rooftop. In the case of absolute pressure, measurement was carried out while going up from the basement to the rooftop, and the measurement was carried out while descending from the rooftop to the basement. This was conducted alternately in consideration of errors that may be occurred during movement. The movement time was minimized during the measurement, and the time was recorded for all measurements to be compared with the differential pressure result measured with a differential pressure gauge. Figure 3-7 is a view of the equipment installation in the first measurement. Figure 3-8 shows the status of the secondary measurement.

Figure 3-7 A view of the equipment installation in the first measurement

Figure 3-8 A view of the equipment installation in the second measurement

D. Air-tightness measurement

To compare the accuracy of the air-tightness predicted according to the magnitude of the differential pressure, the air-tightness was measured on the 4th, 16th, and 42nd floors by using the blower door test method. All intentional openings, including the hood of the kitchen, sink, exhaust fan in the bathroom, drain, washbasin, and a ventilating opening (but not the building envelope of the location to be measured), were either sealed or shut (Figure 3-10). The fan was installed at the front door, and the space was depressurized and pressurized under various pressure conditions. The air-tightness of the building envelope was measured as the airflow rate through the building envelope at those various pressure difference conditions based on ISO 9972 [61] and EN 13829 [24]. The air-tightness was measured by applying the above standard of the blower door test method using Retrotect's Panel system 2000 series. The air-tightness was measured at intervals of 10 Pa based on 70 Pa by the fan pressurization method and the fan depressurization method, and the average value was applied (Figure 3-9).

Figure 3-9 Installation view of measuring air-tightness using blower door test

Figure 3-10 Air-tight works to measure the air-tightness

3.3.3 Results of field measurements

In the case of the field measurement, the air-tightness should be predicted using the method proposed in this study, so each day of the different outdoor temperature was selected and carried out for a total of two times. The measured results are as follows.

A. External weather conditions

Figure 3-11 shows the distribution of temperature and humidity of external weather environment in the first measurement. For the external weather environment, outside temperature and humidity, wind direction, and wind speed were measured, and the results are as follows.

External temperature and humidity, wind direction, and speed were average values between am 2 and 4 am when the differential pressure was measured, and the outdoor temperature was 5.1 °C, and the outdoor humidity was 64%. Based on the 42nd floor, the indoor and outdoor temperature difference was 19 °C (outdoor: 5.1 °C, 42nd floor household: 24.1 °C).

The wind speed was also an average value between 2 am and 4 am, and the main wind direction was SSW in the south-southwest direction, and the average wind speed was 0.02 m/s, with little wind blowing.

Figure 3-11 Results of outdoor temperature and humidity in first measurement

Figure 3-12 shows the distribution of temperature and humidity of external weather environment in the second measurement. In the second measurement, as in the first measurement, outside temperature and humidity, wind direction and wind speed were measured in the external weather environment. The external temperature and humidity, wind direction, and speed are average values between 2 am and 4 am, when the differential pressure is being measured. Based on the 42nd floor, the indoor/outdoor temperature difference was 37.62 °C (outdoor temperature: -13.02 °C, 42nd floor household temperature: 24.6 °C), and because it was selected the day that the outdoor temperature was very low. In other words, temperature difference between indoor and

outdoor was very large.

In the case of wind speed, the average value between 2 am and 4 am, the main wind direction was WNW in the northwest direction, and the average wind speed was 2.4 m/s, which was stronger than the first measurement due to the influence of very cold weather. However, it was expected that it would not significantly affect the differential pressure caused by the stack effect. The magnitude of the differential pressure caused by the stack effect was expected to be significant due to the very low outside temperature.

Figure 3-12 Results of outdoor temperature and humidity in second measurement

B. Temperature and humidity

Tables 3-6 show the temperature and humidity measurement results in the first measurement. The temperature and humidity measurement results show the average value from 2 am to 4 am, which is the time when the differential pressure was measured. The change in temperature and humidity of the household in apartment did not vary greatly by floor, and was approximately between 24 °C and 25 °C. In addition, the temperature distribution was the highest in the middle floor, which was judged to be an error that occurred because the households in apartment were heating the same at 26 °C, but the households in apartment were not heated at the same 26 °C.

However, in the case of the fourth floor, despite heating at 26 °C, the temperature was distributed as low as about 20 °C, which was judged to have been formed at a low temperature because heating was not performed in the neighborhood living facilities on the third floor. In the case of the other floors, both the upper and lower floors were heated, so it is expected that the temperature distribution was higher than that of the fourth floor. All paths such as hall, stair, and elevator shaft showed higher temperature distribution as the number of floors increased from low to high. The temperature distribution of the hall was between 17.1 °C and 19.5 °C, the stairwell was between 17.2 °C and 19.6 °C, and the temperature distribution of the hall and the stair was similar. In the case of the elevator shaft, there was no significant difference between 18.3 °C and 18.9 °C, but the higher the number of floors was, the higher the temperature distribution was. The temperature of the underground parking lot was distributed at 18.4 °C in the 3rd basement level and 11 °C in the 1st basement level.

Table 3-6 Temperature and humidity measurement result of the first measurement

Floor	1 st measurement result							Outdoor (°C)
	Household in apartment		Hall		Stairwell		Elevator shaft	
	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)	Temp. (°C)	
Roof								5.1
42F	24.1	42.3	19.5	35.9	19.6	44.3	18.9	
36F	24.7	45.9	18.9	36.8	18.9	37.8	18.8	
16F	25.0	35.5	18.6	41.9	18.8	47.1	18.7	
4F	20.1	33.8	17.1	42.0	17.2	38.4	18.3	
1F			17.2	37.5	17.4	40.6		
B1								11.0
B3								18.4

* Average value from 2 a.m. to 4 a.m. (No big fluctuation)

Table 3-7 shows the temperature and humidity measurement results in the second measurement. Unlike the first measurement, the second measurement was performed in very cold weather. The temperature and humidity measurement result shows the average value from 2 am to 4 am, which is the time when the differential pressure was measured. The change in temperature and humidity of the household in apartment did not have a large fluctuation range for each floor, and was approximately between 24 °C and 24.6 °C. In the second measurement, heating was performed in the neighborhood living facility on the 3rd floor, the 4th floor showed a similar temperature distribution with the other floors. Like the first measurement, the higher the number of floors in the hall and stairs, the higher the temperature distribution was. The temperature distribution of the hall was between 9.6 °C and 10.8 °C, and the stairwell was between 8.8 °C and 10.8 °C, and the temperature distribution of the hall and the stair was similar. In the underground parking lot, the 3rd basement floor, the temperature was about 11.8 °C. In the case of the evacuation floor, the temperature of the hall and the stair was formed low due to the influence of the cold outside air, and the temperature distribution was between 9.5 °C and 9.7 °C.

Table 3-7 Temperature and humidity measurement result of the second measurement

Floor	2 nd measurement result							
	Household in apartment		Hall		Stairwell		Outdoor	
	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)	Temp. (°C)	Humi. (%)
Roof							-13.02	60.5
42F	24.6	43.8	10.8	43.9	10.8	45.5		
36F	24.3	41.9	10.6	42.8	10.6	47.8		
26F			9.7	42.5	9.5	44.4	-2.5	32.4
16F	24.2	34.0	10.6	42.0	10.5	41.6		
4F	24.0	29.1	9.6	44.5	8.80	44.0		
B3			11.8	44.1	11.3	41.9	11.8	41.6

* Average value from 2 a.m. to 4 a.m. (No big fluctuation)

C. Pressure difference

Figure 3-13 is the result of the first measurement and is the result of measuring the differential pressure of the main air flow path components. External doors were measured at the 3rd basement level, the 1st basement parking lot door, the 1st floor lobby door, and the rooftop floor. The pressure difference was measured at the inside and outside based on the external door. In the case of the lowermost layer, the 3rd basement level, it was measured as 14 Pa. In the case of the top layer, the rooftop layer, it was measured as 40 Pa.

The elevator door is the result of the difference in pressure between the inside of the elevator and the hall based on the elevator door. There was no large pressure difference in all elevator doors, and this is because it is less air-tight than other main air flow path components.

The stair door is the result of the pressure difference between the inside of the stair and the hall based on the stair door. The pressure difference of less than 5 Pa was also measured, but in the case of the stair door going to the outside entrance door to the roof floor, differential pressure was measured as 31 Pa, resulting in a higher pressure difference than other places. This is because there are several factors such as elevator doors, stair doors, and front of household in apartment on the floor where the residential building is located, but only two factors on the rooftop floor are the stair door and the external door. Therefore, a large amount of pressure was distributed because all the pressures have to be distributed the two elements.

The front door of the household in apartment is the result of measuring the pressure difference between the inside of the household in apartment and the hall based on the front door of the household. The most pressure was distributed the front door of the household because the front door of the household is the most air-tight door in a high-rise residential building. The front door of the household was measured as 54 Pa, and the reason that the front door of household was the most air-tight level, so it was judged that all the pressures were distributed the front door of household.

The building envelope is the result of measuring the pressure difference between the inside and outside of the household in apartment based on the window inside the household in apartment. Similar results were shown for each layer, and a pressure difference of about 4–6 Pa was measured.

In the case of the first measurement, the outside temperature was not very low, so that the pressure difference was measured to low results. The differential pressure on the lower floors (the 3rd basement level, the 1st floor, the 3rd floor, and the 4th floor) was positive, indicating that outdoor air flowed into the building from the main entrance door and building envelope. The differential pressure on the 16th floor and above was negative, indicating that the outdoor air flowed into the lower floors and then moved upward through the elevator shaft or stair, flowed indoors on the 16th floor and above, and then escaped through the building envelope.

For the first measurement results, where the temperature difference between indoors and outdoors was about 29 °C, the differential pressure generated on the building envelope was not considerable, and it changed little according to the height of the building. Among the measured pressure differences, the most significant change was at the front door of each household because the front door was the most air-tight of the analyzed components. The pressure difference at the front door on the 4th floor was 10 Pa, and that difference increased toward the upper floors, 46.6 Pa on the 36th floor and 54 Pa on the 42nd floor. The elevator door and stair door showed low differential pressures because they were not air-tight [121]. In addition, it was found that most of the pressure was distributed at the front door of the household, and the neutral zone was formed on the 11th floor, much lower than the 21st floor, which is the middle of the 42nd floor. In this case, when the air-tightness of the upper and lower floors is the same, the neutral zone is theoretically formed in the middle [36], but the phenomenon of the neutral zone lowering occurred because the air-tightness of the front door of household on the upper floors is much more air-tight than the external door on the lower floors [29].

Figure 3-13 Result of the measured pressure difference in the first measurement

Figure 3-14 is the result of measured pressure difference in the second measurement. In the second measurement, the measurement was carried out by selecting when the outside temperature was very low. This is because the outside air temperature was not low in the first measurement, so that a large pressure difference was not formed. In order to predict the air-tightness similar to the measured value, the colder the weather was selected because the larger the interval between

the two differential pressure data sets used, the more reliable air-tightness predicted value could be obtained.

First, in the case of the external door, a pressure difference of about 30 Pa was measured at the 3rd basement level, which is the lowest level, and a differential pressure of about twice as large as the result of the first measurement occurred. A differential pressure of 61.5 Pa was formed on the external door of the rooftop floor, and a differential pressure of about 20 Pa or more was additionally generated compared to the first measurement.

Secondly, in the case of elevator doors, a small pressure of less than 10 Pa was distributed from the 3rd basement level to the 3rd floor above the ground without the front door of household in apartment, and there was almost no pressure difference from the floor with the front door of household in apartment.

The third is the stair door. The stair door did not have much pressure difference in the other floors, but a differential pressure of 51 Pa was formed in the stair door on the top floor. In general, in terms of the stack effect, it may be a problem when it is 25 Pa or more in IBC standard [122] and 50 Pa or more in EN 12101-6 standard [123]. In general, 30 Pa or more in terms of apartment houses is a criterion that can be a problem considering the opening and closing of doors, front door of household, and stair doors, etc. In the case of offices, it is more than 50 Pa, and the elevator door is based on 25 Pa [124]. Therefore, in the viewpoint of the stack effect, a problem occurred that a differential pressure of 51 Pa was formed at the stair door.

Fourth, it is the front door of household. In the first measurement, the most pressure was distributed at the front door of the household because it was the most air-tight. A very large amount of pressure was distributed because the outside temperature was very cold during the second measurement. A differential pressure of 101 Pa occurred at the 42nd floor, which is the uppermost. This is more than double the 50 Pa standards for offices. In fact, at the time of the experiment, an adult man weighing 70 kg could not open the front door of the household in

apartment, and it was difficult to open a sturdy adult man weighing 85 kg or more. In winter, children, the elderly and adult women living on the top floor will not be able to open the door, and many adult men may not be able to open the door.

Lastly, in the case of the building envelope, there was no significant difference from the first measurement, but a pressure difference of 11 Pa was measured in the top layer.

At the time of the first measurement, the difference in pressure difference between the external door and the stair door was about 10 Pa on the rooftop floor, which is the top floor, and similarly, a difference of about 10 Pa occurred during the second measurement. It was determined that the air-tightness of each component was the same as in the first measurement. Therefore, as the indoor and outdoor temperature difference increased, only the size of the differential pressure increased, but the ratio was the same. In addition, the neutral zone was also formed in the 11th floor at the same location in the first measurement. As a result, it was found that as the outside temperature decreased, only the magnitude of the differential pressure increased, but the ratio at which the pressure was distributed to each element was similar. In addition, the direction of airflow across the building was similar to that in the first measurement. However, the pressure difference generated at the front door increased by up to 100 percent compared with the first measurement; the differential pressure was about 101 Pa at the front door on 42nd floor. The differential pressure thus increases as the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increases.

Figure 3-14 Result of the measured pressure difference in the second measurement

D. Air-tightness using blower door test

The air-tightness of the building envelope predicted by the method proposed in this study was compared with the air-tightness determined using the existing blower door test method. The results from the blower door test method are shown in Table 3-8. The air-tightness of the building envelope at 50 Pa on the 4th, 16th, and 42nd floors was 3.13 h⁻¹, 3.11 h⁻¹, and 3.19 h⁻¹, respectively.

The results from the blower door test method did not differ significantly by floor. Additionally, the previously published air-tightness of building envelopes in high-rise residential buildings at 50 Pa is 2.5–3.51 h⁻¹ [102-103] [125], so the air-tightness measured in this study is consistent with those previous results.

Table 3-8 Results of air-tightness measured using the blower door test method

Floor	ACH50 (h ⁻¹)	Air flow coefficient, C (m ³ /h·Pa ⁿ)	Flow exponent, n
42F	3.19	84.24	0.530
16F	3.11	75.82	0.522
4F	3.13	68.63	0.549

3.3.4 Air-tightness prediction using differential pressure

The air-tightness of the building envelope was predicted using the pressure differential measurement results (Table 3-9). For that calculation, the air volume flowing out through the building envelope was calculated. For example, the amount of air passing through the front door under the measured differential pressure condition could be calculated by using the air leakage report on the front door.

The airflow of the building envelope at the 42nd floor was about 195.2 CMH (cubic meter per hour) at 5 Pa and 301.6 CMH at 11 Pa. The C and n values were about 80.3 m³/(h·Paⁿ) and 0.552, respectively. The airflow rate through the building envelope at the 42nd floor can be deduced by equation (55). The air-tightness of the building envelope at the 42nd floor was thus 3.15 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa. The air-tightness of the building envelope at the 36th, 16th, and 4th floors was 3.2 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa, 0.63 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa, and 2.87 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa, respectively.

$$Q = 80.3\Delta P^{0.552} \quad (55)$$

Table 3-9 Air-tightness prediction of the building envelope

Step.	Floor	Front door	Building envelope	Note
Step 2. ΔP measurement	42F	54 Pa	5 Pa	1 st measurement
		101 Pa	11 Pa	2 nd measurement
	36F	38 Pa	3 Pa	1 st measurement
		82 Pa	8 Pa	2 nd measurement
	16F	12 Pa	3 Pa	1 st measurement
		14 Pa	6 Pa	2 nd measurement
	4F	10 Pa	3 Pa	1 st measurement
		23 Pa	6 Pa	2 nd measurement
Step 2. (B-1) Airflow of the building envelope	42F	195.2 CMH		Based on the air leakage report for the front door
		301.6 CMH		
	36F	152.9 CMH		
		260.9 CMH		
	16F	94.3 CMH		
		103.9 CMH		
	4F	60.4 CMH		
		107.8 CMH		
Step 2 (B-2) C, n of the building envelope	42F	n	0.552	n determined using Eq.(7) C determined using Eq.(8)
		C	80.3 m ³ /(h·Pa ⁿ)	
	36F	n	0.545	
		C	84 m ³ /(h·Pa ⁿ)	
	16F	n	0.140	
		C	80.8 m ³ /(h·Pa ⁿ)	
	4F	n	0.835	
		C	24.1 m ³ /(h·Pa ⁿ)	
Step 3. Air-tightness of the building envelope	42F	3.15 h ⁻¹ at 50 Pa		Using Eq.(10)
	36F	3.20 h ⁻¹ at 50 Pa		
	16F	0.63 h ⁻¹ at 50 Pa		
	4F	2.87 h ⁻¹ at 50 Pa		

3.3.5 Comparison of air-tightness determined using the proposed and blower door test methods

Table 3-10 compares the results between the air-tightness of the building envelope determined using the proposed prediction method and the direct measurements. Differences are defined as percentages. On the upper floors (36th and 42nd floors), where the pressure differential is relatively large, the predicted value coincided with the measured value, with a difference of less than 2%. The difference on the 4th floor was about 8%. However, at the 16th floor, adjacent to the neutral zone (12th floor in the target building), where the measured differential pressure was very small, the predicted value deviated widely from the measured value.

Table 3-10 Comparison of measured air-tightness and predicted air-tightness

Floor	Measured air-tightness	Predicted air-tightness	Percentage error* (%)
	ACH50 (h ⁻¹)		
42 nd floor	3.19	3.15	1.3
36 th floor	3.14	3.20	1.9
16 th floor	3.11	0.63	79.7
4 th floor	3.13	2.87	8.31

* Percentage error (%) = (Measured air-tightness – Predicted air-tightness)/Measured air-tightness × 100

3.3.6 Dependence of the predicted air-tightness on factors in the formation of differential pressure

A. Temperature difference

Because the method proposed in this study predicts air-tightness by measuring the differential pressure generated under actual climate conditions, the indoor and outdoor temperature differences and height of the analyzed point relative to the neutral zone, which influence the differential pressure on building components, affect the prediction result [30]. The dependence of the predicted air-tightness results on the indoor and outdoor temperature difference

was analyzed (Figure 3-15).

The indoor and outdoor temperature differences were 25.5 °C, 26.5 °C, and 30 °C. The effect of those temperature differences on the predicted air-tightness was small on the upper floors (36th and 42nd floors) because the differential pressure at those points was significant as a result of the stack effect in high-rise buildings.

Thus, the difference between the predicted and measured values of air-tightness was small. However, on the lower floor (4th floor), the predicted and measured values differed widely depending on the temperature difference. When the temperature difference was 25.5 °C and 26.5 °C, the difference between the predicted and measured results was large, whereas when the temperature difference was 30 °C, the difference was small.

Figure 3-15 Dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the ΔT

B. Height of the analyzed point

As the height difference between the analyzed point and the airflow neutral zone in the target building increases, the differential pressure at the analyzed point increases, which influences the quality of the predicted air-tightness. Figure 3-16 shows how the difference between the predicted

and measured values of air-tightness depends on the height difference between the analysis point and the airflow neutral zone. When the height difference was large (36th and 42nd floors), the predicted and measured values were consistent. On the 4th floor, with a height difference of 21 m, the error between the predicted value and the measured value was large. On the 16th floor, with a height difference of only 15 m, the error was the highest among the analyzed points.

Figure 3-16 Dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the ΔH

C. Pressure difference

The indoor and outdoor temperature difference, the height of the analyzed building, and the distance between the neutral zone and the analysis point of the building greatly affect the formation of differential pressure at the analysis point. Figure 3-17 examines the quality of the predicted air-tightness according to the level of differential pressure. The predicted and measured air-tightness values were almost identical when the differential pressure at the target point was 50 Pa or higher, but significant errors between the two were found when the differential pressure was lower than that.

The air-tightness value predicted through differential pressure measurement under real-

world weather conditions in an actual building using the method proposed in this study was reliable only when the differential pressure was 50 Pa or more.

The pressure difference of building components is affected by the indoor and outdoor temperature difference, building height, and the distance of the analysis point from the neutral zone. Those effects are caused by the stack effect (vertical airflow in high-rise buildings), which causes pressure differences across the building components, and the size of the stack effect is proportionate to the factors listed.

Figure 3-17 Dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the ΔP

3.4 Discussion

This chapter has proposed a new method to predict the air-tightness of high-rise buildings using the differential pressure that occurs under natural climate conditions. The air-tightness of a high-rise residential building was predicted using two differential pressure measurements in actual conditions. The novelty of the study was presented through comparison with the conventional air-tightness measurement method. Also, it was proposed to a new method of the equation and specific processes can be applied in actual buildings. The predicted air-tightness was

compared with measured air-tightness using the blower door test. Finally, the relationship between the predicted air-tightness and the main factor that forms the pressure difference in the building, was analyzed because the method proposed in this study uses the pressure difference that occurs naturally in the actual building. The results of this chapter are as follows.

- 1) It was reviewed to the principle and concept of the conventional air-tightness measurement method. Also, it was identified to the relationship between the differential pressure and the air volume in the principle of the equation applied in the existing air-tightness measurement method. This was used as basic data to propose a new method so that the method proposed in this study can be applied.
- 2) It was explained to the principle and background for predicting the air-tightness by using the pressure difference naturally generated due to the stack effect in the building, and an equation was proposed for the theoretical verification of this. In addition, it was verified through the formula of the existing air-tight performance measurement method that the proposed formula can be logically valid. Finally, a process was established to apply the method proposed in this study to an actual building.
- 3) The difference between the predicted and directly measured air-tightness of the building envelope on the upper floors (36th and 42nd floors), where the differential pressure was relatively large, did not differ significantly. However, the values predicted for the 16th floor near the neutral zone, where the differential pressure was small, differed widely from the measured values. When the differential pressure across a building component formed by the indoor/outdoor temperature difference, the building height, and the distance from the neutral plane of the analyzed building is more than 50 Pa, the air-tightness results predicted using the proposed method in this study were valid.

Comprehensively, if the differential pressure at the point referenced by climatic conditions and building conditions is 50 Pa or more, the air-tightness of a building component can be predicted by measuring only the differential pressure at that building part in normal living conditions. The method proposed in this study can thus predict air-tightness, which is difficult to measure using the blower door test under actual living conditions, using a simple method. Using the proposed simple method to predict air-tightness under actual building conditions will enable further increases in the accuracy of predictions about building energy consumption and indoor air quality.

Chapter 4 Evaluation of the proposed method for air-tightness prediction

The air-tightness prediction method proposed in this study is based on the pressure difference of building components like the blower door test method. However, unlike the blower door test method, this method uses the differential pressure that occurs in real buildings, not the high differential pressure conditions. In a building, pressure or differential pressure is applied to the building components by wind pressure or the internal airflow caused by the stack effect. The magnitude of the pressure difference owing to the stack effect is related to the building height and indoor and outdoor temperature difference.

In the chapter 3, the principle of the proposed method, and the prediction processes of air-tightness were described. Also, the validity of the proposed method was verified by applying it to an actual building. In addition, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the indoor and outdoor temperature and height differences of the building was reviewed. This is because the above two factors cause the pressure difference that occurs in real buildings, and the proposed method is based on the pressure difference. However, in the previous chapter, because the building height and indoor and outdoor temperature differences were significant, a differential pressure was largely formed. Therefore, since it was not applied for a small differential pressure, and it was not applied to many buildings, it was difficult to generalize the proposed method.

The aim of this chapter is to analyze the validity of the proposed method for various outdoor weather conditions and building heights. The analyzed buildings were a low- and mid-rise buildings with a relatively small differential pressure. Similar to the previous chapter, the differential pressures in the analyzed building components were measured and the air-tightness of the building envelope was predicted using the proposed method. The air-tightness on all floors

to predict was measured by the blower door test method to compare the results predicted by the proposed method. In addition, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the indoor and outdoor temperature and height differences of the building was reviewed, and the minimum differential pressure conditions and acceptable conditions that could be predicted the valid air-tightness of the building components by the proposed method were analyzed.

4.1 Proposal of processes for air-tightness prediction method using pressure difference based on various conditions

4.1.1 The factors creating the pressure difference in buildings

The factors creating a differential pressure in buildings are described in detail in Chapter 2 and are briefly summarized as follows. The pressure difference owing to the stack effect [35] can be expressed as a function of the difference in air density between the interior and exterior of the building and the vertical distance from the neutral zone, as shown in Equation (56).

$$\Delta P = g \Delta \rho H \quad (56)$$

where ΔP is the pressure difference inside and outside the building (Pa), g is the gravitational acceleration (m/s^2), $\Delta \rho$ is the air density difference inside and outside the building (kg/m^3), and H is the distance from reference plane (m).

The pressure at a specific height varies independently with the distance from the reference plane. The pressure difference owing to the stack effect at a specific height is the product of the gravitational acceleration and the difference in air density. If the height of the floor of a building is zero, the distance from the neutral zone to a specific point can be expressed using Equation (57) based on the difference between the height of the neutral zone (N) from the reference plane and the height of a specific point (h) from the reference plane. The position of the neutral zone varies depending on the looseness of air through the building envelope in the lower or upper part of the

less than 0.5, the value of n was not limited during the process.

However, unlike in Chapter 3, it was judged here that the value of n should be limited because relatively low- and mid-rise buildings were being targeting rather than high-rise buildings. ASTM E779-19 [126] recommends that, if the flow exponent is greater than 0.5 or less than 1, then the test is invalid and should be repeated. The following should be checked before repeating the test: (1) the equipment for proper calibration, (2) weather conditions against the temperature and pressure used in the calculations, (3) leaks in the connection of the pressurizing fan to the enclosure, (4) the connection between sections of the building, and (5) all windows, doors, and other potential building openings to determine whether they are closed. In this chapter, the value of n was limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1, and if the predicted value of n did not meet this criterion, it was judged to be unreliable and was excluded from the prediction result. All the predicted air-tightness values in this study are valid because the n values meet this criterion. The process described in this chapter is shown in Figure 4-2.

Step 1 describes the conditions evaluated in this chapter. Measurements were carried out under various heights and temperatures, and these measurements were conducted in buildings with three different numbers of floors, such as low- and mid-rise buildings. In addition, for each building, measurements were conducted based on the various number of floors and outdoor temperature conditions. These were used to predict the air-tightness under various differential pressure conditions and to determine the minimum differential pressure to which the method proposed in this paper can be applied.

In Step 2, the differential pressure was measured in the same manner as that of previous studies. C and n were calculated in the same way as in Chapter 3. However, in this chapter, n was limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1, because conventional air-tightness measurement methods recommend a re-measurement if n does not meet this standard even if the predicted air-tightness value is similar to the actual value as this predicted air-tightness value may be unreliable.

Because the purpose of the proposed method is to evaluate the air-tightness of the components of a target building using a simple technique instead of the complex blower door test, it was judged that the conditions for achieving reliable air-tightness measurement results suggested by conventional measurement methods should be satisfied.

Finally, in Step 3, the air-tightness under various conditions was predicted in the same manner as in Chapter 3, and the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the height difference, temperature difference, and differential pressure was examined. Also, the relationship between the height difference, temperature difference, and differential pressure was examined through Pearson's correlation analysis. To generalize the proposed method in this paper, a 95% confidence interval in the pressurization and depressurization results by blower door test was derived. Based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval for each building, the minimum differential pressure condition that could be applied to the proposed method in this study was presented. After conducting each analysis review on the applicable pressure difference, acceptable conditions in which the predicted and measured values were consistent for all buildings were suggested. The acceptable condition is suggested by existing air-tightness measurement standards such as ASTM Standard E779-03 [57], ISO 9972 [61], and EN 13829 [24] as $\Delta H \times \Delta T$. Finally, the predicted results at the derived 95% confidence interval were statistically evaluated using the indicators (NMSE, FB, and FS) suggested in the ASTM Guide D5157-97 [127].

Figure 4-2 Process to generalize the proposed method

4.2 Application of the proposed method based on various conditions

Actual measurements were conducted according to the process suggested in this chapter using the method proposed herein. In this chapter, case studies were conducted under various conditions to ensure that the proposed method was reliable and could be generalized. The proposed method can not only be applied to one case but it can be applied to all residential buildings where a differential pressure occurs. Therefore, case studies were conducted under various differential pressure conditions using different conditions and variables. In the theoretical review (Chapter 2, Section 1), the two main factors that form a differential pressure in high-rise residential buildings, i.e., height and temperature, were described. In this study, measurements were performed on three buildings of different heights. The actual measurements were performed for three completely constructed buildings, and all three buildings used to verify the proposed method were relatively lower in height than those described in Chapter 3. A description of the

buildings examined is presented as follows.

4.2.1 Description of target buildings

A. Low-rise (21F) building

The first building to be evaluated was a low-rise residential building, which had the lowest height among the three. Located in Pyeongtaek, Gyeonggi province, this building had 2 basement levels and 21 stories above the ground. The height of the building was 69.1 m. Other facilities existed in one of the neighboring residential complexes in the district; they were not included in the building that was evaluated.

The 1st and 2nd floor basement levels were used as underground parking lots, and the 1st floor above the ground was the main entrance. There were no residential facilities on these floors. Residential facilities were distributed from 2 floors above the ground to 21 floors above the ground, and unlike the building evaluated in Chapter 3, no evacuation floor was present. The building included 542 apartments with sizes of 64.80 m² (21 apartments), 64.28 m² (46 apartments), 73.55 m² (40 apartments), 73.42 m² (152 apartments), and 84.87 m² (283 apartments). Table 4-1 outlines the first building to be evaluated.

Table 4-1 Details regarding the first building to be evaluated

Building information	Location: Pyeongtaek, Gyeonggi province, South Korea
	Type: Residential building
	Number of floors: 21F above ground and B2F underground
	Height: 69.1 m
	Floor area of each household: 64.80 m ² – 84.87 m ²

B. Mid-rise (27F) building

The second building evaluated was a mid-rise residential building with a height between those of the other two buildings. The building evaluated was a residential building with two

basement levels and 27 stories above the ground; it was located in the same place as the first building. The height of the building was 86.2 m. In addition, no amenities were present in the building. Other facilities existed in one of the neighboring residential complexes in the district; they were not included in the building that was evaluated.

The basement floor in this building was also used as an underground parking lot, similar to the first building. The ground floor was also used for the same purpose as in the first building. Residential facilities were distributed from 2 floors above the ground to 27 floors above the ground, and there was no evacuation floor. The building consisted of a total of 542 apartments, similar to the first building evaluated; the number and sizes of the apartments were also the same. A description of the second building is presented in Table 4-2.

Table 4-2 Details regarding the second building to be evaluated

Building information	Location: Pyeongtaek, Gyeonggi province, South Korea
	Type: Residential building
	Number of floors: 27F above ground and B2F underground
	Height: 86.2 m
	Floor area of each household: 64.80 m ² – 84.87 m ²

C. Mid-rise (33F) building

The third building evaluated had the highest floor height among the three buildings; however, it was considered a mid-rise residential building that was relatively lower compared to the building assessed in Chapter 3.

The evaluated building was a residential building with two basement levels and 33 stories above the ground; it was located in Dongtan, Gyeonggi province, and the height of the building was 94.1 m. As with the other two buildings to be evaluated, there were no shopping centers, convenience facilities, or evacuation floors in this building. Other facilities existed in one of the neighboring residential complexes in the district; they were not included in the building that was

evaluated.

The 1st and 2nd basement floors were used as underground parking lots, similar to the other two target buildings. However, unlike the other two buildings, the third building to be evaluated had residential facilities on the 1st floor. Residential facilities were distributed from 1 floor above the ground to 33 floors above the ground.

The complex included 1479 apartments in 16 buildings, and the sizes of the apartments were as follows: are 61.92 m² (150 apartments), 74.95 m² (73 apartments), 74.97 m² (144 apartments), 74.89 m² (71 apartments), and 84.84 m² (1041 apartments). A description of the third building is presented in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3 Details regarding the third building to be evaluated

Building information	Location: Dongtan, Gyeonggi province, South Korea
	Type: Residential building
	Number of floors: 33F above ground and B2F underground
	Height: 94.1 m
	Floor area of each household: 61.92 m ² – 84.88 m ²

4.2.2 Description of field measurements

A. Measurement period and location

Although the buildings to be assessed were low- and mid-rise residential buildings, they were relatively small in height compared to the high-rise building covered in Chapter 3 and larger than a typical villa or residential complex. In addition, the stack effect in these buildings is smaller than that in a high-rise building and cannot be avoided. As in Chapter 3, because the method proposed here involves predicting the air-tightness by using the differential pressure naturally generated owing to the stack effect, the airflow throughout the building was identified.

The shape was the same for all the buildings. As for the vertical airflow path of the buildings, there were two main airflow paths from the 2nd floor basement to the rooftop as well as the elevator

shaft and stairs. There are two apartments in the horizontal airflow path based on the elevator and stairwell corridors, and there is a fixed window in the corridor that is in contact with the outside air. Air from the entrance on the basement floor and the main entrance door on the 1st floor moves vertically through the stairwell and elevator shaft and flows into the front door of each household through the corridor. At levels above the neutral zone, air flows into the outside through the building envelope, and on the floors below the neutral zone, air flows into households through the exterior of the building, moving to the corridor through the front door of the household.

To understand the airflow and pressure distribution in the building, measurements were performed at dawn to minimize the influence of wind, elevator, and ventilation systems, similar to the process described in Chapter 3. The actual measurements were carried out during a no-operation state. In addition, the temperature difference, the second factor that could affect the differential pressure in the building, was considered.

(1) Low- (21F) and mid-rise (27F) buildings

Because the 21F low-rise and the 27F mid-rise buildings were located at the same place, measurements were conducted at the same time. For both the sites, the indoor temperature was set to 10 °C, which is the minimum temperature required for protection against freezing. This was done in order to vary the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures. In addition, a large number of measurements were performed under various outside temperature conditions. Measurements were conducted on days when the outside air temperature was low, e.g., -7.3 °C, -6.8 °C, -2.3 °C, -2.2 °C, -1.9 °C, -1.4 °C, -0.9 °C, -0.4 °C, and -0.3 °C. Measurements were carried out under different ambient temperature conditions. The measurement equipment was the same as that used in Chapter 3.

Furthermore, the horizontal measurement position was the same as that in Chapter 3, where the air vertically elevated through the elevator shaft and stairwell from the upper part of the neutral

zone flows out through the building envelope via the entrance of the household or partially through the fixed window of the corridor. In the lower part of the neutral zone, outside air flows in through the building envelope and the fixed window of the corridor; it then moves to the elevator shaft and stairwell through the corridor via the household's entrance door and rises vertically. Taking this into account, the horizontal differential pressure measurements were conducted at the elevator shaft, stairwell door, front door of the household, and the building envelope. Vertical measurements were conducted in the basement floor and at the lobby of the 1st floor, where there was a high amount of air inflow. Because the proposed method uses the differential pressure in the building, the effect of measuring the height, which is one of the factors affecting the formation of the differential pressure, was evaluated for different floors. For the 27F mid-rise building, measurements were performed for a total of nine floors, i.e., 27th, 24th, 21st, 17th, 14th, 11th, 8th, 5th, and 2nd floors. In addition, for the 21F low-rise building, measurements were performed for a total of seven floors, i.e., 21st, 17th, 14th, 11th, 8th, 5th, and 2nd floors. Figure 4-3 shows the horizontal and vertical measurement positions of the 21F low-rise building, and Figure 4-4 shows the horizontal and vertical measurement locations of the 27F mid-rise building.

Figure 4-3 Horizontal and vertical measurement positions of the 21F building

Figure 4-4 Horizontal and vertical measurement positions of the 27F building

(2) Mid-rise (33F) building

Unlike the other two buildings, in the 33F mid-rise building, the indoor temperature was set to 24 °C, which is the temperature set by heating systems in winter. This was used include varying indoor and outdoor temperature differences by ensuring that the temperature difference between indoor and outdoor conditions was different from that of the other two buildings. In addition, the measurements were conducted under various outside temperatures, similar to the other two buildings. Measurements were conducted on days when the outside air temperature was low, e.g., at -5.4 °C, -4.4 °C, -3.6 °C, -3.1 °C, -2.4 °C, -1.6 °C, and 0.5 °C. Measurements were carried out under different ambient temperature conditions. The equipment used for the survey was the same as that used in the other two buildings. The horizontal measurements were also performed in the elevator shaft, stairwell, front door of the household, and building envelope because the airflow path was the same as that in the other two buildings. Vertical measurements were also conducted in the basement floor and at the lobby of the 1st floor, where there was a high amount of air inflow. Similar to the other two buildings, measurements were performed on different floors. In the case of the 33F mid-rise building, measurements were performed on a total of 14 floors, i.e., 33rd, 32nd, 31st, 30th, 27th, 24th, 21st, 17th, 14th, 11th, 8th, 5th, 2nd, and 1st floors. Unlike the other two buildings, this building had residential facilities on the 1st floor, and thus, measurements were not only performed at the main entrance door of the lobby of the 1st floor, but they were also performed at the front door of the household and the building envelope. Figure 4-5 shows the horizontal and vertical measurement positions of the 33F mid-rise building.

Figure 4-5 Horizontal and vertical measurement position of 33F building

B. Measurement of external weather, temperature and humidity

The measurements were conducted in the same way as that described in Chapter 3. A weather station was installed on the rooftop using the same equipment. The temperature- and humidity-measuring device described in Chapter 3 was installed at the measurement location. Figure 4-6 shows measurements being performed and installation of measuring devices in the low- and medium-rise buildings

(a) Hallway

(b) Parking lot

(c) Stair

(d) Household in apartment

(e) Weather station

Figure 4-6 Installation of measurement equipment in the 21F and 27F buildings

C. Pressure difference measurements

Differential pressure measurements were also performed using the same method as that described in Chapter 3. Because the differential pressure of the building envelope needs to be measured inside and outside the household, an iron rod was installed to minimize the effect of the hose. The hose was placed inside the iron rod to enable exposure to the outside. The position of the iron rod was adjusted considering the wind direction to minimize the effect of wind pressure. The measurement process is shown in Figure 4-7.

(a) Preparation for measurement

(b) Measurement

Figure 4-7 Measurements performed for building envelope

D. Air-tightness measurements

Air-tightness measurements were also conducted in the same way as the method described in Chapter 3. Before these measurements were performed, a survey was conducted after the bathrooms, kitchens, and households were made air-tight. The air-tightness measurements aimed to determine the air-tightness of the building envelope. In this chapter, the air-tightness of the front door was measured and the difference in the air-tightness of the building envelope was examined. Because the element of the building in which the greatest differential pressure is distributed is the front door of a household, the air-tightness of this element was determined. The

first method that can be used to measure the air-tightness of the front door of a household involves blocking all spaces except for this front door. Because many spaces such as the door to each room, the boiler room, kitchen hood, and building envelope were blocked, significant time and effort were involved. A fan was installed at the door of the room closest to the front door, and the room was depressurized and pressurized such that air could flow in/out only through the front door of the household. In particular, when measuring the air-tightness of the front door of a household, the measurement fails in many cases, and because significant effort and time are required, there is very little existing research on actual measurements. The second method involves installing a fan in the middle door of the front door. However, in the case of the above method, because the distance between the middle door and the front door of the household is short, the possibility of a failed measurement is high. However, this is the simplest method as there is no need to make the area air-tight. Figure 4-8 presents the methods used for performing measurements at the front door of a household. Figure 4-9 indicates the air-tight status for this first method. The air-tightness at the front door was measured in three households of the 33F mid-rise building.

(a) First method

(b) Second method

Figure 4-8 Methods used to perform measurements at the front door of a household

Figure 4-9 Air-tight status when the first method is used to perform measurements at the front door of a household

4.2.3 Results of the external weather conditions, temperature, and humidity

A. External weather conditions

(1) Low- (21F) and mid-rise (27F) buildings

A weather station was installed on the roof of the 27F mid-rise building because it was judged that there would be no significant change in the external weather environment. This is because the 21F low-rise building and the 27F mid-rise building were located within the same complex.

A total of nine measurements were performed. The following describes the first set of weather measurement results obtained. Figure 4-10 shows the external temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise and the 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 1:00 am and 2:30 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-6.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 54.0%. The main wind direction was northeast-east, and the average wind speed was 0.55 m/s, which was relatively low.

Figure 4-10 First set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-11 shows the second set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 3:00 am and 4:30 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was -7.3 °C, and the average outdoor humidity was 56.3%. The main wind direction was southeast-east, and the average wind speed was 0.69 m/s, which was relatively low.

Figure 4-11 Second set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-12 shows the third set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 10:00 pm and 11:10 pm when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-0.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 27.7%. The main wind direction was north, and the average wind speed was 0.64 m/s, which was relatively low.

Figure 4-12 Third set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-13 shows the fourth set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 11:30 pm and 12:30 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-1.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 33.3%. The main wind direction was northeast-east, and the average wind speed was 0.89 m/s, which was slightly higher than that on other days, but it was not sufficiently strong to affect the building envelope.

Figure 4-13 Fourth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-14 shows the fifth set of external temperature and humidity distributions for the cases of the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 4:00 am and 5:00 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-2.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 39.9%. The main wind direction was northeast east, and the average wind speed was 0.75 m/s, which was relatively low.

Figure 4-14 Fifth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-15 shows the sixth set of temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 5:00 am and 6:00 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was -2.2 °C, and the average outdoor humidity was 38.4%. The main wind direction was northeast, and the average wind speed was 0.08 m/s, which was extremely low.

Figure 4-15 Sixth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-16 shows the seventh set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 8:00 pm and 9:00 pm when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was -0.3 °C, and the average outdoor humidity was 78.6%. The main wind direction was northeast, and the average wind speed was 0.06 m/s, which was extremely low with almost no wind blowing.

Figure 4-16 Seventh set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-17 shows the eighth set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 11:30 pm and 12:30 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-0.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 79.7%. The main wind direction was south-southwest, and the average wind speed was 0.42 m/s, which was relatively low.

Figure 4-17 Eighth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

Figure 4-18 shows the ninth set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured for the cases of the 21F low-rise and 27F mid-rise buildings. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 1:00 am and 2:00 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-1.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 72.7%. The main wind direction was northeast, and the average wind speed was 0.71 m/s, which, although slightly high, was insufficient to affect the building envelope.

Figure 4-18 Ninth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 21F and 27F buildings

(2) Mid-rise (33F) building

A weather station was installed on the roof of the 33F mid-rise building, and a total of seven measurements were conducted.

Figure 4-19 shows the first set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 2:00 am and 3:00 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-4.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 30.4%. The main wind direction was northwest, and the average wind speed was 0.83 m/s, indicating that it was somewhat windy. However, this wind speed was not high enough to affect the building envelope.

Figure 4-19 First set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

Figure 4-20 shows the second set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 4:30 am and 5:30 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-5.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 35.2%. The main wind direction was north-northeast, and the average wind speed was 0.22 m/s, which was extremely low.

Figure 4-20 Second set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

Figure 4-21 shows the third set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 8:00 pm and 9:00 pm when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was 0.5 °C, and the average outdoor humidity was 22.9%. These measurements were conducted on days when the average outdoor temperature was not low in order to create variation in the outdoor temperature conditions.

The main wind direction was north, and the average wind speed was 1.21 m/s, which was not very high; however, it was relatively strong compared to other measurement days. The differential pressure distribution in a building is mainly measured at dawn. This is because the wind speed is extremely weak at dawn; thus, the influence of wind pressure on the building can be minimized.

Figure 4-21 Third set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

Figure 4-22 shows the fourth set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 1:35 am and 2:35 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-1.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 33.8%. The outdoor temperature gradually decreased as time passed, and the humidity increased accordingly. The main wind direction was northeast-east, and the average wind speed was 0.26 m/s, which was extremely low.

Figure 4-22 Fourth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

Figure 4-23 shows the fifth set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 2:40 am and 3:40 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-2.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 40.5%. As time passed, the outdoor temperature gradually decreased, and most of the relative humidity decreased. The main wind direction was northwest, and the average wind speed was 0.49 m/s, which was low.

Figure 4-23 Fifth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

Figure 4-24 shows the sixth set of external temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 4:00 am and 5:00 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-3.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 25.0%. As time passed, the outdoor temperature gradually decreased, and the relative humidity increased. The main wind direction was west-west, and the average wind speed was 0.27 m/s, which was extremely low.

Figure 4-24 Sixth set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

Figure 4-25 shows the seventh set of temperature and humidity distributions measured in the 33F mid-rise building. The temperature and humidity distribution results were obtained between 4:50 am and 5:50 am when the differential pressure was measured. The average outdoor temperature was $-3.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the average outdoor humidity was 29.5%. The distributions of outdoor temperature and humidity over time were the same as those of the sixth measurement. The main wind direction was west-west, and the average wind speed was 0.33 m/s, which was extremely low.

Figure 4-25 Seventh set of outdoor temperature and humidity measurement results for the 33F building

B. Temperature and humidity

(1) Low-rise (21F) building

The measurement results for the household, hall, and stairwell in the 21F low-rise building are shown in Table 4-4. The results indicate the average values of the temperature and humidity measured when measuring the differential pressure. In the case of the household results, because the minimum heating temperature for protection against freezing was set to 10 °C, a temperature distribution between 8.5 °C and 11.3 °C was observed. The temperature of the hall ranged from 2.3 °C to 4.4 °C and that of the stairwell ranged from 1.1 °C to 2.8 °C. A higher temperature distribution was observed from the lower to the upper floors. Under all measurement conditions described below, because minimal heating to prevent freezing was always applied in households, a similar temperature distribution was observed, and in the cases of the halls and stairwells, higher temperature distributions were formed from lower to upper floors.

Table 4-4 Results of temperature and humidity in the 21F building

Conditions: -0.3 °C to -7.3 °C						
Floor	Household		Hall		Stairwell	
	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)
21F	9.0 to 10.3	45.9 to 53.7	3.3 to 4.4	48.1 to 59.6	2.3 to 2.8	56.4 to 63.7
17F	8.5 to 10.2	45.0 to 52.8	3.2 to 3.5	45.6 to 61.2	1.6 to 2.2	57.7 to 64.7
14F	8.7 to 10.2	43.4 to 50.7	2.9 to 3.2	43.0 to 62.5	1.6 to 2.0	56.2 to 66.3
11F	9.3 to 10.8	43.0 to 48.5	2.8 to 3.2	43.5 to 62.3	1.5 to 2.0	56.2 to 64.8
8F	9.9 to 10.8	48.0 to 52.0	2.9 to 3.2	43.0 to 62.5	1.5 to 1.8	53.8 to 66.8
5F	9.6 to 11.3	42.6 to 52.0	2.5 to 3.0	44.2 to 64.2	1.3 to 1.6	51.0 to 67.9
2F	9.9 to 10.6	52.6 to 54.3	2.3 to 2.6	45.7 to 65.2	1.1 to 1.3	48.6 to 67.0

* Range of values at various temperatures

* The value is average value measured during differential pressure measurement at various temperatures

(2) Mid-rise (27F) building

The 27F mid-rise building also has the same outside temperature conditions as the first building. The measurement results for the household, hall, and stairwell are shown in Table 4-5. The results indicate the average values of the temperature and humidity measured while measuring the differential pressure.

In the same way as the 21F low-rise building, the indoor household temperature was set to 10 °C, which is the minimum heating temperature to prevent freezing. Thus, a temperature distribution between 9.0 °C and 11.3 °C was observed in the household. Although this differs depending on the heating conditions for each household, the highest temperature distribution was observed on the top floor. Additionally, the humidity in this floor was the lowest.

In the case of the hall and stairwell, similar to the 21F building, a higher temperature distribution occurs from lower to upper floors. In particular, the 27F mid-rise building has a relatively large temperature stratification because the height of the building is greater than that of the 21F low-rise building. A temperature distribution between 2.0 °C and 3.6 °C was observed in the hall and that between 0.7 °C and 3.0 °C was observed in the stairwell.

Table 4-5 Results of temperature and humidity in the 27F building

Floor	Conditions: -0.3 °C to -7.3 °C					
	Household		Hall		Stairwell	
	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)
27F	10.5 to 11.3	41.0 to 45.0	3.4 to 3.6	43.8 to 55.5	2.7 to 3.0	40.5 to 56.8
24F	9.3 to 10.2	53.0 to 55.1	2.9 to 3.3	42.8 to 55.8	2.0 to 2.4	42.7 to 57.9
21F	9.2 to 9.8	55.0 to 57.7	2.6 to 3.0	41.5 to 56.7	1.8 to 2.2	42.7 to 56.6
17F	9.1 to 10.3	53.0 to 54.0	2.5 to 2.8	41.7 to 57.5	1.4 to 1.8	43.8 to 59.0
14F	9.4 to 10.2	47.5 to 54.0	2.3 to 2.6	41.9 to 58.9	1.3 to 1.6	44.6 to 58.4
11F	9.3 to 10.1	50.8 to 54.0	2.4 to 2.6	42.5 to 59.1	1.1 to 1.5	44.9 to 59.3
8F	9.6 to 11.3	21.0 to 37.0	2.2 to 2.6	41.8 to 59.7	1.2 to 1.4	45.4 to 58.9
5F	9.0 to 10.1	53.7 to 57.0	2.1 to 2.5	41.2 to 60.2	0.9 to 1.4	46.2 to 59.5
2F	9.8 to 10.9	52.0 to 59.0	2.0 to 2.5	40.8 to 60.7	0.7 to 1.1	48.6 to 60.6

* Range of values at various temperatures

* Average value measured during differential pressure measurement at various temperatures

(3) Mid-rise (33F) building

The 33F mid-rise building was evaluated under outdoor temperature conditions different to those of the previous buildings. A total of seven outside temperature measurements were obtained, i.e., $-5.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-4.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-3.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-3.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-1.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The temperature in the interior of the household was set to $24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is a typical heating temperature set during the winter, rather than minimum heating temperature used to prevent freezing. The aim of this case was to examine the dependence of the predicted air-tightness, reviewed in this chapter, on the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures.

The measurement results for the household, hall, and stairwell are shown in Table 4-6. The results indicate the average values of the temperature and humidity measured when measuring the differential pressure as in the previous buildings. As described above, because the temperature in the 33F mid-rise building was set to $24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is a winter heating condition, a temperature distribution of $23.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $24.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was observed inside the household.

In the case of the halls and stairwells, as in the previous buildings, a higher temperature distribution was observed from the lower to the higher floors. In particular, the 33F mid-rise building was relatively higher than the 27F mid-rise building; thus, temperature stratification was more evident. The range of temperature in the hall of the 1st floor was $4.5\text{--}5.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and that in the hall of the 33rd floor (i.e., the top floor) was $9.2\text{--}9.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, indicating a difference in temperature of $3.6\text{--}4.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at that height. The temperature distribution in the halls in the building was $4.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $9.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Temperature stratification could also be observed in the stairwell according to the height of the hall; the range of temperature was $4.0\text{--}5.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on the 1st floor and $8.5\text{--}9.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on the 33rd floor (i.e., the top floor), indicating a difference in temperature of $3.8\text{--}4.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Temperature stratification largely appeared along the hall. The temperature distribution in the stairwells in the building was $4.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $9.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Under all external temperature conditions, the temperature in the interior of the household

was approximately 24 °C owing to the heating conditions, and temperature stratification was largely visible in both the hall and stairwell. The same phenomenon occurred under all outdoor temperature conditions, and only the results of the temperature distribution inside the household, hall, and stairwell under all outdoor temperature conditions are presented below.

Table 4-6 Results of temperature and humidity in the 33F building

Conditions: 0.5 °C to -5.4 °C						
Floor	Household		Hall		Stairwell	
	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)	Temp.*(°C)	Humi.*(%)
33F	23.5 to 24.8	44.0 to 46.4	9.2 to 9.5	47.0 to 48.9	8.5 to 9.2	46.9 to 49.7
32F	23.6 to 23.8	44.0 to 45.6	8.7 to 9.3	47.1 to 49.7	8.2 to 8.7	47.5 to 50.1
31F	23.5 to 24.3	44.7 to 47.1	8.7 to 9.2	47.6 to 49.4	8.1 to 8.6	48.1 to 49.8
30F	23.4 to 23.8	44.0 to 45.4	8.1 to 9.2	48.4 to 50.2	7.6 to 8.9	48.5 to 50.3
27F	23.5 to 24.7	44.1 to 47.1	7.7 to 8.7	48.3 to 50.5	7.5 to 8.0	48.7 to 50.5
24F	23.3 to 24.7	44.6 to 47.8	7.6 to 8.3	48.6 to 50.8	7.0 to 7.6	49.0 to 50.8
21F	23.3 to 24.1	44.0 to 47.8	6.9 to 7.7	48.8 to 51.7	6.4 to 7.4	49.2 to 50.9
17F	23.7 to 24.3	44.0 to 47.1	6.9 to 7.2	49.4 to 51.5	6.4 to 6.8	49.8 to 51.3
14F	23.4 to 23.9	44.6 to 47.8	6.1 to 7.1	49.7 to 51.4	5.5 to 6.6	50.2 to 51.2
11F	23.7 to 24.2	44.1 to 49.4	5.7 to 6.8	49.2 to 51.2	5.1 to 6.2	49.8 to 52.0
8F	23.5 to 24.7	44.1 to 49.5	5.7 to 6.5	49.4 to 51.2	5.2 to 6.3	49.8 to 51.7
5F	23.3 to 24.3	44.0 to 47.8	5.1 to 6.3	49.4 to 51.4	4.5 to 5.7	50.6 to 51.9
2F	23.6 to 24.3	44.0 to 49.4	5.0 to 6.1	49.8 to 51.5	4.2 to 5.6	50.9 to 52.0
1F	23.5 to 24.3	45.1 to 49.5	4.5 to 5.9	50.2 to 52.0	4.0 to 5.4	51.1 to 52.5

* Range of values at various temperatures

* Average value measured during differential pressure measurement at various temperatures

4.2.4 Results of pressure difference measurements

The differential pressure was measured by considering the stack effect. The horizontal measurement locations included the elevator shaft, stairwell door, front door of the household, and building envelope. The vertical measurement locations included the basement floor, lobby, and household. In the case of the elevator shaft and stair door, the measured differential pressure was mostly 0 to 1 Pa on all floors. In the case of the basement entrance and lobby entrance doors, a differential pressure of approximately 10 to 17 Pa was generated in the windshield of the basement floor according to the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures. A differential pressure of approximately 6 to 12 Pa was formed in the windbreak room at the entrance of the lobby. This forms the principle behind a method of reducing the stack effect by distributing the pressure formed at the entrance door owing to the additional division of a windbreak room [128].

As described in Chapter 3, the differential pressure was measured for the horizontal and vertical airflow paths, and most of the pressure was distributed toward the front door of the household. This is because the front door of the household is the most air-tight. In particular, to apply the method proposed in this paper, it is important to measure the differential pressure at the front door of the household and at the building envelope. This is because the proposed method uses the differential pressure owing to the stack effect in the building and does not use the differential pressure of all components in the building. Among the various components in the building, places that can be considered the most important in terms of energy consumption and indoor air quality are apartments. The only factors necessary to predict the air-tightness of a household are the pressure differences at the front door of the household and at the building envelope. Thus, the pressure difference at the front door of a household and at the building envelope is analyzed in detail in this part of the chapter.

A. Low-rise (21F) building

In the 21F low-rise building, measurements were performed at the front door of a household and the building envelope of the main airflow path for each floor under nine different outdoor temperature conditions, i.e., $-7.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-6.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-1.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-1.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-0.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-0.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $-0.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The indoor temperature was $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

First, the differential pressure measured at the front door of a household in order to predict the air-tightness of the 21F low-rise building is shown in Figure 4-26. A neutral zone in which the inflow and outflow of air are changed was formed near the 5th floor. The differential pressure was positive at the 5th floor and below, and a negative differential pressure occurred beyond the 5th floor. This means that in the floors below the neutral zone, outside air flows into a room, and this air then flows into the elevator shaft or stairwell, rises vertically, and flows out from the room above the neutral zone to the outside.

The differential pressure at the front door of the household on the 21st floor, i.e., the top floor, on the day when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at $17.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was 21 Pa . A differential pressure of 19 Pa was formed even on the day when the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures was $16.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a differential pressure of 12 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was $12.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $12.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. A differential pressure of 10 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was $11.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $11.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a differential pressure of 9 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was $10.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In addition, a differential pressure of 4 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the smallest, i.e., $10.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $10.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Therefore, the differential pressure was observed to gradually decrease as difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures decreased.

The differential pressure at the front door of the household on the 2nd floor, i.e., the lowest

floor, was 5 Pa on the day when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at 17.3 °C. The differential pressure was 3 Pa on the day when the temperature difference was 16.8 °C. However, under all conditions in which the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures was less than 12.3 °C, the differential pressure took a value between 0 and 1 Pa. This is because the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was small; thus, a differential pressure did not properly form.

The differential pressure at the front door of the household on the 17th, 14th, 11th, 8th, and 5th floors showed a gradual decrease as the number of floors decreased. This is because the smaller the difference in height, the smaller is the differential pressure generated owing to the stack effect. A differential pressure of 16 Pa was formed on the 17th floor on the day when the difference in the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the largest at 17.3 °C, and a differential pressure of 4 Pa was formed on the day when the difference in the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the smallest at 10.3 °C. The differential pressure was 3–11 Pa on the 14th floor, 3–7 Pa on the 11th floor, 3–4 Pa on the 8th floor, and 0–2 Pa on the 5th floor depending on the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures.

Second, the differential pressure measured at the building envelope in order to predict the air-tightness of the 21F low-rise building is shown in Figure 4-27. In the case of the building envelope, when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 17.3 °C, the pressure difference was 5 Pa on the 21st floor, 3 Pa on the 17th floor, 2 Pa on the 14th floor, 1 Pa on the 11th, 8th, and 5th floors, and 3 Pa on the 2nd floor. On days when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 16.8 °C, the pressure difference was 4 Pa on the 21st floor, 3 Pa on the 17th floor, 2 Pa on the 14th and 11th floors, 1 Pa on the 11th, 8th, and 5th floors, and 2 Pa on the 2nd floor. On days with other differences in the indoor and outdoor temperatures, excluding those presented above, a differential pressure of 0–2 Pa was formed on all floors. This is because the front door of the household is relatively more air-tight than the building envelope. Therefore,

a high pressure was distributed to the relatively air-tight front door of the household, and a small pressure was distributed to the relatively less air-tight building envelope. Figure 4-28 shows the results of the differential pressure of the building envelope in the 21F low-rise building

Figure 4-26 Results of measured pressure difference at the front door of household in the 21F building

B. Mid-rise (27F) building

Second, in the 27F mid-rise building, the differential pressure was measured under the same outdoor temperature conditions as in the 21F low-rise building. In the 27F mid-rise building, measurements were performed at the front door of the household and the building envelope of the main airflow path on each floor under nine different outdoor temperature conditions of $-7.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-6.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-1.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-1.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-0.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-0.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $-0.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The indoor temperature was $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 4-27 Results of measured pressure difference at the building envelope in the 21F building

Figure 4-28 shows the measured results of the differential pressure at the front door of a household, which were used to predict the air-tightness of the 27F mid-rise building. The neutral zone was approximately at the 8th floor, and the differential pressure at the front door of the household on the 2nd floor was 0–2 Pa for all differences in indoor and outdoor temperatures considered including when the difference between the indoor and outdoor was the largest at 17.3 °C and the smallest at 10.3 °C. It was judged that the differential pressure did not properly form because the indoor and outdoor temperature difference was small owing to the lack of indoor heating. However, on the 11th floor above the neutral zone, a differential pressure of 12 Pa was formed on the day when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at 17.3 °C; a pressure of 15 Pa was formed on the 14th floor, 20 Pa on the 17th floor, 24

Pa on the 21st floor, and 26 Pa on the 24th floor. In the case of the 27th floor in the uppermost layer, a differential pressure of 34 Pa was formed, and this differential pressure gradually increased as the number of layers increased. On the day when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the smallest at approximately 10.3 °C, a differential pressure of 2 Pa was formed on the 11th floor above the neutral zone; a pressure of 5 Pa was formed on the 14th floor, 4 Pa on the 17th and 21st floors, 5 Pa on the 24th floor, and 7 Pa on the top floor, i.e., the 27th floor. In the 11th to 27th floors above the neutral zone, the greater the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures, the greater the differential pressure that was formed. In particular, when the difference in the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the largest at 17.3 °C and second-largest at 16.8 °C, a greater differential pressure was formed than under any other indoor/ outdoor temperature difference conditions.

Figure 4-28 Results of measured pressure difference at the front door of a household in the 27F building

The differential pressure of the building envelope was 6 Pa on the 27th floor, 3 Pa on the 24th and 21st floors, 2 Pa on the 17th floor, 1 Pa on the 14th floor, 2 Pa on the 11th floor, 1 Pa on the 8th floor, and 2 Pa on the 5th and 2nd floors, which is the lowest floor, on the day when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 17.3 °C. There were no significant differences from the results of the 21F low-rise building. On the day when the temperature difference between the indoor and outdoor was 16.8 °C, the differential pressure was 4 Pa on the 27th floor, 5 Pa on the 24th floor, 2 Pa on the 21st and 17th floors, and 1 Pa on all floors from the 14th to the 2nd floor. In addition, under all other indoor and outdoor temperature differences, a differential pressure of 0–2 Pa was formed on all floors, similar to the 21F low-rise building. As with the 21F low-rise building, the building envelope is relatively less air-tight than the front door of the household, and thus, the differential pressure on the building envelope formed because more pressure than that on the front door of the household could not be distributed. Figure 4-29 shows the results of the measured differential pressure of the building envelope for the 27F building.

C. Mid-rise (33F) building

Finally, measurements for the 33F mid-rise building were conducted under different outdoor temperature conditions than those of the previous buildings. The differential pressure at the front door of the household and the building envelope for each floor was measured for a total of seven different outdoor temperature conditions, i.e., -5.4 °C, -4.4 °C, -3.6 °C, -3.1 °C, -2.4 °C, -1.6 °C, and 0.5 °C. Unlike in the previous buildings, the indoor temperature was set to 24 °C.

Figure 4-29 Results of measured pressure difference at the building envelope in the 27F building

Figure 4-30 shows the measured results of the differential pressure at the front door of a household, which were used to predict the air-tightness of the 33F mid-rise building. A neutral zone was formed on the 8th floor, similar to the 27F mid-rise building. In the case of the 1st floor, a differential pressure of 11 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at 29.4 °C, and a pressure of 8 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 28.4 °C, 27.6 °C, and 27.1 °C. When the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 26.4 °C, a differential pressure of 6 Pa was formed, and when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the smallest at 25.6 °C and 24.5 °C, a differential pressure of 4 Pa was formed. Although the outside air temperature was not as low compared to that in the other two buildings, it was judged that a

high differential pressure could be formed because the difference in the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased owing to indoor heating to 24 °C. The differential pressure in the 1st, 2nd, and 5th floors based on the 8th floor, which is the neutral zone, was positive, and the differential pressure gradually increased from the 8th floor to the 1st floor. In addition, the differential pressure from the 11th to the 33rd floor was negative based on the 8th floor, and its value increased as the number of floors increased. In the case of the top floor, i.e., the 33rd floor, a differential pressure of 32 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at 29.4 °C. A differential pressure of 26 Pa occurred when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 28.4 °C; similarly pressures of 24 Pa at a difference of 27.6 °C, 21 Pa at a difference of 27.1 °C, 20 Pa at a difference of 26.4 °C, 18 Pa at a difference of 25.6 °C, and 12 Pa at a difference of 24.5 °C. In the case of the 33rd floor, i.e., the uppermost layer, the differential pressure differed according to each outdoor temperature condition, and the greater the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures, the greater was the differential pressure that formed.

Figure 4-31 shows the measured results of the differential pressure at the building envelope, which were used to predict the air-tightness of the 33F mid-rise building. In the case of the 1st floor, a differential pressure of 4 Pa was formed on the building envelope when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at 29.4 °C, and a pressure of 3 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 28.4 °C, 27.6 °C, and 27.1 °C. When the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 26.4 °C, 25.6 °C, and 24.5 °C, a differential pressure of 2 Pa was formed.

In the case of the 33rd floor, i.e., the uppermost layer, a differential pressure of 5 Pa was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the greatest at 29.4 °C, and a 4 Pa differential pressure was formed when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 28.4 °C and 27.6 °C. The difference in pressure was 3 Pa at 27.1 °C,

26.4 °C, and 25.6 °C. In addition, a differential pressure of 2 Pa was formed when the difference in the indoor and outdoor temperatures was the smallest at 24.5 °C. Although slight differences occurred depending on the floor and outside temperature, most differential pressures took a value of 0–2 Pa, which is similar to the results of the previous two buildings. The differential pressure in the building varies according to the air-tightness, and the greater the air-tightness, the more pressure is distributed. Therefore, it is expected that the results of measuring the differential pressure of the building envelope will be similar in most buildings.

Figure 4-30 Results of measured pressure difference at the front door of a household in the 33F building

Figure 4-31 Results of measured pressure difference at the building envelope in the 33F building

4.2.5 Results of the air-tightness measurement using blower door test

In this study, in order to verify the air-tightness predicted using the proposed method, the air-tightness of the building envelope was measured using the blower door test at the same place where the differential pressure was measured. In addition, the air-tightness of the front door of the household was measured to compare it with that of the building envelope. Figure 4-32 shows the distribution of the air-tightness measurement results of the building envelope and the front door for each building. The level of air-tightness at the depressurization was the most air-tight in the 33F building, followed by the 21F building and 27F building. The level of air-tightness at the pressurization was the most air-tight in the 21F building, followed by the 33F building and 27F building. The level of the average air-tightness was the most air-tight in the 33F building, followed

by the 21F building and 27F building. In all measurements such as depressurization, pressurization, the deviation of the air-tightness level was the largest in the 27F building, followed by 33F building and 21F building. In addition, when comparing the air-tightness level of the building envelope and the front door in the 33F building, the air-tightness of the front door was approximately 3.2 times more air-tight.

Figure 4-32 Results of measured air-tightness of the building envelope and the front door for each building using the blower door test

The average air-tightness measurement results for the building envelope are shown in Figure 4-33. In the 21F low-rise building, the air-tightness of the building envelope was 2.60 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 2nd floor, which is the lowest floor; 2.46 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 5th floor, which is the neutral zone; 2.42 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 8th floor; 2.68 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 11th floor; 2.34 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 14th floor; 2.59 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 17th floor; and 2.51 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 21st floor, which is the top floor. In the 27F mid-rise building, the air-tightness of the building envelope was 2.93 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 2nd floor, which is the lowest floor; 2.58 h^{-1} at 50 Pa on the 5th floor; 2.56 h^{-1} at 50

Pa on the 8th floor, which is the neutral zone; 2.52 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 11th floor; 2.39 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 14th floor; 2.59 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 17th floor; 2.56 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 21st floor; 2.54 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 24th floor, and 2.93 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 27th floor, which is the top floor. In the 33F mid-rise building, the air-tightness of the building envelope was 2.84 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 1st floor; 2.80 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 2nd floor; 2.78 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 5th floor; 2.48 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 8th floor, which is the neutral zone; 2.56 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 11th floor; 2.41 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 14th floor; 2.53 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 17th floor; 2.48 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 21st floor; 2.45 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 24th floor; 2.46 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 27th floor; 2.48 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 30th floor; 2.27 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 31st floor; 2.32 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 32nd floor; and 2.48 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa on the 33rd floor, which is the top floor. The target buildings were extremely air-tight in comparison to the buildings in previous studies, where air-tightness levels from 2.5 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa to 3.51 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa were measured [95] [102-103] [125]. According to the envelope air-tightness results of all the three buildings, the air-tightness of the lowermost and uppermost floors was greater than that of the other floors, and the neutral zone showed similar patterns in all buildings.

Figure 4-33 Results of measured average air-tightness of the building envelope for each building using the blower door test

Figures 4-34 and 4-35 show the air-tightness values obtained for each building as a result of depressurization and pressurization. At the time of depressurization, the air-tightness was large in the lowermost layer and small in the uppermost layer. Conversely, when pressurized, the air-tightness was large on the top floor of all buildings and small in the lowermost layer. Owing to the stack effect in buildings, air moves from the building envelope to the front door of the household on the lower floors, and from the front door of the household to the building envelope on the upper floors. Therefore, because a fan was used to blow wind in the same direction as that of the airflow, the air-tightness value in the lower layers was higher than that in the upper layers at the time of depressurization, while the opposite pattern was observed at the time of pressurization. However, all three buildings showed similar values in the neutral zone where there was no air inflow or outflow. Accordingly, if the air-tightness of buildings is compared, a representative value should be compared to that measured in the neutral zone.

Figure 4-34 Results of air-tightness measured under depressurization for each building using the blower door test

Figure 4-35 Results of air-tightness measured under pressurization for each building using the blower door test

Table 4-7 shows a comparison of the measurement results of the air-tightness of the front door of the household and the building envelope. The air-tightness of the front door of the household was compared for the 33rd floor, i.e., the topmost floor, the 11th floor, and the 1st floor, i.e., the lowermost floor; the air-tightness on the 33rd floor showed a difference of 75.4% between the building envelope and the front door of the household, and the front door of household was approximately 4.1 times more air-tight than the building envelope. In addition, the difference between the air-tightness of the two elements was 66.4% on the 11th floor, and the front door of household was approximately 3 times more air-tight than the building envelope. The difference between the air-tightness of the two elements of the building was 68.0% on the 1st floor, and the front door of the household was approximately 3.1 times more air-tight than the building envelope.

In previous studies, it was indicated that more pressure is distributed to the front door of a household because the front door is more air-tight than the building envelope; however, most

studies that measured the front door [100] [129] were based in the early 2000s. Therefore, this was confirmed through measurements in this study. In addition, compared to previous studies, which showed values of 70 cm²/item [100] and 124.3 cm²/item [129], the 33rd floor showed values of 53.1 cm²/item; the 11th floor, 69 cm²/item; and the 1st floor, 73 cm²/item. The front door of the household was observed to become more air-tight than indicated by previous measurement results.

Table 4-7 Comparison of building envelope air-tightness and front door air-tightness

Floor	Building envelope	Front door	Difference* (%)
	ACH50 (h ⁻¹)		
33 rd floor	2.48	0.61	75.4
11 th floor	2.56	0.86	66.4
1 st floor	2.84	0.91	68.0

* Difference (%) = (Building envelope – Front door)/Building envelope × 100

4.3 Applicability when predicting air-tightness under various conditions

4.3.1 Limitation of the n value in each building

Air-tightness was predicted using the method proposed in this Chapter 3. The 21F and 27F building were subjected to nine different outside temperature conditions: -7.3 °C, -6.8 °C, -2.3 °C, -2.2 °C, -1.9 °C, -1.4 °C, -0.9 °C, -0.4 °C, and -0.3 °C. Unlike the previous buildings, the outside air temperature of the 33F mid-rise building had seven different values: -5.4 °C, -4.4 °C, -3.6 °C, -3.1 °C, -2.4 °C, -1.6 °C, and 0.5 °C. In addition, on the 33rd floor, the interior and exterior temperature differences were larger than those of other buildings because the interior of the building was heated. Among them, n was limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1, according to the ASTM Standard E779-19 [126].

Figure 4-36 shows the relationship between the predicted air-tightness and n values. For n values smaller than 0.5, the maximum value of the air-tightness was predicted to be 1.94 h⁻¹ at 50

Pa; however, most of the air-tightness values were predicted to be as low as 1 h^{-1} or less at 50 Pa. For values with n values greater than 1, the minimum value of the air-tightness was predicted to be 3.01 h^{-1} at 50 Pa; however, most air-tightness values were predicted to be larger than 7 h^{-1} at 50 Pa. Most air-tightness values with n values greater than 0.5 and less than 1 were predicted to be $2\text{--}3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 50 Pa. According to ASTM Standard E779-19 [126], the n value is reliable only for values greater than 0.5 and less than 1. The prediction results of this study showed that the closer the n value was to the standard, the closer the predicted air-tightness was to that of the previous study. The air-tightness values were measured as $2.5\text{--}3.51 \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 50 Pa [95] [102-103] [125] in previous research studies, and air-tightness values with n values greater than 0.5 and less than 1 were similar to those reported in previous studies. In addition, the air-tightness measured using the blower door test in this study was also measured as $2\text{--}3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 50 Pa, similar to the results reported in the literature.

Figure 4-36 Limitation of the n value for predicted results in each building

4.3.2 Influence on height differences for the same difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures

Next, the dependence of the predicted results on the difference in height from the neutral zone of the target building to the analyzed point, among other factors affecting the formation of the differential pressure in the building, was determined. In particular, the relationship between the height difference and the percentage errors for the predicted results was reviewed for the same difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures. This analysis was possible because measurements in the 21F and 27F buildings were performed simultaneously and under the same weather conditions. The percentage error was calculated as defined in Chapter 3.

Figure 4-37 shows the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the height difference for the same difference in indoor and outdoor temperatures. It was found that as this temperature difference increases, the predicted air-tightness becomes similar to the measured air-tightness. In addition, the predicted air-tightness in the 27F building was more similar to the measured air-tightness than that in the 21F building for the same difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures. That is, as the height difference of the building increased for the same difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures, the predicted air-tightness became more similar to the measured air-tightness.

When the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 10–11 °C, the percentage error for the predicted results in the 21F building was distributed over 25.5–57.5%, and the deviation in the percentage errors for the predicted results was distributed over 24–66.8%. Similarly, in the 27F building, the range and deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results were distributed over 30.6–32.1% and 29.9–32.8%, respectively. When comparing the two buildings, the minimum value of the range and deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results was smaller in the 21F building than that in the 27F building, but the number was very small. When the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 11–12 °C, the

deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results was smaller in the 27F building than that in the 21F building; however, the range of percentage errors for the predicted results was larger in the 27F building. Comprehensively, when the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures was 10–12 °C, the percentage errors for the predicted results did not necessarily decrease as the height difference increased. That is, when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was small, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the height difference was small as well.

In contrast, when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 14–17 °C, as the height difference increased, both the range and deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results were smaller in the 27F building than those in the 21F building. In addition, when the values of difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures were 14–15 °C, 15–16 °C, and 16–17 °C, both the range and deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results decreased as the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased. When the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 16–17 °C, i.e., when the temperature difference was the largest, the range and deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results in the 21F building were distributed over 5.3–22.9% and 5.1–27.6%, respectively. Similarly, in the 27F building, the range and deviation of the percentage errors for the predicted results were distributed over 1.5–6.5% and 1.2–10.7%, respectively. Of note, both the values were less than approximately 10% here. Here, as the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the height difference increased as well.

Figure 4-37 Dependence of the predicted air-tightness on ΔH at the same ΔT

4.3.3 Influence of difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures at the same height difference for each building

A. Low-rise (21F) building

As a second factor, the effect of the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures on the predicted air-tightness was examined. In particular, the relationship between the percentage errors for the predicted results and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was reviewed at the same height difference (the difference in height between the point to be analyzed and the neutral zone). Figure 4-38 shows this relationship for the case of the 21F building. The relationship between the predicted air-tightness and the measured air-tightness was reviewed for five values of height difference: 9 m, 18 m, 27 m, 36 m, and 48 m.

At a height difference of 9 m, the percentage errors of the predicted results were relatively lower under conditions with large differences between indoor and outdoor temperatures compared to conditions with small temperature differences. That is, as the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased, the predicted results became similar to the measured results. In particular, the percentage error of the predicted results was approximately 67% when the

difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 10.5 °C, while it was approximately 24% when the temperature difference was 16.9 °C.

The predicted result at a height difference of 18 m was similar to the trend observed for the height difference of 9 m. The values of temperature difference were 14.9 °C and 15.4 °C when the percentage error was approximately 51%. There was no difference in the percentage error because there was no significant difference between the two temperature difference values. In addition, the same trend was observed when the percentage error was approximately 23%, and the values of difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures were 15.9 °C and 16.4 °C.

The predicted result for 27 m was the same as that for 9 m and 18 m. That is, the larger the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, the more the predicted result was consistent with the measured result. Moreover, temperature difference values were 15.9 °C and 16.4 °C when the percentage error was approximately 28%.

The predicted results for both 36 m and 48 m were also the same as the previous results. For the results predicted for the 21F building, the percentage errors of the predicted results decreased as the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures increased at the same height difference. In addition, the percentage errors decreased as the height difference increased.

B. Mid-rise (27F) building

Figure 4-39 shows the relationship between the percentage errors for the predicted results and differences between indoor and outdoor temperatures at the same height difference for 27F building. The relationship between the predicted air-tightness and the measured air-tightness was reviewed for five values of height difference: 30 m, 39 m, 51 m, 60 m, and 69 m. The predicted result for the height difference of 21 m was excluded because there was the only one temperature difference.

Figure 4-38 Dependence of the predicted results on ΔT at the same ΔH in the 21F building

In the 27F and 21F buildings, the predicted results were consistent with the measured results; the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased at the same height difference. In addition, as the height difference increased, the percentage error of the predicted results decreased. Notably, the percentage error for the predicted results in the 27F building was lower than that for the predicted results in the 21F building. This was because as the height of the building increased, the differential pressure formed at the analysis point of the 27F building was larger than that of the 21F building. In addition, the percentage error of the predicted results was less than 10% for all height differences when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 16–17 °C. The differential pressure formed at a height difference of 30 m was 15 Pa, while the differential pressures formed at height differences of 39 m, 51 m, 60 m, and 69 m were all over 20 Pa.

The percentage error for the predicted result was approximately 32% when the height difference was 30 m and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 15.9 °C.

Although the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was large because the height difference was low, the differential pressure was as low as 11 Pa. Thus, the percentage error of the predicted results was high.

In contrast, the percentage error for the predicted result was approximately 32% when the height difference was 69 m and the temperature difference was 10.5–11.5 °C. Even though the height difference was large, because the temperature difference was small, the differential pressure formed was as low as 12 Pa. Thus, the percentage error of the predicted results was high.

Figure 4-39 Dependence of the predicted results on ΔT at the same ΔH in the 27F building

C. Mid-rise (33F) building

Figure 4-40 shows the same relationship as in Figures 4-38 and 4-39 but for the 33F building. In this case, the percentage errors for the predicted results were reviewed for 11 values of height difference: 9 m, 18 m, 24 m, 27 m, 36 m, 45 m, 54 m, 63 m, 66 m, 69 m, and 72 m. Thus, the results were predicted for a higher number of conditions compared to those for the 21F and 27F

buildings. The reason for this is explained later.

In the 33F building, the same results were obtained as those for the 21F and 27F buildings. As a result, for all target buildings, the predicted results were consistent with the measured results as the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased at the same height difference. In addition, as the height difference increased, the percentage error of the predicted results decreased. In particular, at 54 m, 63 m, 66 m, 69 m, and 72 m, the percentage errors for the predicted results were less than 20%, regardless of the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures. The height difference was high even though the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was low, and the differential pressure formed at the analysis point was 22 Pa or more. The results under the conditions of low height difference in the 33F building were predicted, when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was larger than that of the other two buildings because the indoor temperature was set to 24 °C. This is the reason why the results for this building were predicted for a higher number of conditions compared to those for the previous two buildings.

At a height difference of 9 m, when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 27.9 °C, the percentage error for the predicted results was approximately 42%, and the differential pressure at the analysis point was 4 Pa. In comparison, when the values of height difference and temperature difference were 18 m and 24 m and 27.8 °C and 27 °C, respectively, the percentage errors for the predicted results were approximately 67%, and the differential pressures at the analysis point were 6 Pa and 11 Pa, respectively. Although the height differences of these two cases are larger than 9 m, the percentage errors for the predicted results at 18 m and 24 m were high; however, the predicted results at 9 m, 18 m, and 24 m were all significantly different from the measured results.

Figure 4-40 Dependence of the predicted results on ΔT at the same ΔH in the 33F building

4.3.4 Correlation analysis between percentage errors, temperature difference, height difference, and pressure difference

Based on the above data, Pearson's correlation analysis was performed for the height difference, difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, differential pressure, and percentage error of the predicted results. Pearson's correlation coefficient is a statistical test that measures the relationship or association between two continuous variables. It is known to be the best method for measuring the association between variables of interest because it is based on the method of covariance. Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted using Equation (59).

$$r_{XY} = \frac{\sum_i^n (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum_i^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2} \sqrt{\sum_i^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (59)$$

where r is the Pearson's correlation coefficient. Table 4-8 summarizes the relationship between Pearson's correlation coefficient and the degree of correlation. The coefficient values can range from +1 to -1, where +1 indicates a perfect positive relationship, -1 indicates a perfect negative

relationship, and 0 indicates that no relationship exists.

Table 4-8 Degree of correlation and Pearson's correlation coefficient

Degree of correlation	Pearson's correlation coefficient, PCC
Perfect	± 1
High degree	± 0.7 to ± 0.9
Moderate degree	± 0.4 to ± 0.7
Low degree	± 0.2 to ± 0.4
No correlation	0 to ± 0.2

Table 4-9 shows the results of Pearson's correlation analysis. Both the height difference and the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures were found to be significantly correlated with the differential pressure at the 1% significance level. This means that as the height difference and temperature difference increased, the differential pressure increased. However, as per Table 4-8 the coefficient for the height difference was 0.709, indicating a high positive correlation. In contrast, the coefficient for the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 0.235, indicating a low positive correlation. Therefore, the height difference had a greater effect than the temperature difference on the differential pressure. This is because the fluctuation range of the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures is very small compared to the height difference due to factors such as limited outside temperature and heating set point under actual conditions.

The height difference and differential pressure were significantly correlated with the percentage errors of the predicted results at a significance level of 1%, and the height difference and differential pressure were negatively correlated with the percentage errors of the predicted results with correlation coefficients of -0.605 and -0.458 , respectively. This means that as the height difference and differential pressure increased, the percentage errors for the predicted result decreased. That is, as the height difference and differential pressure increased, the predicted results became similar to the measured results.

Table 4-9 Results of the Pearson's correlation analysis

		ΔH	ΔT	ΔP	Percentage error
ΔP	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0.709**	0.235**	1	-0.458**
	Significance probability	0.000	0.001		0.000
Percentage error	Pearson's correlation coefficient	-0.605**	-0.067	-0.458**	1
	Significance probability	0.000	0.339	0.000	

** : Significance level 1%

4.4 Generalization of the proposed air-tightness prediction method

4.4.1 95% confidence interval in the measured results using the blower door test

To generalize the proposed air-tightness prediction method, the following procedure was followed. ASTM Standard E779-19 [126], which is a blower door test standard, was used to obtain the confidence limits of the combined pressurization and depressurization results using the combined result (which is the simple average of the pressurization and depressurization values) plus and minus the quantity calculated using Equation (60).

$$PE95(X_{\text{combined}}) = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \times \sqrt{PE95(X_{\text{depress}})^2 + PE95(X_{\text{press}})^2} \quad (60)$$

where $PE95(X_{\text{depress}})$ is half the width of the 95% confidence interval for the depressurization result (h^{-1}) and $PE95(X_{\text{press}})$ is half the width of the 95% confidence interval for the pressurization result (h^{-1}).

In Chapter 2, the C and n values of the blower door test standard are calculated using Equations (31)–(40). The 95% confidence limits for C and n can be determined by the following equations. The variance of n and ln(C) is given by Equations (61)–(62). The confidence limits for ln(C) and n are Equations (63)–(64). Where the values of the two-sided student distribution ($T(95\%, N - 2)$) are given in Table 4-10.

$$S_n = \frac{1}{S_x} \left(\frac{S_{y-n}^2 \cdot S_{xy}}{N-2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (61)$$

$$S_{\ln(C)} = S_n \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2}{N} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (62)$$

$$I_n = S_n T(95\%, N-2) \quad (63)$$

$$I_{\ln(C)} = S_{\ln(C)} T(95\%, N-2) \quad (64)$$

Table 4-10 Two-sided confidence limits T (95%, N) for a student distribution

N-2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
T (95%, N-2)	3.182	2.776	2.571	2.447	2.365	2.306	2.262	2.228
N-2	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
T (95%, N-2)	2.201	2.179	2.160	2.145	2.131	2.120	2.110	2.101

This means that the probability is 95% that the pressure exponent n lies in the interval $(n - I_n, n + I_n)$ and the probability is 95% that the air leakage coefficient C lies in the interval $(C \cdot \exp^{-I_{\ln(C)}}, C \cdot \exp^{I_{\ln(C)}})$. The estimate of the variance around the regression line Equation (33) at the value x is Equation (65), and the confidence interval in the estimate of y using Equation (33) at any x is Equation (66). In practice, the above error analysis was carried out using a standard statistical computer program, IBM SPSS statistics 26.

$$S_y(x) = S_n \left(\frac{N-1}{N} S_x^2 + (x-\bar{x})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (65)$$

$$I_y(x) = S_y(x) T(95\%, N-2) \quad (66)$$

Table 4-11 summarizes the lower and upper limits of the measured results at the 95% confidence interval, while Figure 4-41 shows the measured and predicted results at the calculated 95% confidence interval. Figure 4-41 (a) shows the results for the 21F building, and all results included in the 95% confidence interval were predicted on only the 21st floor. Figure 4-41 (b) shows the results for the 27F building, and the results in this case were predicted on floors 14, 17,

21, 24, and 27. Figure 4-41 (c) shows the results for the 33F building, and the results here were predicted on floors 1, 17, 21, 24, 27, and 30–33. Notably, more floors were included for the 33F building than for the 21F and 27F buildings because the air-tightness was predicted when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was larger than that of the other two buildings. In addition, the pressure difference formed in the 33F building was larger than that in the other two buildings. Figure 4-41 (d) shows the results for the 42F building, and the results included in the 95% confidence interval here were predicted on floors 4, 36, and 42. Because the 42F building was measured to examine the reliability of the method proposed in Chapter 3, the measurement locations were not changed. Thus, although only few predicted results were included in the 95% confidence interval, all of them on the 36th and 42nd floors were included in the 95% confidence interval.

Table 4-11 95% confidence intervals for the predicted and measured results

Buildings		Measured results (h ⁻¹ at 50 Pa)			Predicted results (h ⁻¹ at 50 Pa)
		Lower limit PE95	Measurement	Upper limit PE95	
21F building	21 st floor	2.01	2.51	2.98	2.17, 2.19, 2.38, 2.64
	27 th floor	2.34	2.93	3.43	2.34, 2.58, 2.59, 2.90
27F building	24 th floor	2.27	2.54	2.74	2.49, 2.73
	21 st floor	2.21	2.56	2.84	2.53, 2.59, 2.76
	17 th floor	2.29	2.59	2.87	2.47, 2.86
	14 th floor	2.17	2.39	2.61	2.56
33F building	33 rd floor	2.05	2.48	2.91	2.30, 2.63, 2.67, 2.72, 2.90
	32 nd floor	1.98	2.32	2.74	2.02, 2.09, 2.17, 2.28, 2.45, 2.73
	31 st floor	1.95	2.27	2.60	2.18, 2.23, 2.29
	30 th floor	2.14	2.48	2.88	2.43, 2.87
	27 th floor	2.16	2.46	2.79	2.19, 2.42
	24 th floor	2.17	2.45	2.77	2.74
	21 st floor	2.11	2.48	2.93	2.10, 2.42
	17 th floor	1.98	2.53	3.00	2.07, 2.56
42F building	1 st floor	2.44	2.84	3.22	2.45
	42 nd floor	2.79	3.19	3.64	2.96, 2.97, 3.14, 3.15, 3.22
	36 th floor	2.68	3.14	3.71	3.07, 3.20, 3.27
	4 th floor	2.66	3.13	3.68	2.87

(a) 21F building

(b) 27F building

(c) 33F building

(d) 42F building

Figure 4-41 Results of the 95% confidence interval for the measured and predicted results

4.4.2 Suggested applicable pressure difference, temperature difference, and height difference at the 95% confidence interval

Figure 4-42 shows the relationship between the predicted results, the pressure difference, difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, and the height difference from the neutral zone at the 95% confidence interval.

Figure 4-42 (a) shows the results for the 21F building. Here, the results included in the 95% confidence interval were predicted under the condition of 19–21 Pa. The height difference was 48 m, which corresponded to the top floor of the building (21st floor), and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 14.9–16.4 °C. Because this building had a lower height than the other buildings, few prediction results were included in the 95% confidence interval, and the analysis points of the predicted results were all above the neutral level.

Figure 4-42 (b) shows the results for the 27F building. Here, the results included in the 95% confidence interval were predicted under the condition of 15–34 Pa, and the analyzed points were from the 14th floor to the 27th floor. When the differential pressure of the predicted results was 15 Pa, the analyzed point was the 14th floor. The height difference was 30 m, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 16.5–17 °C. Similarly, when the differential pressure of the predicted results was 34 Pa, the analyzed point was the 27th floor. The height difference was 69 m, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 15.4–17 °C. In this building, as in the 21F building, the analysis points of the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval were all above the neutral level.

Figure 4-42 (c) shows the results for the 33F building. Here, the results included in the 95% confidence interval were predicted under the condition of 10–32 Pa, and the analyzed points were the 1st floor and from the 17th floor to the 33rd floor. In particular, when the analyzed point was the 1st floor, where the height difference was 24 m, the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 29.8–30 °C, which was the highest. Thus, the differential pressure of the

predicted results was 11 Pa. In this building, unlike the 21F and 27F buildings, the analysis point of the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval was not only in the upper neutral zone but also in the lower neutral zone. In addition, when the differential pressure of the predicted results was 32 Pa, the analyzed point was the 33rd floor. The height difference was 72 m, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 27.9–29.1 °C.

Figure 4-41 (d) shows the results for the 42F building. Here, the results included in the 95% confidence interval were predicted under the condition of 23–101 Pa, and the analyzed points were the 4th, 36th, and 42nd floors. In this building, as in the 33F building, the analysis points of the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval were not only in the upper neutral zone but also in the lower neutral zone. In addition, here too, few prediction results were included in the 95% confidence interval because the results were not predicted under various conditions of height and temperature difference values. When the differential pressure of the predicted results was 23 Pa, the analyzed point was the 4th floor. The height difference was 21 m, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 29.9 °C. Similarly, when the differential pressure of the predicted results was 101 Pa, the analyzed point was the 42nd floor. The height difference was 93 m, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 26.3–30 °C.

Figure 4-42 Relationship between the predicted results, ΔP , ΔH , and ΔT

at the 95% confidence interval

Based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval, a differential pressure condition that could be applied to the proposed method was investigated. Figure 4-43 shows the applicable pressure difference based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval. When the differential pressure formed at the analysis point was at least 10 Pa, the predicted results were consistent with the measured results; however, a considerable number of results did not match. The applicable differential pressure condition was based on the section that was considered reliable because all the predicted values were consistent with the measured values. At a pressure of 24 Pa formed owing to the stack effect in a building, all the predicted results were consistent with the measured results. Thus, the minimum differential pressure that could be applied to all buildings was approximately 24 Pa, and the method proposed here can be applied to cases in which the differential pressure formed by the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures and the difference in the height from the neutral zone of the target building to the analysis point is 24 Pa.

In Chapter 3, it was suggested that the predicted value is reliable only when a certain differential pressure is formed at the point to be analyzed and when the differential pressure is over 50 Pa. However, based on various analysis techniques, the predicted results were deemed valid even at a pressure of 24 Pa, which is smaller than 50 Pa.

In the following sections, the temperature difference and height difference for the target buildings for the 24 Pa pressure value are presented. Acceptable conditions using the temperature difference and height difference are suggested by the existing air-tightness measurement standards, and air-tightness measurement is recommended only under those conditions. For the proposed method, acceptable conditions and guidelines are discussed.

Figure 4-43 Applicable pressure difference based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval

4.4.3 Suggested guidelines for the proposed method using the acceptable condition

Existing air-tightness measurement standards such as ASTM Standard E779-03 [57], ISO 9972 [61], and EN 13829 [24] suggest $\Delta H \times \Delta T$ as acceptable conditions. According to ASTM Standard E779-03 [57], if the product of the absolute value of the indoor/outdoor air temperature difference multiplied by the building height, gives an acceptable condition greater than $200 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$ ($1,180 \text{ ft}\cdot\text{°F}$), the test shall not be performed, because the pressure difference induced by the stack effect is too large to allow accurate interpretation of the results. In addition, EN 13829 limits the acceptable condition to $500 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$ and wind speed below 6 m/s [24], and ISO 9972 limits the acceptable condition to $250 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$ and wind speed below 6 m/s [61]. Also, CIBSE TM-23 of the existing standard does no limit the acceptable condition, but this imposes the certain limiting conditions that the internal to external air temperature difference should be less than 10 °C , and the wind speed should be less than 3 m/s [62], and CAN/CGSB-149.10-M86 limits the wind speed

should be less than 20 km/h [64]. According to ATTMA Technical Standard L1, the dwelling differential pressures induced during an air test should be greater than those occurring naturally to minimize the influence of wind and stack effects, and the minimum pressure of at least 50 Pa must be established across the building envelope [130]. Although it was a concept opposite to the above acceptable conditions, acceptable conditions suitable for this study are presented because the predicted air-tightness became similar to the measured air-tightness as the stack effect increases. Thus, to provide guidelines for future use, an acceptable condition that satisfied the differential pressure condition of 24 Pa for each building was investigated—as in the aforementioned standards. Figure 4-44 shows the relationship between the acceptable conditions and the differential pressure.

Figure 4-44 Relationship between acceptable condition and applicable ΔP

For the 21F building, the minimum differential pressure of the predicted results included in the 95% confidence interval was less than 24 Pa. Therefore, an acceptable condition for the largest differential pressure among the predicted results was investigated. The differential pressure was 21 Pa, which was measured on the 21st floor. Because the height difference was 48 m and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 16.4 °C, the acceptable condition suggested by the existing air-tightness measurement standard was $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 787 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$.

For the 27F building, when the differential pressure of the predicted results was more than 24 Pa, it was from the 21st floor to the 27th floor, and the differential pressure was 25–34 Pa. When the differential pressure was 25 Pa, it was measured on the 21st floor. The pressure difference was formed by a height difference of 51 m and a temperature difference of 15.9 °C. Based on the temperature difference and height difference, the acceptable condition suggested by the existing air-tightness measurement standard was $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 811 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$.

For example, when the building envelope air-tightness is similar to that observed in previous studies [95] [102-103] [125] with 2.5–3.5 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa, the occupants of the 21st floor can reliably predict the air-tightness using the method proposed in this study under the condition that the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures is 15.4 °C or more. The difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures of 15.4 °C is obtained when the outdoor temperature is 8.6 °C and the indoor temperature is set to 24 °C, which is the temperature set by heating systems in winter. In addition, a temperature difference of 5.4 °C is obtained when the outdoor temperature is 15.4 °C and the indoor temperature is set to 10 °C, which is the minimum temperature required for protection against freezing. When the outdoor weather environment was measured in this study, the outdoor temperature was the same as in early December. For Pyeongtaek, where the 27F building was located, the Korea Meteorological Administration reported that the outside air temperature was 8.2 °C at 5 pm and 4.8 °C at 9 pm on December 1, 2020.

For the 33F building, the differential pressure of the predicted results satisfying the criteria analyzed above was 24–32 Pa. The differential pressure was 24 Pa, and it was measured on the 30th floor. The pressure difference was formed by a height difference of 63 m and a temperature difference of 27.0 °C. Based on the temperature difference and height difference, the acceptable condition was $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,701 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$. Therefore, when the building envelope air-tightness has a similar level of air-tightness as in the literature suggested above, the occupants of the 30th floor can reliably predict the air-tightness using the proposed method under the condition that the difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures is 27.0 °C or more (outdoor temperature: -3 °C at an indoor temperature of 24 °C).

Although the difference between the indoors and outdoors temperatures in the 33F building was larger than that in the 27F building, the differential pressure was small. From the perspective of horizontal airflow, TDC is determined according to the air-tightness of horizontal airflow elements such as an elevator door, stairwell door, front door of household, and building envelope. In the 33F building, most of the pressure was distributed at the front door of the household, but pressures greater than 10 Pa were also distributed at the stairwell door. In contrast, in the 27F building, a small pressure of 2–4 Pa was distributed at the stairwell door. Because the method proposed in this study is used to predict the air-tightness using the differential pressure of the front door of the household and the building envelope, the applicable differential pressure conditions were investigated based on the front door of the household. Therefore, the suggested differential pressure condition may be slightly different because the TDC of the airflow path may vary depending on architectural characteristics, and it should be utilized with reference to acceptable conditions in the applicable differential pressure suggested in Section 3.3 (B).

For the 42F building, the pressure difference of the predicted results satisfying the criteria analyzed above was 52–101 Pa. The smallest differential pressure (52 Pa) was measured at the top floor of the 42F building. The pressure difference was formed by a height difference of 93 m

and a temperature difference of 25.8 °C. Based on the temperature difference and height difference, the acceptable condition was $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 2,399 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$. Therefore, when the building envelope air-tightness has a similar level of air-tightness as in the literature discussed above, the occupants living on the 42nd floor can reliably predict the air-tightness using the proposed method under the condition that the temperature difference between indoor and outdoor is 25.8 °C or more (outdoor temperature: -1.8 °C at an indoor temperature of 24 °C).

The acceptable conditions presented in the 33F and 42F buildings and the acceptable conditions presented in the 27F building are different. In addition, although the acceptable condition presented in the 27F building was satisfied, it was difficult to generalize because there were results with a difference between the predicted and measured values.

Among the results that had differences between the predicted value and the measured value, the highest limit level of the acceptable condition was $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 997.2 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$. The conditions were measured on the 21st floor of the 33F building, the height difference was 36 m, and the temperature difference was 27.7 °C. Therefore, the acceptable conditions in which the predicted and measured values were consistent for all buildings were $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,000 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$. Based on the suggested acceptable condition, when the indoor temperature was set to 24 °C, if the outdoor temperature is -11.3 °C based on the winter design standard temperature, air-tightness could be reliably predicted at a height difference of 29 m using the proposed method. The height difference of 29 m varies depending on the location of the neutral zone; it is the 15th floor in the 21F building, 18th floor in the 27F building, 19th floor in the 33F building, and 21st floor in the 42F building. Table 4-12 lists the applicable condition for each building.

Table 4-12 Acceptable condition in each building

Building	Acceptable condition
21F building	$\Delta H \times \Delta T < 787 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$
27F building	$\Delta H \times \Delta T < 811 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$
33F building	$\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,701 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$
42F building	$\Delta H \times \Delta T < 2,399 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$
All buildings	$\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,000 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$

4.4.4 Normalized mean square error (NMSE), fractional bias (FB), and fractional standard deviation (FS) of the predicted results at the 95% confidence interval

The predicted results at the derived 95% confidence interval were statistically evaluated using indicators such as the normalized mean square error (NMSE), fractional bias (FB), and fractional standard deviation (FS) suggested in the ASTM Guide D5157-97 [127] to assess agreement with the measured results.

The NMSE (Equation (67)) is a measure of the magnitude of the error between the predicted and measured results. This statistic emphasizes the scatter in the entire dataset. The normalization by the product of the predicted results and the measured results assures that the NMSE will not be biased towards models that overpredict or under-predict the results. Smaller NMSE values indicate better model performance.

The FB (Equation (68)) is a measure of the bias of the mean concentration of the predicted and measured results. The bias was normalized to make it nondimensionless. This FB varies between +2 and -2 and has an ideal value of zero for an ideal model.

The FS (Equation (69)) is a similar index of bias based on the variance of the predicted and measurement results. This FS has an ideal value of zero for an ideal model.

$$NMSE = \frac{(\overline{ACH_{50m}} - \overline{ACH_{50p}})^2}{\overline{ACH_{50m}} \times \overline{ACH_{50p}}} \quad (67)$$

$$FB = 2 \times \left(\frac{\overline{ACH_{50m}} - \overline{ACH_{50p}}}{\overline{ACH_{50m}} + \overline{ACH_{50p}}} \right) \quad (68)$$

$$FS = 2 \times \left(\frac{\sigma^2 \times \overline{ACH_{50m}} - \sigma^2 \times \overline{ACH_{50p}}}{\sigma^2 \times \overline{ACH_{50m}} + \sigma^2 \times \overline{ACH_{50p}}} \right) \quad (69)$$

where $\overline{ACH_{50m}}$ is the measured results of air-tightness using the blower door test (h^{-1}), and $\overline{ACH_{50p}}$ is the predicted result of air-tightness using the proposed method (h^{-1}).

For the results to be considered acceptable, NMSE should be less than 0.25, FB should be 0.25 or lower and be -0.25 or higher. FS should be 0.5 or lower and be -0.5 or higher. The calculated results of this study are presented in Table 4-13. The NMSE, FB, and FS calculated for the proposed method were 0.006, 0.024, and -0.389 , respectively. These values meet the criteria for adequate model performance.

Table 4-13 Accuracy of the proposed method

Index (acceptable range)	Value
NMSE (NMSE < 0.25)	0.006
FB ($-0.25 \leq FB \leq 0.25$)	0.024
FS ($-0.5 \leq FS \leq 0.5$)	-0.389

4.5 Discussion

In this chapter, because the building verified in Chapter 3 had a large differential pressure caused by the stack effect, the proposed method was verified and generalized for relatively low-rise and mid-rise buildings. First, a process for generalizing the proposed method was suggested through a theoretical review of the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures and the height difference of the building, as these factors form the differential

pressure in the building. In the 21F low-rise building and 27F mid-rise building, measurements were taken under nine different outdoor temperature conditions, and in the 33F mid-rise building, seven different outdoor temperature conditions were measured. Depending on the process applied, the external weather environment, indoor temperature, humidity, and the differential pressure of the main airflow path were measured under various outdoor temperature conditions in the same manner as verified in Chapter 3. The air-tightness was predicted by using the measured differential pressure, which was compared with the measured air-tightness by using the blower door test. By examining the dependence on the main factors that form the differential pressure, the minimum differential pressure condition to which the proposed method can be applied was presented. In addition, this pressure difference was generalized for application to all buildings. The results of this chapter are as follows.

- 1) The differential pressure was measured by using various conditions such as different buildings, varying indoor and outdoor temperatures, and many floor conditions for each building. In addition, the air-tightness was predicted by the proposed method using the measured differential pressure, and the n value of the predicted air-tightness was limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1. The dependence of the predicted air-tightness values that met both the standard and the measured air-tightness obtained using a blower door test was examined for the factors that form the differential pressure in the building. Finally, after examining the dependence, the proposed method was generalized by presenting the minimum differential pressure condition that can be applied to all buildings.
- 2) As a result of the temperature and humidity distributions of a household, in the 21F and 27F buildings, all measured floors were formed at 10 °C. Further, according to the heating conditions, in the 33F building, all measured floors were formed at 24 °C according to the heating conditions. In all buildings, the halls and stairwells

showed a high temperature distribution as the height increased from the lower floors to the higher floors, and the temperature stratification was evident as the number of floors increased. As a result of the differential pressure measurement, because the pressure difference was measured under various conditions, there were differences between the measured buildings. However, in most buildings, the differential pressure of the building envelope was measured as 0–5 Pa, and the maximum pressure was distributed at the front door of the household; thus, a maximum pressure of 21–33 Pa was measured according to the outdoor temperature conditions. The air-tightness measurements of the building envelope, which were obtained using the blower door test at the point where the differential pressure was measured, ranged from 2.46–2.93 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa. Although the measurement results were different for each building, the neutral zone was similar in all buildings. This suggests that if the air-tightness of the building is compared, the representative value should be compared with that measured in the neutral zone. In addition, the air-tightness of the front door of household was obtained approximately 3- to 4.1-times more than that of the building envelope.

- 3) In this chapter, air-tightness was predicted using the method proposed in Chapter 3, and n values were limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1. Most of the air-tightness values with n values greater than 0.5 and less than 1 were predicted to be 2–3 h⁻¹ at 50 Pa. Next, the dependence of the predicted results on the factors affecting the formation of differential pressure in the building was reviewed. In particular, when the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was small, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the height difference was small as well. In contrast, when the temperatures differences were larger than the temperatures differences of the previous, as the height difference increased, the

predicted results became consistent with the measured results. Therefore, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the height difference increased. In the 21F, 27F, and 33F buildings, the percentage errors of the predicted results decreased as the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased under the same height difference condition; thus, the dependence of the predicted air-tightness on the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased. Following this, Pearson's correlation analysis was performed based on the above data. For the correlation with the differential pressure, both the height difference and temperature difference were significant at the 1% significance level. The height difference was greater than the temperature difference in terms of the degree of influence on the differential pressure. For the correlation with the percentage errors of the predicted results, the height difference and differential pressure were significant at the 1% significance level.

- 4) To generalize the air-tightness prediction method proposed in this paper, the 95% confidence interval in the measured results was calculated using the blower door test. The results included in the 95% confidence interval for the 21F building were predicted under the condition of 19–21 Pa. The height difference was 48 m, which was the top floor of the building on the 21st floor, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 14.9–16.4 °C. Next, the results included in the 95% confidence interval for the 27F building were predicted under the condition of 15–34 Pa, the analyzed points were from the 14th floor to the 27th floor, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 15.4–17 °C. Subsequently, the results included in the 95% confidence interval for the 33F building were predicted under the condition of a differential pressure of 10–32 Pa, the analyzed points were the 1st floor and from the 17th floor to the 33rd floor, and

the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures was 27.9–30 °C. Finally, the results included in the 95% confidence interval for the 42F building were predicted when the differential pressure was 23–101 Pa, the analyzed points were the 4th, 36th, and 42nd floors, and the temperature difference was 26.3–30 °C. Based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval for each building, the minimum differential pressure condition for all predicted results included in the 95% confidence interval was found to be at least 24 Pa. Next, an acceptable condition that satisfied the differential pressure condition of 24 Pa for each building analyzed in this study was investigated. For the 21F building, the minimum differential pressure of the predicted results included in the 95% confidence interval was less than 24 Pa. Therefore, an acceptable condition for the largest differential pressure among the predicted results was investigated. The acceptable condition was found to be $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 787 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$. For the 27F, 33F, and 42F buildings, the acceptable conditions were found to be $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 811 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$, $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,701 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$, and $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 2,399 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$, respectively. Based on the applicable 24 Pa pressure, the acceptable condition for which the predicted and measured values were consistent for all buildings was found to be $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,000 \text{ m}\cdot\text{°C}$. When the indoor temperature was set to 24 °C and if the outdoor temperature was –11.3 °C based on the winter design standard temperature ($\Delta T = 35.3 \text{ °C}$), airtightness could be reliably predicted at a height difference of 29 m (approximately 15th floor to 21st floor) using the proposed method. Predicted values at the derived 95% confidence interval were statistically evaluated using the NMSE, FB, and FS parameters for assessing agreement with the measured results. The NMSE, FB, and FS calculated for the proposed method were 0.006, 0.024, and –0.389, respectively, and these values met the criteria for adequate model performance.

The limitations of this study are as follows. The method of this study aims to predict the air-tightness using the differential pressure generated by the stack effect in the building; however, in case of an air leakage from the front door of the household, the direction of the airflow formed by the stack effect is clear. Therefore, this method can only be applied to high-rise residential buildings. Because most high-rise office buildings have open plans, the direction of airflow is not unidirectional, as in residential buildings, where air flows out through the building envelope at the upper floors, but is rather bidirectional. In addition, because the air-tightness of internal partitions is not tight compared to that of a residential building, the direction of airflow is not clearly formed. In addition, it is difficult to apply the proposed method to office buildings where the effect of wind pressure is very large.

In the future, more types of buildings will be reviewed by applying simulation and optimization techniques, and the differential pressure and acceptable conditions in this study will be presented more clearly. In addition, based on this study, the author plans to analyze each type of apartment house in Korea and present, in more detail, the type conditions, air-tightness conditions, applicable differential pressure, number of floors in buildings, and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures.

Chapter 5 Conclusions

This study suggested a new method for predicting the air-tightness by measuring the difference in pressure that occurs naturally in a building owing to the stack effect. In particular, this study aimed to address the problems and limitations of existing air-tightness measurement methods. Accordingly, this study analyzed the relationship between the differential pressure and the air-tightness in a building, as well as the principle behind existing air-tightness measurement methods. The method proposed herein was verified through actual measurements in various buildings. The results of the study are summarized as follows.

5.1 Pressure difference and air-tightness in buildings

The driving force of air in a building can be formed by the stack effect, wind, difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, and mechanical ventilation systems; this force can vary depending on various factors. The differential pressure in a building is formed by the stack effect, and the relationship between the differential pressure in a building, air-tightness, and airflow can be explained by the Bernoulli equation. Because the differential pressure inside a building is formed by the stack effect, the pressure distribution varies depending on the air-tightness (air leakage area) of the main airflow path inside the building.

Representative methods of measuring air-tightness include the tracer gas method and the fan pressurization method. The limitations of each method were analyzed. The decay method is lengthy; further, it can only measure the amount of infiltration of the entire building and cannot measure that of the components of the building. Limitations of the blower door test include a complex measurement preparation process, high cost, and a large amount of noise generated during the measurements. Because of measurement limitations, it is difficult to accurately

determine the zero-flow pressure, and it is difficult to adjust the pressure of the building according to the surrounding environment. Moreover, instability, difficulties in determining the air volume according to the characteristics of the building, complexities in the measurement process, and difficulties in performing measurements owing to poor expertise are also other problems that can occur.

A review of domestic and international research trends on air-tightness measurements and predictions indicates that CO₂ concentration decay tests have been conducted from the 1980s to the present, and efforts to measure air-tightness using low-concentration CO₂ gas generated by the occupants of a building have been made. The blower door test was studied in other countries in the 1970s and in Korea in the 1990s and has been actively employed in recent years. Most studies have aimed to measure the air-tightness of many buildings and then predict the air-tightness through a statistical analysis based on the measured data. However, it is generally difficult to secure a large amount of air-tightness data.

In addition, this study is different from the concept of TDC previously reviewed, but the viewpoint of predicting the air-tightness by using the differential pressure formed by the stack effect is the same. Using 'TDC' proposed by Cho, Yoon et al. redefined the TDC to reflect the leakage area, which is an input parameter that is difficult to measure appropriately from the perspective of simulation modeling. However, their study measured the input parameters of the simulation such as the leakage area. In other words, there is a disadvantage in that the leakage area must be measured for an element in the horizontal leakage path of the building.

5.2 Development of a new method to measure air-tightness

This paper proposed a new method for predicting the air-tightness of high-rise residential buildings using the pressure difference that occurs under natural climate conditions. By analyzing

the principles and concepts of existing air-tightness measurement methods, a formula and process for applying the method proposed in this paper to an actual building were presented using the relationship between the differential pressure and airflow.

In brief, a fan is installed on the front door of a household as in the existing blower door test. The amount of air flowing into and out of the building envelope is not measured using the fan to pressurize and depressurize the household but is instead measured under the condition in which a differential pressure forms in the building through the stack effect. The air-tightness is predicted based on the pressure difference between the front door of the household and the building envelope. The air volume of the building envelope can be calculated using the differential pressure and air volume conditions presented in the air leakage report of the front door of the household and compared to the actual measured differential pressure of the front door of the household and the building envelope. However, at least two measurements are required. Using these two sets of differential pressure data and air volume data of the building envelope, it is possible to calculate the C and n values, which are unique characteristic values of the building envelope, using the formula proposed in this paper. Finally, the air-tightness (ACH50) of the building envelope can be determined using the calculated C and n values.

As a case study, the proposed method was applied to an actual building. The predicted air-tightness results of the upper floors (36th and 42nd floors), where the differential pressure was relatively large, and the measured air-tightness results obtained using the blower door test were not largely different. However, the air-tightness values predicted using the differential pressure measured at 16th floor near the neutral zone, where the differential pressure was small, were considerably different from the measured values. The air-tightness results predicted using the method proposed in this paper were reliable when the differential pressure of the building components was more than 50 Pa.

5.3 Evaluation of the proposed method for air-tightness prediction

This study generalized the proposed air-tightness measurement method in such a way that it could also be applied to buildings other than high-rise buildings. The differential pressure was measured under various conditions by varying the indoor and outdoor temperatures, considering low- and mid-rise buildings, and varying the number of floors in each building. The air-tightness was predicted using the measured differential pressure and was also measured using a blower door test at the same points where the differential pressure was measured for a suitable comparison of the results. The air-tightness was predicted using the method proposed in this Chapter 3, and n values are limited to be greater than 0.5 or less than 1.

At the same difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures, the dependence of the height difference on the predicted results was large. At the same height difference, as the value of the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperatures increased, the percentage errors of the predicted results tended to decrease. Based on the Pearson's correlation analysis of the differential pressure, the degree of influence of the height difference was greater than the temperature difference on the differential pressure. Similarly, it was found that, based on the Pearson's correlation analysis of the percentage errors of the predicted results, the percentage errors decreased as the height difference and differential pressure increased.

To generalize the air-tightness prediction method proposed in this study, the 95% confidence interval in the measured results was calculated using the blower door test. Based on the prediction results included in the 95% confidence interval for each building, the minimum differential pressure condition for all predicted results included in the 95% confidence interval was at least 24 Pa. Based on the applicable 24 Pa pressure, the acceptable condition in which the predicted and measured values were consistent for all buildings was found to be $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,000 \text{ m} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$. When the predicted results at the derived 95% confidence interval were statistically evaluated

using NMSE, FB, and FS, the values calculated for the proposed method met the criteria for adequate model performance. Synthetically, if a differential pressure of at least 24 Pa or more can be formed in all buildings, the air-tightness can be predicted by measuring only the differential pressure using a simple method proposed in this study, instead of a blower door test, which is difficult to implement in an actual environment and has a complicated measurement process. If the simple method proposed here is used to predict the air-tightness under actual building conditions, the accuracy of EUI and IAQ predictions can be further improved.

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논문요약

고층 주거건물의 공기유동 특성을 고려한

기밀성능 예측 방법의 제안

박 승 환

건설환경시스템공학과

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최근 건물들은 대부분 고층화됨에 따라 연돌효과가 극심해져 다양한 문제점들이 발생되고 있다. 이러한 문제점을 해결하기 위해 기밀시공 기법이 적용되고 있다. 이러한 기밀시공 기법이 적용됨에 따라 건물들은 고기밀화되고 있기 때문에 건물의 기밀성능을 정확히 파악하는 것이 매우 중요하다. 또한, 건물의 기밀성능은 실내 공기질 및 에너지 사용량과 밀접한 관련이 있기 때문에 건물의 기밀성능 측정은 반드시 이루어져야 한다. 기밀성능을 측정하는 대표적인 방법은 추적 가스법과 팬 가압법이 있다. 추적 가스법은 건물 전체의 기밀성능을 측정할 수 있지만 건물 요소의 기밀성능을 측정할 수 없다. 반면 건물 요소의 기밀성능은 팬 가압법의 대표적인 방법인 블로어 도어 테스트를 사용하여 측정할 수 있다. 그러나 블로어 도어 테스트는 복잡한 측정 준비 과정, 높은 비용, 측정 시 발생하는 문제점 등이 있다. 따라서 본 연구에서는 기존의 기밀성능 측정 방법의 문제점과

한계점을 해결할 수 있는 간단한 기밀성능 예측 방법을 제안하였다.

본 연구에서 제안한 새로운 기밀성능 예측 방법은 고층 주거 건물에서 연돌 효과에 의해 발생하는 차압을 이용한 것이다. 이 연구의 독창성은 블로어 도어 테스트와 같이 팬을 사용하여 풍량을 측정하는 것이 아니라 두 세트의 차압과 기밀성적서만을 이용하여 풍량을 산출하는 것이다. 본 연구의 전제조건은 연돌 효과로 인해 일정 수준의 차압이 형성되어야 하며, 하나의 기밀성적서가 확보되어야 한다. 또한, 본 연구에서는 실제 건물에서 적용할 수 있는 수식과 프로세스를 제안하였으며, 실제 건물을 대상으로 타당성을 검증하였다.

본 연구에서 제안한 방법을 일반화하기 위해 예측 결과와 비교 검증하였던 블로어 도어 실측 결과에 대한 가압 및 감압 결과의 95% 신뢰 구간을 도출 하였다. 도출된 95% 신뢰 구간에 해당되는 예측결과를 바탕으로 모든 예측 결과들이 실측결과와 일치되는 최소 차압은 24 Pa이었다. 그 차압을 기준으로, 기존 기밀성능 측정 기준에서 제시하고 있는 허용 조건에 대해 산출하였을 때, $\Delta H \times \Delta T < 1,000 \text{ m} \cdot \text{C}$ 이었다. 제안된 방법에 대해 ASTM Guide D5157-97에 제시된 지표인 NMSE, FB, FS 등을 사용하여 신뢰성을 검증하였으며, 제안된 방법은 적절한 모델 성능 기준을 충족하였다. 따라서, 모든 건물에서 위에서 제시된 차압 및 허용 조건을 만족할 수 있다면 실제 상황을 대별하기 어려운 블로어 도어 테스트 대신 간단한 방법으로 기밀성능을 예측할 수 있으며, 실제 건물 조건에서 기밀성능을 예측한다면 건물 에너지 사용량 및 실내 공기질 예측의 정확도를 더욱 높일 수 있을 것이다.

주제어: 기밀성능 예측, 차압, 주거건물, 실제 생활 조건, 외피